

Heterogeneous trust in reliable broadcast via modal logic and history structures

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Abstract

We propose a novel modal logic and semantics for specifying and proving properties of distributed full-information-transfer protocols (protocols that broadcast state to all participants in a distributed system). We use this to design and prove correctness of novel generalisations of Bracha’s ‘reliable broadcast’ algorithm to a heterogeneous trust setting (where distinct participants may have distinct trust assumptions); these proofs have been mechanically formalised and checked.

Keywords: Heterogeneous distributed systems ; Distributed Broadcast ; Bracha Broadcast ; Modal Logic ; Kripke semantics ; History Structures

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1. Introduction

1.1. The problem

This is a paper about modal logic applied to heterogeneous distributed protocols, so we will start by sketching what *modal logic*, *distributed protocol*, and *heterogeneous* mean, and why they matter.

A *modal logic* is a logic where the validity of its predicates may reference some notion of place or time. Instead of a judgement $\models \phi$ meaning ‘ ϕ is valid’, we have a judgement of the form $w \models \phi$ meaning ‘ ϕ is valid in some modal context w ’ [BdRV01].¹

¹If the reader is familiar with typing contexts and wonders how these differ from modal contexts, these are indeed both contexts, and an argument (out of scope for this paper) can be made that there is some technical overlap. But we hope the following intuitive rule might help: if your w helps you to type x , y , and z then it is probably a typing context; if your w tells you who you are, where you are, and/or what time it is, then this is probably a modal context. Readers who remain confused might pause reading to

Classic motivations for modalities include sentences like ‘it is raining’ (whose validity depends on where and when we are), or ‘I see rain’ (whose validity may additionally depend on who is making the claim), or ‘tomorrow, it will rain’, or ‘eventually, it will rain’ (which quantifies over future times), or ‘it rains everywhere sometime’ (which is ambiguous in English but can be disambiguated using the precision of ordering modal operators), and so on.²

In this paper, our modalities will refer to notions of place, time, and to quorums of participants (we explain quorums in a moment).

A *distributed protocol*, or synonymously a *distributed algorithm*, is a protocol/algorithm that runs over many participants [CGR11]. What makes the theory of distributed protocols different from that of parallel or concurrent ones is that in distributed protocols, some proportion of the participants may be *faulty*, by which we mean that they need not follow the protocol and may display arbitrary, possibly deliberately hostile, behaviour (a term *byzantine* is also well-established in the literature [LSP82]; we may use this synonymously with ‘faulty’).³

Distributed protocols gained their modern relevance when computers became networked in the 1980s (this is when Ethernet was invented). A machine on a network cannot necessarily vouch for the correctness of other machines on that network; the best it can do is proceed on a *failure assumption* that not too many of them are faulty (for some appropriate notion of ‘too many’) — and hope that this assumption is accurate. The subsequent developments of peer-to-peer protocols and blockchains — and other systems such that being distributed is part of the essential character of what that system is meant to accomplish — have made distributed systems an integral part of how modern computing works. Applied and theoretical research activity in distributed algorithms has grown accordingly.

The usual solution to the possibility of faulty participants, in general, is to treat a step in the protocol as completed only when some *quorum* of participants have attested to it. If we assume that quorums are large relative to the set of faulty participants then every quorum will contain a non-faulty (correct) participant⁴ — so that with this assumption, if we know that a quorum of participants agree on some output, then we can rely on the output being the result of a correct run of the protocol by *some* correct participant. It is simplistic but reasonably

look in the mirror, step outside, and go for a half-hour walk.

²How? $\diamond_{time} \square_{place}$ (it rains) means ‘there is a time when it rains at all places’ and $\square_{place} \diamond_{time}$ (it rains) means ‘at all places there exists a time where it rains’. Traditionally, the box symbol carries some meaning of all/everywhere/always and the diamond symbol carries some meaning of exists/somewhere/sometime. Thank you for asking.

³There are many subtly different notions of faulty/byzantine behaviour. This is material for an interesting discussion which is out-of-scope here, aside from emphasising that for us, by definition, ‘faulty’ will mean ‘might deviate arbitrarily from the protocol’.

⁴We have to make a *trust assumption* here; e.g. “up to a third of participants may be faulty, but no more”. If our trust assumptions are inaccurate, then behaviour can no longer be guaranteed. Such is life.

accurate to say that the typical distributed algorithm has the form ‘wait until we hear a quorum of participants return suitable messages, then proceed to our next relevant step on the assumption that at least one of them was an outcome of a correct run of the protocol thus far’.

A protocol is *heterogeneous* when different participants, or perhaps even the same participant at different times, might *differ on what sets they recognise as quorums*. In other words: in a heterogeneous protocol, the notion of ‘trust’ (as expressed by what quorums participants assume may be trustworthy) may vary with time and/or participant.

It is now time for some definitions:

DEFINITION 1.1.1. Assume \mathbf{P} some set of **participants** in a distributed algorithm. A **quorum system** $\mathcal{O} \subseteq \text{powerset}(\mathbf{P})$ is some set of sets of participants in a distributed algorithm. We call each $O \in \mathcal{O}$ a **quorum**. We may also call \mathcal{O} a **trust assumption**, a **semifilter**, or a **learner**.

DEFINITION 1.1.2. A **heterogeneous** distributed algorithm is such that several trust assumptions are present, and which is used may potentially vary by time and participant. In other words, we have not one quorum system \mathcal{O} , but some nonempty set of them: $\mathbb{O} = \{\mathcal{O}_1, \dots, \mathcal{O}_n\} \subseteq \text{powerset}(\text{powerset}(\mathbf{P}))$.⁵

REMARK 1.1.3. Heterogeneity is a natural phenomenon which arises along axes of both space and time:

1. Multiple distributed systems — possibly with overlapping participants, but each with their own community identity — may seek to interact. There is not one national voting system; there are several. There is not one bank; there are many. There is not one blockchain; there are more than one. There is not one local council or residents’ committee or family; there are multitudes. All these systems may be more or less successful within themselves, but for practical outcomes it matters just as much how smoothly they can interact, across their different trust assumptions.
2. A single participant may revise its quorum system over time. Real-life examples of this include a change of citizenship, political leanings, or indeed our natural changes in our groups of friends with time. Whom we are friends with or trust when we are children may differ from whom we are friends with or trust when we are adolescents or adults.

It is a truism that the world is distributed, but more than that, the world is *heterogeneously* distributed. As mathematicians, we should build maths to model this, so we can describe ...

⁵In a real-world system, all these sets are finite, but unless stated otherwise, our discussion will not depend on this.

REMARK 1.1.4 (This paper in a nutshell).

1. We develop a logic enriched with modalities for talking about *participants* (places), *times*, participants' *knowledge* at each particular place and time, and rich *modal properties* having to do with *heterogeneous quorums and quorum intersections*.
2. We apply our logic to invent and prove correctness properties of heterogeneous generalisations of Bracha's reliable broadcast algorithm (see next Subsection): ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3, each of which is interesting in its own right.
3. The definitions and proofs in this paper have been formalised in the Lean 4 theorem prover, complete with clear instructions for use and with clear and precise linkages between the results in this paper and their formalised Lean code. The interested reader can download the files [Har25] and run the verification locally.

REMARK 1.1.5. We have already stated that a heterogeneous distributed system is just one where multiple notions of quorum are in use. Even at this early stage, and even before we have set up the mathematics, it is useful to unpack some implications of this.

Consider that Ethereum (a homogeneous system) bridged with Bitcoin (another homogeneous system) is heterogeneous (because Ethereum and Bitcoin have distinct quorums); and XRP Ledger (a heterogeneous system) bridged with Ethereum is also heterogeneous. These observations reflect that homogeneity is not a naturally compositional property, whereas heterogeneity is naturally compositional: a combination of two homogeneous systems is (most likely) heterogeneous, and if we combine a heterogeneous system with any other system, we get another heterogeneous system. Thus, going from homogeneity to heterogeneity is easy; remaining homogeneous (as a system scales up and interacts with other systems) is hard; reversing heterogeneity once established is *very* hard, and may be impossible.

So to the reader who may be inclined to think of being heterogeneous as somehow an edge case, we would say: no. Homogeneity is the edge case. Heterogeneity is the natural state of affairs. This is how the world *is*.

A state where everyone agrees on trust assumptions is an important special case, but it is not always a natural state of affairs, and even if we attain such agreement momentarily, the inherent noncompositonality of this agreement means that it may be difficult or impossible to maintain.

1.2. A nontrivial test bench: Bracha Broadcast

A seminal distributed algorithm is **Bracha Broadcast (BB)**, introduced in a paper by Bracha [Bra87] (Bracha called it *reliable broadcast* there). In the homogeneous case as considered by Bracha — so there is one, globally agreed,

quorum system — this solves the problem of how a proposer can broadcast a value across the network, such that correct participants agree on the value proposed. BB has three correctness properties, which we sketch as follows (these are not mathematical statements, yet):

- *Liveness 1* If there is a quorum of correct participants (meaning: all participants in the quorum are live and correctly follow the protocol)⁶ and precisely one value v is proposed, then that correct quorum eventually concludes v .
- *Liveness 2* If there is a quorum of correct participants and one participant in that quorum concludes v , then all participants in that quorum eventually conclude v .
- *Soundness / Agreement* If two correct participants conclude v and v' respectively, then $v = v'$.

Note above that we write ‘there is a quorum’, without specifying *who* decides what a quorum is. This is because it is assumed that everyone agrees on this; Bracha’s trust assumptions where what we here call *homogeneous*.

It turns out that many heterogeneous generalisations of Bracha’s reliable broadcast exist, and we will introduce three of them, which between them triangulate in a rich design space. We will state precise analogues of the liveness 1, liveness 2, and soundness properties later (see Figures 8, 10, and 12); the above is just to give the reader a flavour.

1.3. Why broadcast? Why a new logic? Why heterogeneity?

Other distributed problems exist, including for example Consensus. Why focus on Broadcast in this paper

Broadcast is arguably a canonical simplest nontrivial distributed algorithm, and research shows how Consensus can be built on top of it [Bra87, Section 4, “The Consensus Protocol”].⁷

⁶The pedantic reader (including the first author, when he was first introduced to these concepts) might now ask: but what do ‘live’ and ‘correctly follow the protocol’ mean *precisely*? Intuitively these concepts are clear enough for this introductory exposition, but what do they actually *mean*? Such a reader is in luck, because logic excels at giving precise mathematical form(s) to compelling but informal concepts. See Subsection 5.2.

⁷For the interested reader, section 3 of [CGR11] contains an exhaustive survey of broadcast algorithms, all making different safety assumptions and delivering different correctness guarantees. In particular *crusader agreement* [Dol82] stands out as arguably simpler than Bracha Broadcast, and it has a termination property which our algorithms will not have — but only because it makes a strong assumption which we do not wish to make, of assuming a globally synchronous network (messages arrive reliably and on time). Arguably, a globally synchronous network makes less sense in a heterogeneous setting, because this is a global trust assumption on the network, and we do not want a crash in one trust system to prevent progress of another.

So perhaps we should say that Bracha Broadcast is *a simplest nontrivial useful distributed algorithm that makes sense (to us) in a heterogeneous setting*. See Footnote 8.

Thus, Heterogeneous Bracha Broadcast (HBB) is a kind of universal building block, a useful test subject, and a convenient place to start. It is simple enough to be accessible, and expressive enough to be useful.⁸

Furthermore, it turns out that Bracha’s reliable broadcast algorithm is a useful and fruitful object of study because it admits multiple, and multiple interesting, generalisations to the heterogeneous case.

Other logics exist for specifying distributed algorithms. Why design a new one

Our logic will let us specify and reason about distributed algorithms declaratively: in our analysis an algorithm is an axiomatic theory, and a run of the algorithm is a model of that theory. We mean by *declarative* that we elide details of *control flow* and *evaluation order* — where we deem these inessential, which is surprisingly often — so we can focus on the essence of what the protocol is.

This method, which follows a thread of previous research [GZ25], yields simplifications that are analogous to what we see moving from programming in a low-level imperative language to a higher-level functional or logic programming language: more compact assertions, less control flow, less worrying about evaluation order, and more (and more clear) high-level specification of what the program *does*.

So one answer to the question above is: because it works well.

But there are also two things going on in the logic we use in this paper, which are specific to this paper in particular.

1. Its logical modalities are tailored to talk about heterogeneous quorums and quorum intersections; see the three modalities \downarrow , \uparrow , and \diamond in Figure 3 and their semantics. This yields a compact but expressive logic with which we will be able to concisely and precisely express complex reasoning on our three algorithms.

This is so effective that once we have things set up, our correctness proofs can just proceed by symbolic manipulation (so-called ‘symbol

⁸Bracha’s reliable broadcast may be simple (at least in the tautological sense that it is simpler than more complex protocols) but this belies its considerable expressive power. It suffices to update state in several types of distributed systems, including cryptocurrencies (although many of them unnecessarily use Consensus, which is stronger) [GKM⁺19].

Broadcast has *consensus number 1*, meaning it can be used to update a distributed register despite byzantine failures, with the caveat that an entry may get stuck (never update again) if two simultaneous updates are proposed [Her91]. For a cryptocurrency account, this should only happen if owner of that entry (i.e. the account holder) misbehaves. This might freeze that owner’s account, but it would not affect the rest of the system.

Sui generalises this to a notion of *owned objects*, which can update much more quickly and easily (using broadcast) than the rest of Sui’s state (which uses consensus). If an object’s owner misbehaves then that object can become stuck (to the presumed detriment of the object’s misbehaving owner), but other objects, and the rest of Sui’s state, are unaffected and do not become stuck [BCD⁺24].

pushing’). The proof of Proposition 6.4.5 is a case in point. The notation might take a bit of getting used to, but the proof is succinct and precise — and the other proofs are basically just minor variations of it. This is a feature, because it is *good* when correctness proofs are short, routine, and predictable.

2. Second, and furthermore, we use a novel epsilon-inductive notion of time⁹ which we call *History Structures*. In a history structure, the time of an event is equal to the set of events that have happened before that event. We mean this literally. Time is not a number or a vector of numbers (cf. Lamport clocks [Lam78] or vector clocks [SM94, RS96]).¹⁰ For us, time is literally a set of past events, which themselves are indexed by times that are sets of past events, and so on.

The slogan is that

time is equal precisely to *that which has happened before*.

It turns out that this interacts elegantly and naturally with our logical methodology and axiomatisation, as we shall see.

Why heterogeneous distributed algorithms matter

Heterogeneity reflects the following question:

how, and in what mathematical circumstances, can distinct communities collaborate, even if they have distinct trust assumptions?

Heterogeneity can provide diversity and resilience, in that different communities can make different choices and yet still interact, and the overall system can continue operating (in a suitable sense) even when some communities may fail.

In order for heterogeneous trust systems to compete on the basis of user-facing experience and simplicity with ones featuring a single homogeneous trust assumption, the system overall must be able to automate the accounting of managing multiple trust systems, such that two users with trust preferences compatible in the actual course of history can interact as if they were using a homogeneous system. In the ideal case, the system would be as easy to use as a centralised one that relies on a single trusted party who behaved as expected — even though it actually is composed of multiple communities with multiple trust assumptions, all stitched together in some mathematical way. So the challenge is how, and in what circumstances, we might reduce the differential user-facing complexity cost of a heterogeneous trust system to nearly zero.

⁹Epsilon-inductive’ is fancy set-theoretic jargon for saying that something is built from sets, or sets of sets, or sets of sets of sets, and so on. See Definition 2.2.4, which is visibly epsilon-inductive because it builds a prehistory as a set of things that themselves contain prehistories.

¹⁰Vector clocks seem to have been independently invented by several people during the 1980s. The surveys [SM94, RS96] includes historical comments in footnote 3 on page 6, and on page 4, respectively.

Our three protocols give three partial, preliminary, but precise and rigorous answers to that question, and our logic gives a methodology for validating their correctness and, perhaps, for designing more protocols in future.

1.4. Map of the paper

1. We begin in Section 1 with the Introduction. You Are Here.
2. In Section 2 we introduce *history structures*. This inductive structure gives us our notion of time: a moment in time consists by definition of the collection of events that have happened before that time. The key definitions are Definitions 2.2.4 (prehistories) and 2.3.5 (history structures).
3. In Section 3 we develop the syntax and semantics of a modal logic for specifying and reasoning about distributed algorithms. The key definitions are in Figures 2 (syntax) and 3 (validity).
4. In Section 4 we explore the modal structure of our logic, which gives us a rich choice of modalities for talking about quorums and quorum intersections. This is not a long Section but it focusses on one of the most distinctive features of our logic, which is also key to its intended application of declaratively specifying and reasoning about heterogeneous distributed protocols.
5. In Section 5 we discuss the two canonical correctness properties for participants: *sequentiality* and *liveness*.

A participant is sequential when (intuitively) it experiences linear time. Recall that our model of time is *that which has happened before*, so sequentiality excludes *equivocation*; telling different and incompatible things to other participants.

In blockchain terminology, sequentiality corresponds roughly to *not forking*, which is arguably *the* canonical correctness property that a blockchain should preserve. Sequentiality is thus a form of non-forking consistency, for participants.

A participant is live when it is correct (= follows the protocol) and always eventually progresses the protocol where possible (= does not crash). In a nutshell we can write:

Live = Correct/non-faulty + Non-crashing.

It turns out that we can express liveness formally as a logical theory (Figure 6).

6. We now have enough to axiomatise and prove correctness properties of our three heterogeneous broadcast protocols, ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3. We do this in Sections 6, 7, and 8.
7. We then conclude with the Conclusions in Section 9.

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2. History structures and their logic

2.1. A brief discussion using programming terminology

This work is theoretical but we still want it to be accessible to programmers who might implement it, so before we define prehistories (Definition 2.2.4) and history structures (Definition 2.3.5), we will present the idea of history structures as an inductive datatype in the style of functional programming. Then, we will explain why we do not just take that inductive datatype as our definition.

Intuitively, a history structure is a polymorphic datatype of finitely-branching trees labelled with uninterpreted types of *places* and *events*, along with a ‘descendent of’ relation on these trees.

We define this in Haskell style as follows:

```
import Data.Set as S
data History p e = History p (Maybe e) (S.Set (History p e)) deriving (Eq,Ord)
isDesc h (History p e l) = (S.member h l) || or (S.map (isDesc h) l)
:t isDesc
isDesc :: (Ord p, Ord e) => History p e -> History p e -> Bool
```

Each node of the tree is labelled by a place and a maybe-event, and it may have finitely many children in a list. *Being a descendent of* is defined (as usual) as the transitive closure of child-of.

This definition is short and clear, and it may be especially palatable to readers with a coding background (though perhaps less so to set theorists). A problem with this datatype is that it is highly redundant: many distinct trees in `History` `pe` correspond to the same intended history structure. Consider for example:

```
h0 = History 0 Nothing (S.empty)
h1 = History 0 Nothing (S.singleton h0)
h2 = History 0 Nothing (S.singleton h1)
h2b = History 0 Nothing (S.fromList [h1,h0])
```

Then `h2` and `h2b` are extensionally equal — they have the same descendants — but they are not intensionally identical — they are different elements of the datatype.

If we are doing mathematics, we deprecate such redundancy: for each thing in our intended domain, we want our mathematical model to contain a *single* element that represents *that thing*.¹¹ Therefore we will now repeat the definitions in mathematical style.

The resulting Definitions 2.2.4 and 2.3.5 are more verbose, but the sets representation has no redundancies and will be mathematically easier to work with.

If the reader does not mind redundancy (and perhaps is fluent in Haskell) then they can take the code above as primitive and little harm will come of it.

2.2. Prehistories

2.2.1. Finite subsets and maybe-sets

We start with some basic notation:

NOTATION 2.2.1. Suppose X and Y are sets. Define $X \subseteq_{fin} Y$, read **X is a finite subset of Y** , by

$$X \subseteq_{fin} Y \quad \text{when} \quad X \subseteq Y \text{ and } X \text{ is finite.}$$

Note that X may be empty, so $\emptyset \subseteq_{fin} Y$ always.

NOTATION 2.2.2. Suppose X is a set. Define X_{\downarrow} , read **maybe- X** , by

$$X_{\downarrow} = X \cup \{\downarrow\}$$

where \downarrow is an uninterpreted disjoint element $\downarrow \notin X$.

REMARK 2.2.3. In mathematics, X_{\downarrow} is traditionally written X_{\perp} and the adjoined element is written \perp . In programming, the set is typically written `Maybe(X)` and the adjoined element is `Nothing`. The intuition is the same: to provide a

¹¹The first author has a motto: Quotient sets are a sign of failure.

default value that is not already in X — e.g. for when we have a function and want it to (mostly) return values from X , but occasionally to return some non- X return value.

We use the symbol \downarrow because upside-down-T-like symbols are already well-represented in our text: we use \perp for meta-level logical false, and \perp for the false symbol in our logic (see Figure 2).

2.2.2. Definition of prehistories

DEFINITION 2.2.4 (Prehistories). Assume \mathbf{P} a nonempty set of *places* — we may synonymously call these *points* or *participants* — and \mathbf{Event} a disjoint set of *events*.¹²

Let $\mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$, the set of **prehistories** over \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Event} , be the least set closed under the following rule:

$$\frac{H \subseteq_{fin} \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})}{H \in \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})}$$

In words:

Any finite (possibly empty) set of place-(maybe-event)-prehistory tuples, is a prehistory.

EXAMPLE 2.2.5. Two prehistories are illustrated in Figure 1. (These examples are also history structures, which we will define shortly.)

DEFINITION 2.2.6. We need some definitions:

1. Call a triple $(p, x, H) \in \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$, an **event-tuple**. Calling it a ‘maybe-event tuple’ would be more precise, but that is longer to say, so we abbreviate it to just ‘event-tuple’.
2. Given an event-tuple $w = (p, x, H) \in \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$, we define

$$place(w) = p \quad event(w) = x \quad \text{and} \quad time(w) = H.$$

We call $place(w)$ the **place** of w , $event(w)$ its **(maybe-)event**, and $time(w)$ its **time**.

3. We may call a prehistory a **time** (as per the previous item). For our purposes we will be most interested in *histories*, which are times that satisfy an additional well-formedness condition of being *hereditarily transitive* (Definition 2.3.5). However, we can already make a point here about prehistories, that if these are our notion of time then the only thing we will care about in that notion of time is *that which has happened before*.

¹²For this definition, we do not care about the internal structure of places and events. If we have in mind to implement them then we might want them to be recursively enumerable, but the definition and mathematics do not require that.

This is so important that we will say it again: a prehistory is a set of events, so taking this as our notion of ‘time’ is to promise that all we care about of a time, is the set of events that happened before that time. See also Remark 2.3.7.

4. If H and H' are prehistories then write that H' **precedes** H when $H' \subseteq H$. Note that this notion is *non-strict*, in the sense that H precedes itself.
5. We may say that H **knows of** an event-tuple $w = (p', x', H')$ when $w \in H$.

REMARK 2.2.7. By the Kleene fixpoint theorem [Wik25] $\text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$ is characterised by

$$\begin{aligned} F(X) &= \text{fin}(\mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times X) \\ \text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event}) &= \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{N}} F^i(\emptyset), \end{aligned}$$

and $\text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$ is the least set such that

$$\text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event}) = F(\text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})).$$

The restriction to *finite* powersets on the right-hand side is just to keep things simple; we plan to model finite runs of distributed algorithms, so finite subsets suffice. The mathematics would easily generalise: we would take countable subsets or recursively enumerable subsets and nothing in our proofs would change. We could even take arbitrary subsets.¹³

2.3. History structures

2.3.1. Definition

A history structure is just a hereditarily transitive prehistory. We give the relevant definitions:

DEFINITION 2.3.1 (Element-of relation). Suppose $H, H' \in \text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$.

1. Define $H' \prec H$ by

$$H' \prec H \quad \text{when } \exists p' \in \mathbf{P}, x' \in \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}. H' \in H.$$

When $H' \prec H$ we may call H' an **element** of H . Intuitively, $H' \prec H$ when H' is the time of some event-tuple in H .

2. Define $H' \preceq H$ by

$$H' \preceq H \quad \text{when } H' \prec H \vee H' = H.$$

When $H' \preceq H$ we may call H' a **non-strict element** of H .

¹³... but then prehistories would become a *proper class*, in the set-theoretic sense [Jec06, page 6] — this is a collection of elements that is too large to be a set, e.g. the ‘collection of all sets’ is not itself a set, at least if we are working in a Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory. This discussion is out of scope for this paper, so ... we just use finite powersets.

DEFINITION 2.3.2. Call a prehistory $H \in \text{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \text{Event})$ **transitive** when

$$H' \prec H \implies H' \subsetneq H \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad H' \preceq H \implies H' \subseteq H.$$

In words: if H' is a (strict/non-strict) element of H then H' is a (strict/non-strict) subset of H .

REMARK 2.3.3. Unpacking Definition 2.3.1(1), transitivity just means:

$$\forall p', x'. ((p', x', H') \in H \implies H' \subsetneq H).$$

Strictness of the inclusion (i.e. that $H' \neq H$) follows from well-foundedness of sets, that $(p', x', H') \in H$ and $H' = H$ is impossible.¹⁴

We can sum this up in words with two equivalent slogans:

H is transitive when it is preceded (Definition 2.2.6(4)) by the time of every event-tuple that it contains.

Or, more compactly:

Transitive H is preceded by its elements.

REMARK 2.3.4. A practical motivation for transitivity is that it models an idea of *full information*: if H knows of an event (p', x', H') in the sense of Definition 2.2.6(5) that $(p', x', H') \in H$, then H also knows of the full circumstances in which (p', x', H') took place, namely H knows of every event-tuple in H' .

We do not expect a practical protocol to necessarily carry full information *but* mathematically, reasoning about a full information protocol lets us reason about what *can* be done. We can then reduce to exactly what things participants have to derive from their own memory and messages in order to make a given protocol work. Transitivity reflects this idealisation.¹⁵

¹⁴Note for set theorists: impossible in a well-founded set theory.

In Definition 2.2.4 we define a prehistory as an inductive datatype built up using sets membership. The set theorists' term for that is *inductively defined epsilon-structure*. This is almost exactly the same thing as what a programmer would call *an inductively defined data structure*, the only difference being that sets come natively with some algebraic identities, for example $X \cup X = X$ and $X \cup Y = Y \cup X$. These are *sets*, and for our needs the identities that come with this fact will be helpful.

However, what makes the epsilon-structure *inductive* — so making $(p', x', H') \in H$ and $H' = H$ impossible — is the *Axiom of Foundation* [Joh87, page 61]. If we were in a non-wellfounded set theory [Acz88] then we would not have Foundation, and $(p', x', H') \in H$ and $H' = H$ would be possible. (Even in a well-founded set theory we can build non-wellfounded data structures; we just have to define a bespoke membership relation for this, rather than co-opting the ambient sets membership \in .)

So to fully unpack the strictness in $H' \subsetneq H$, it works like this: we build our datatype of prehistory structures inductively using \in and we assume a well-founded set theory and therefore $(p', x', H') \in H$ and $H' = H$ are impossible.

¹⁵In other applications we might want the precise opposite, i.e. *information hiding*. That is a topic in itself, which is out of scope here. This could be accommodated in our framework; impose suitable axioms that precisely *contradict* transitivity (we control the definition; we can impose whatever axioms we like). Thus, whether we insist on transitivity or perhaps insist on properties that contradict it, either way, this property is an important reference point.

DEFINITION 2.3.5 (History structures). Define **History**(P, Event) the set of **history structures**

$$\text{History}(P, \text{Event}) \subseteq \text{PreHistory}(P, \text{Event})$$

to be the set of **hereditarily transitive** elements in **PreHistory**(P, Event), by which we mean that this is the greatest set of prehistories such that

$H \in \text{History}(P, \text{Event})$ implies H transitive $\wedge \forall H' \prec H. (H' \in \text{History}(P, \text{Event}))$.

NOTATION 2.3.6. Recall from Definition 2.2.6(3) that we call a prehistory a *time*. Henceforth, all times will be hereditarily transitive unless stated otherwise — i.e. all times are histories (Definition 2.3.5). Indeed, henceforth if the reader sees the symbol H then they can assume it is a history (not just a prehistory), unless stated otherwise.

This should always be clear from context.

REMARK 2.3.7. The following observation might help the reader to parse the meaning of (pre)history structures from Definitions 2.2.4 and 2.3.5.

In an event-tuple p, x, H , the H is three things simultaneously:

- a full epsilon-structure of events preceding the event-tuple,
- now (i.e. the moment in time when the event ‘occurs’), and
- (for histories, by transitivity) a full record of what p knows at the time this event-tuple occurs.

These are all equated in the strong sense that they are *literally equal*. We can sum this up as follows:

H = the past (= a set of event-tuples) = now = what we know.

This ‘epistemic’ approach to time is novel, to the best of our knowledge.¹⁶ Existing approaches treat time as an exogenous concept, i.e. there is a clock and it tells us what time it is, typically as a (possibly structured) timestamp [Lam78, SM94, RS96] (a number or a vector of numbers). Obviously, if time is a timestamp then we can talk about what has happened before that timestamp, or what an agent knows at that timestamp.

For our purposes this level of indirection is not needed. There are no timestamps. Time is simply that which has happened before.

2.3.2. Discussion and examples

EXAMPLE 2.3.8 (Illustrating history structures). A history structure can be represented as a directed acyclic graph, or as a derivation tree. Of the two we

¹⁶Epistemic: *relating to knowledge*. We discuss the relation of our logic to purpose-built epistemic logics, i.e. ones with modalities for reasoning directly about knowledge, in Subsection 9.3.

$$(1) \frac{\frac{p \vdash \text{print}(\text{hello})}{p \vdash \text{print}(\text{world})}}{p \vdash \text{exit}()} \quad (2) \frac{\frac{p \vdash \text{print}(\text{hello})}{p \vdash \text{exit}()} \quad \frac{p \vdash \text{print}(\text{world})}{p \vdash \text{exit}()}}{p \vdash \text{exit}()}$$

$$(1) \left\{ (p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset), \right. \\ \left. (p, \text{print}(\text{world}), \{(p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset)\}), \right. \\ \left. (p, \text{exit}(), \{(p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset), \right. \\ \left. (p, \text{print}(\text{world}), \{(p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset)\})\}) \right\}$$

$$(2) \left\{ (p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset), (p, \text{print}(\text{world}), \emptyset), \right. \\ \left. (p, \text{exit}(), \{(p, \text{print}(\text{world}), \emptyset), (p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset)\}) \right\}$$

Figure 1. Illustrating (pre)history structures (Examples 2.2.5 and 2.3.8)

will favour a derivation tree style, just because there are particularly convenient LaTeX packages for typesetting these.

Figure 1 presents two history structures. Above are derivation-tree style presentations, and below are corresponding history structure written out in full. We assume events `print` and `exit` and just one participant p . The two examples represent two sequencings of events `print(hello)`, `print(world)`, and `exit()`.

In the first history:

- p sends `hello` to stout (standard output) at time $H_0 = \emptyset$,
- p sends `world` to stout at time $H_1 = \{(p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), H_0)\}$, and then
- p stops at time $H_2 = \{(p, \text{print}(\text{world}), \emptyset), (p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), \emptyset)\}$.

In the second history,

- p sends `hello` to stout at time $H_0 = \emptyset$,
- p sends `world` to stout at the *same* time $H_0 = \emptyset$, and then
- p stops at time $H_1 = \{(p, \text{print}(\text{world}), H_0), (p, \text{print}(\text{hello}), H_0)\}$.

Obviously the derivation-tree presentation is more readable, but the sets definition is definitive and is what we use to do the mathematics.

EXAMPLE 2.3.9. Here is a simple example of a prehistory P that is not a history structure:

$$P = \{ (p, \dagger, \{(p, \dagger, \emptyset)\}) \}.$$

P is not a history because it is not transitive: $(p, \dagger, \{(p, \dagger, \emptyset)\}) \in P$ yet $\{(p, \dagger, \emptyset)\} \notin P$.

EXAMPLE 2.3.10. Example 2.3.8 only involved one participant. What if we have more? We demonstrate this with a simple message-passing example. Assume *two* participants p and q , and two actions `propose` and `accept` which we will treat as 0-ary. Here are two example history structures in which p takes action `propose()` and then q takes action `accept()`. We indicate participants with $p \vdash$ and $q \vdash$:

$$\frac{p \vdash \text{propose}()}{q \vdash \text{accept}()} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash \text{propose}(), q \vdash \text{accept}()}$$

The difference is that in the left-hand history, q knows that p has proposed before it accepts; whereas in the right-hand history it does not. Here are the corresponding history structures in full: In the left-hand history:

- p proposes at time $H_0 = \emptyset$.
- q accepts at time $H_1 = \{(p, \text{propose}(), H_0)\}$.
- The full history structure is $\mathbb{H} = \{(q, \text{accept}(), H_1), H_1\}$.

In the right-hand history:

- p proposes at time $H_0 = \emptyset$.
- q accepts at the same time H_0 .
- The full history structure is $\mathbb{H} = \{(q, \text{accept}(), H_0), (p, \text{propose}(), H_0)\}$.

Finally, we illustrate a simple history where p proposes and then q learns that p has proposed:

$$\frac{p \vdash \text{propose}()}{q \vdash \downarrow}$$

Here is the corresponding history structure written in full:

$$\{(p, \text{propose}(), \emptyset), (q, \downarrow, \{(p, \text{propose}(), \emptyset)\})\}$$

History structures are rich and complex, but structurally the examples above represent everything that can happen. The complexity just follows from scaling up.

2.3.3. Element-transitivity

We mention that an alternative notion of transitivity on prehistories to that in Definition 2.3.2 is possible, but it will be too weak for our needs here:

DEFINITION 2.3.11. Call $H \in \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$ **element-transitive** when for every $H', H'' \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$,

$$H'' \prec H' \wedge H' \prec H \quad \text{implies} \quad H'' \prec H.$$

LEMMA 2.3.12. *Suppose $H \in \mathbf{PreHistory}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$. Then:*

1. If H is transitive (Definition 2.3.2) then it is element-transitive (Definition 2.3.11).
2. The reverse implication need not hold: it is possible for H to be element-transitive but not transitive.
3. Every $H \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$ is element-transitive.

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. Suppose $H'' \prec H' \prec H$. Then $H' \subseteq H$ by Definition 2.3.2 (transitivity of H). The reader can check from Definition 2.3.1(1) that $H'' \prec H' \subseteq H$ implies $H'' \prec H$, so we are done.
2. It suffices to provide a counterexample. Take $\mathbf{P} = \{p, q\}$ (so there are two participants) and $\mathbf{Event} = \emptyset$ (so the only maybe-event is \downarrow):

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \{(p, \downarrow, \emptyset)\} \\ H_2 &= \{(p, \downarrow, H_1), (q, \downarrow, \emptyset)\} \end{aligned}$$

Here is an illustration in derivation tree style:

$$\frac{\frac{}{p \vdash \downarrow}}{p \vdash \downarrow} \quad \frac{}{q \vdash \downarrow}}{p \vdash \downarrow}$$

Then H_2 is trivially element-transitive and $H_1 \prec H_2$, yet $H_1 \not\subseteq H_2$.

3. By construction in Definition 2.3.5, $H \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$ is transitive. We use part 1 of this result. \square

2.3.4. Discussion of nothing: \downarrow

The end of time, and initial and final event-tuples. Discussing nothing requires us to build a little bit of machinery:¹⁷

DEFINITION 2.3.13. Fix $\mathbb{H} \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$. Then:

1. We may call \mathbb{H} the **end of time** in \mathbb{H} , because every $H \prec \mathbb{H}$ precedes it (Definition 2.2.6(4)) by transitivity (Definition 2.3.2).
2. Call an event-tuple $(p, x, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ **initial/p-initial** when H in \mathbb{H} is \prec -least / \prec -least among tuples starting with p .
3. Call an event-tuple $(p, x, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ **final/p-final** when H in \mathbb{H} is \prec -final / \prec -final among tuples starting with p .

REMARK 2.3.14. Initial and final event-tuples need not exist (the empty history $\mathbb{H} = \emptyset$ has neither), and if they exist they need not be unique (the right-hand history in Example 2.3.10 has two of each).

Note that if $(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ then $H = \mathbb{H}$ is impossible, so the end of time cannot be the time of an event-tuple in \mathbb{H} , and in particular \mathbb{H} is never the time of a final event-tuple.

¹⁷We are mathematicians, so we appreciate that careers — good ones — have been made from studying nothing.

The problem: final event-tuples. Why do we use $\mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$ to build (pre)history structures in Definitions 2.2.4 and 2.3.5, instead of just \mathbf{Event} ? This is motivated by the design of the Knowledge axiom-schemes (Knowledge \diamond) and (Knowledge \square) in the theory of liveness ThyLive in Figure 6.

We will discuss these axioms in detail in Subsection 5.2. What matters here is that they express that live participants communicate information to one another; if some information ϕ becomes known to some live participant p , then eventually every other live participant will know that someone (namely: p) knew ϕ .

The technical difficulty is that a history structure \mathbb{H} is a finite set of event-tuples, so there is such a thing as a *final event-tuple*. As per Definition 2.3.13(3), this is a triple $(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ such that H is \leftarrow -maximal in \mathbb{H} .

If our notion of history is *only* mapped out in terms of event-tuples — i.e. if \mathbb{H} consists *only* of triples (p, E, H) where $E \in \mathbf{Event}$ — then this final event cannot be communicated, because another participant learning of this event would have to itself be an event, which would come later than the final event, contradicting finality of the final event.

\downarrow : **the solution.** Broadly speaking we have the following options:

1. We can accept this infinite regression and make history structures infinite: I did E ; you learned that I did E ; I learned that you learned that I did E , ...
We have nothing against infinities but here this feels like a hack, because it does not correspond to how we think of distributed algorithms actually behaving.
2. We can tweak the meaning of our temporal modalities, or perhaps tweak ThyLive.
3. We can introduce \downarrow and maybe-events $\mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$ as defined above. This is what we do.

Thus we permit a triple (p, \downarrow, H) in a participant's history. This \downarrow -event-tuple does not record an event — in the technical sense that the event-tuple has \downarrow in its second entry, which is not in the set of events \mathbf{Event} — but it *does* represent an H -update to the view that p has of history.

We can think of this as corresponding roughly to p receiving a message, e.g. as per a Lamport diagram [Lam78, Figure 1].¹⁸

Now suppose (p, E, H) is a final event in \mathbb{H} . If we have \downarrow , then the model can continue to evolve such that this event becomes known to another participant q ,

¹⁸Though Lamport considers receiving a message to be an event, and we do not. Just under Figure 1, Lamport writes “We assume that sending or receiving a message is an event in a process”. Indeed, traditionally in distributed systems receiving a message is considered an event. We classify things a little differently to avoid infinite regression and to permit finite nonempty history structures and the existence of final events.

by adding a tuple $(q, \downarrow, \{(p, E, H), H\})$. This is not technically an event. It is a *maybe-event*, which reflects q becoming aware of (p, E, H) .

2.3.5. Further discussion of nothing

REMARK 2.3.15 (\downarrow viewed as a receive action). We can think of \downarrow as a generalisation of the notion of a ‘receive’ action, as follows:

Let us view $E \in \mathbf{Event}$ as a broadcast event, so that (p, E, H) means ‘ p broadcasts E at time H ’. Then we can view \downarrow as a receive action, where $(p', \downarrow, H \cup \{(p, E, H)\})$ is the time when information arrives at p' that (p, E, H) happened.

Note that, following this analogy, not every ‘receive’ action needs to be via \downarrow . For instance, we can have $(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ and also $(p', E', H \cup \{(p, E, H)\}) \in \mathbb{H}$. By our analogy, this corresponds to p broadcasting E and then p' broadcasting E' at the same time as it receives the broadcast from p .¹⁹

Nevertheless, we still need \downarrow in order to account for a final broadcast event, so that participants can learn of this event and update their local history without themselves broadcasting another event.

Note that this Remark is just an analogy: history structures, events, and \downarrow are their own thing.

REMARK 2.3.16 (\downarrow viewed as an ϵ transition). In the theories of automata there is a notion of automaton making a *silent* or *internal* transition. Traditionally these are called ϵ -transitions [HMU07, Subsection 2.5, “Finite Automata With Epsilon-Transitions”].

The traditional reading of this is an internal state change that does not involve interaction with the environment.

A difficulty with interpreting \downarrow as a receive action, as we do in Remark 2.3.15, is that there is no restriction on an event-tuple (p, \downarrow, H) that H should contain information that is somewhere in the rest of some larger history for p to ‘receive’. H could be arbitrary.

In this sense, it also makes sense to think of \downarrow simply as an internal transition of p , more akin to the automata-theoretic ϵ action.

Yet \downarrow is not *just* a silent internal action without interaction with the environment, because H *could also* contain information that *is* in the rest of some larger history, e.g. when we interpret it as a receive action. So we repeat the final line of Remark 2.3.16: history structures, events, and \downarrow are their own thing.

REMARK 2.3.17 (\downarrow viewed as an attestation). Perhaps a better way to think of \downarrow is as marking a pure attestation: when $(p, \downarrow, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ this means that p *attests* to knowing of time H and the information encoded therein.

¹⁹Think of this in the style of Mealy machines, in which every step has to receive a message, update state, and send a message.

Of course $(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ also means that p attests to knowing of H , but that happens in the sense that an event E occurs at p at time H . In contrast, (p, \downarrow, H) is a pure attestation; p might have received the information that the time H exists from the environment, or p might have computed the time H internally. In this sense, \downarrow generalises both *receive* and ϵ : it represents the act of attesting to some internal state change of knowledge, and in our model, knowledge and time are the same thing.

REMARK 2.3.18. It is perfectly feasible to have

$$(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H} \quad \text{and also} \quad (p, \downarrow, H \cup \{(p, E, H)\}) \in \mathbb{H}.$$

For instance, this is a valid history structure:²⁰

$$\mathbb{H} = \{(p, E, \emptyset), (p, \downarrow, \{(p, E, \emptyset)\})\}.$$

In derivation tree style (and bearing in mind that there is only one participant) we can illustrate it as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c} E \\ \hline \downarrow \end{array}$$

We could even replace E with \downarrow above, to obtain this:

$$\begin{array}{c} \downarrow \\ \hline \downarrow \end{array}$$

With respect to the encoding of natural numbers in Remark 2.3.19 below, this is the natural encoding of the number 2.

It is surprisingly interesting to look at a history structure with no events. Thus, the only maybe-event possible is \downarrow itself:

REMARK 2.3.19. Consider history structures with no events and only one participant, so that

$$\text{Event} = \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Event}_{\downarrow} = \{\downarrow\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{P} = \{p\}.$$

Then the definitions simplify up to isomorphism as follows:

- **PreHistory** is a least fixedpoint under the rule

$$\frac{H \subseteq_{fin} \text{PreHistory}}{H \in \text{PreHistory}}$$

- **History** is the set of hereditarily transitive prehistories.

²⁰It is a *sequential* one, in the sense of Definition 3.4.9(2).

This simplifies to:

$$\emptyset \in \mathbf{History} \quad H \in \mathbf{History} \implies H \cup \{(p, \downarrow, H)\} \in \mathbf{History}.$$

The reader might recognise this as essentially identical to the construction of finite von Neumann ordinals:

$$0 = \emptyset \quad n + 1 = n \cup \{n\}.$$

This is the standard *von Neumann* construction of the natural numbers in set theory, which has the nice property that a number n is represented as the set of representations of numbers less than n [Dev93, Figure 7.2].

We can take this coincidence seriously and view history structures as a generalisation of the finite von Neumann ordinals, extending them with concurrency (given by letting \mathbf{P} contain multiple participants) and with events (given by letting \mathbf{Event} be nonempty). Thus we can view histories as *concurrent numbers*, where the mapping

$$(p, x, H) \longmapsto (p, \downarrow, H \cup \{(p, x, H)\})$$

corresponds to the mapping $n \mapsto \{n\}$ used above to define $n+1$. In this sense, we can loosely identify \downarrow with the successor operation.

Conversely, von Neumann ordinals are obtained from History structures as the special case where there is just one participant, and only the one maybe-event \downarrow .²¹

REMARK 2.3.20 (Taking stock). We have set up the following mathematical machinery so far:

- *History structures* give us a notion of events happening in time and at places, where $(p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ is interpreted as ‘event E happens at place p at time H ’.
- *Semifilters* give us the notion of quorum which is fundamental to many distributed algorithms, including broadcast algorithms of the type we will study here.

Mathematically, this is all the machinery we need. In Section 3 we will combine history structures with semifilters to define the syntax and semantics of a logic for reasoning about heterogeneous broadcast algorithms.

²¹It might be interesting to take this seriously and replay the evolution of set-theoretic semantics for numbers. We list some questions in increasing order of speculativeness:

What are the arithmetic properties of ‘concurrent naturals’? What are the arithmetic and topological properties of the spaces of ‘concurrent rationals’ and ‘concurrent reals’? What might ‘concurrent surreal numbers’ mean? And even: is the natural notion of ‘concurrent sets’ substantively different from its encoding in normal set theory as per the definition of prehistories above? Such ideas are out of scope for this paper, but they might be a starting point for nice research programme in mathematical foundations.

$$\begin{aligned}
t &::= (a \in \mathbf{VSym}) \mid (v \in \mathbf{Value}) \\
\phi &::= \perp \mid \phi \Rightarrow \psi \mid t=t \mid \forall a.\phi \mid E(t, \dots, t) \mid P(t, \dots, t) \mid \\
&\quad \downarrow\phi \mid \uparrow\phi \mid \diamond_{t_1 \dots t_n} \phi \mid \text{seq}
\end{aligned}$$

Above: $E \in \mathbf{ESym}$ and $P \in \mathbf{PSym}$; and $n \geq 0$ is any nonnegative integer.

Figure 2. Syntax of predicates (Definition 3.1.3)

3. Logic over history structures

3.1. Syntax

DEFINITION 3.1.1.

1. A **signature** Σ is a tuple

$$\Sigma = (\mathbf{VSym}, \mathbf{ESym}, \mathbf{PSym}, \mathbf{Value})$$

of disjoint sets of **variable symbols**, **event symbols**, **predicate symbols**, and **values**.

We assume that \mathbf{VSym} is countably infinite and that \mathbf{Value} is nonempty (so there are many variable symbols and at least one value).

For reasons discussed in Remark 3.3.8, we may write \mathbf{Value} synonymously as **Learner**. These are different concepts but we use a single set to represent both.²²

2. We define sets of **events** and **atomic predicates** over Σ by:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{Event}(\Sigma) &= \{E(v_1, \dots, v_n) \mid E \in \mathbf{ESym}, v_1, \dots, v_n \in \mathbf{Value}\} \\
\mathbf{AtmPred}(\Sigma) &= \{P(v_1, \dots, v_n) \mid P \in \mathbf{PSym}, v_1, \dots, v_n \in \mathbf{Value}\}
\end{aligned}$$

NOTATION 3.1.2. We do not impose an arity or sort system on our syntax, so if $P \in \mathbf{PSym}$ then $P()$, $P(v)$, and $P(v_1, v_2)$, are all valid syntax, and similarly for $E \in \mathbf{ESym}$.

In practice we will use each event and predicate symbol with a consistent arity (= number of arguments). In the 0-ary case we may elide the empty brackets, writing $P()$ just as P . For instance, we do this with *live* in our theory of liveness in Figure 6.

DEFINITION 3.1.3. Suppose Σ is a signature.

1. We define the syntax of **terms** t and **predicates** ϕ over Σ by the grammar in Figure 2.
2. By convention the modal operators $\downarrow\phi$, $\uparrow\phi$, and $\diamond_{t_1 \dots t_n} \phi$ bind less tightly than \Rightarrow , so that for example $\downarrow\phi \Rightarrow \psi$ brackets as $(\downarrow\phi) \Rightarrow \psi$.

Also by convention the quantifier $\forall a.\phi$ binds as far to the right as possible, so that for example $\forall a.\downarrow\phi \Rightarrow \psi$ brackets as $\forall a.((\downarrow\phi) \Rightarrow \psi)$. That said, we may

²²It is standard to use a single set to represent multiple domains. Set theory takes this to its extreme, where sets represent *everything* (e.g. \emptyset can represent both the empty set and the number zero), and in computing, it is fundamental that all data can be serialised to binary bitstrings.

use whitespace rather than brackets for clarity, so that for example $\forall a.\phi \Rightarrow \psi$ brackets as $(\forall a.\phi) \Rightarrow \psi$. Meaning will always be clear, and where there is any danger of confusion we may insert brackets, even if this is not required according to our conventions.

3. A **closed predicate** is one with no free variable symbols. It can still mention values; so if $a \in \mathbf{VSym}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ then $a=v$ is not closed, and $\exists a.a=v$ is closed.

REMARK 3.1.4. We read the predicates in Figure 2 as follows:

- \perp is **false**, \Rightarrow is **implies**, and \forall is **for all**, as usual.
- $t=t'$ is equality; the equality holds when t and t' denote equal values.
- $E(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ is an **event** and $P(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ is an **atomic predicate**.
Both events and atomic predicates are predicates in our logical syntax (but an event is not an atomic predicate, nor vice-versa). This is intuitively justified because $E(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ -the-predicate will assert that $E(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ happens.²³
Events and atomic predicates are syntactically similar, but they have different meanings in the denotation. Events are handled by a history structure, whereas predicates are handled by an interpretation. See the rules for interpreting $w \models E$ and $w \models P$ in Figure 3.
- We read \downarrow as **at the time of some event up to now** or just **in the past** (where ‘the past’ may include now); and
- We read $\uparrow\phi$ as **ϕ at the end of time**.
- We read $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$ as **someone in every $l_1 \dots l_n$ -quorum intersection has ϕ** or **$l_1 \dots l_n$ -quorum intersections admit ϕ** (cf. Remark 3.6.3(7)); and
- seq as **sequential** (we define and study what this means in Definition 3.4.9 and Subsection 5.1). .

The above are intuitions; they will be made formal in the denotation in Figure 3.

3.2. Examples predicates, and their intended meanings

In Figure 3 we will build a notion (in fact, three notions) of logical validity; and in Figures 4 and 5 we will extend our syntax with useful macros (syntactic sugar).

However, even before we do that, we can use the syntax from Figure 2 show how some properties of interest to distributed systems can be expressed. We assume an event $\text{echo} \in \mathbf{ESym}$ and an atomic predicate symbol $\text{live} \in \mathbf{PSym}$:

²³This is just as in natural language. The English predicate ‘The cat sits on the mat’ asserts that the cat sits on the mat. That is, the sentence ‘The cat sits on the mat’ is true when the cat *does* sit on the mat, i.e. when the event “the cat sits on the mat” is actually happening, and it is false when the cat *does not* sit on the mat, i.e. what that event is not happening. Thus observe in English that the predicate ‘The cat sits on the mat’ and the event “the cat sits on the mat” are written identically (here we use single quote marks around the predicate and double quote marks around the (linguistic representation of) the event).

1. $\text{echo}(\textit{hello world})$.
We echo ‘hello world’. Note that the logic does not know what ‘echo’ means; this is just an abstract event.
2. $\text{live}()$.
Here and now, we are live. We abbreviate empty brackets to nothing, so a 0-ary use of a predicate symbol may be written just as live in the maths that follows. Note that the logic does not know what ‘live’ means; but we will develop an axiomatisation of liveness in Figure 6.
3. seq .
Up until now, we have been sequential (performed actions in linear order).
4. $\uparrow\text{seq}$.
At the end of time we have been sequential. In plain English: we are sequential forever.
5. $\downarrow\text{echo}(\textit{hello world})$.
We have echoed ‘hello world’ now or in the past.
6. $\uparrow\downarrow\text{echo}(\textit{hello world})$.
By the end of time in the past we will have echoed ‘hello world’. Or in more colloquial English: we echo ‘hello world’ sometime.
7. $\diamond\uparrow\downarrow\text{echo}(\textit{hello world})$ and $\uparrow\downarrow\diamond\text{echo}(\textit{hello world})$
These mean: somewhere sometime a participant echoes ‘hello world’; and sometime somewhere a participant echoes ‘hello world’. As it happens, one is valid in a model if and only if the other is, so these are equivalent in that sense.
8. $\diamond_{l'}\top$.
Every l -quorum intersects every l' -quorum. What l - and l' -quorums are will be explained in Subsection 3.3.1; think of them as trust assumptions, and see Lemma 4.1.1.
9. $\diamond_{l'}\text{seq}$.
Every l -quorum intersects every l' -quorum at a sequential participant (again, see Lemma 4.1.1):
10. $\diamond_{ll}\text{seq}$.
We take $l = l'$ in the previous example, so: every pair of l -quorums intersect at a sequential participant.
11. $\diamond\text{live}$, and $\neg\diamond\neg\text{live}$.
Some participant is live, and every participant is live, respectively.
12. $\uparrow\forall v.\diamond\downarrow\text{echo}(v)$.
By the end of time, for every value there is a participant who echoed v in the past. Or in plain English: every value is eventually echoed by some participant.
13. $\text{echo}(\textit{world}) \Rightarrow \downarrow\text{echo}(\textit{hello})$.
If we echo ‘world’, then we must have echoed ‘hello’ now or in the past.
14. $\text{echo}(\textit{hello}) \Rightarrow \uparrow\downarrow\text{echo}(\textit{world})$.

If we echo ‘hello’, then we must echo ‘world’ at some time (though we do not say precisely when).

15. \diamond seq, \diamond_l seq, $\diamond_{ll'}$ seq, and \diamond_{lll} seq.

Respectively these mean: some participant is sequential; every l -quorum contains a sequential participant; the intersection of every pair of l - and l' -quorums contains a sequential participant; and any three l -quorums intersect at a sequential participant.

Sequentiality is from Definition 3.4.9; intuitively a participant is sequential when it does not *equivocate*; report incompatible histories to different participants. This will be an important well-behavedness property for our proofs.

We hope this gives the reader some initial feeling for how the syntax in Figure 2 can be used. We are now ready to build models and use these to give the logic a formal notion of validity.

3.3. Models

3.3.1. Semifilters

We need a technical notion to build our models: *semitopologies* are a mathematical generalisation of the notion of *quorum system* typically used in distributed systems [Gab24, Gab25b]. We do not need the full machinery of semitopologies in this paper but it is convenient to import a useful notation \checkmark , and the notion of a *semifilter*.

NOTATION 3.3.1. Suppose O and O' are sets. Define $O \checkmark O'$ [Gab24, Gab25b, Notation 3.1.1] by

$$O \checkmark O' \quad \text{when} \quad O \cap O' \neq \emptyset.$$

In this case we say that O **intersects** O' .

DEFINITION 3.3.2. Suppose \mathbf{P} is a set of **points**. A **semifilter** L on \mathbf{P} [Gab24, Definition 13.1.1(5)] is a nonempty up-closed set of pairwise intersecting nonempty subsets of \mathbf{P} . Spelling this out:

1. *Nonempty subsets* $\emptyset \neq L \subseteq \text{pow}(P)$.
2. *Up-closed* If $O \in L$ and $O \subseteq O' \subseteq \mathbf{P}$, then $O' \in L$.
3. *Pairwise intersecting* If $O, O' \in L$ then $O \checkmark O'$.

Nonemptiness of the subsets follows as the special case that $O \in L$ must intersect itself.

Semifilters are essentially just the notion of *quorum system* from [Mal99, MR97]. Page 1 of [Mal99] says (in edited form) that: a *quorum system* is a set of pairwise intersecting subsets of some universe of servers. The difference between this and [Gab24, Definition 13.1.1(5)] is just that the latter

identifies the former as a topological concept corresponding to the notion of *abstract point* in topology.²⁴

This logic-and-topology view of quorum systems helped us to design our logic here — but if every time we write *semifilter*, the reader reads *quorum system*, then no harm will come of it.

Write $\mathbf{SemiFilter}(\mathbf{P})$ for the set of semifilters on \mathbf{P} . Thus:

$$\mathbf{SemiFilter}(\mathbf{P}) = \{L \subseteq \mathit{pow}(\mathbf{P}) \mid L \text{ is a semifilter}\}.$$

If L is a semifilter then we might call $O \in L$ an **open set** or a **quorum**.

3.3.2. Definition of models

DEFINITION 3.3.3. Suppose $\Sigma = (\mathbf{VSym}, \mathbf{ESym}, \mathbf{PSym}, \mathbf{Value})$ is a signature. Then a **model** \mathbb{M} for Σ is a tuple

$$\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \varrho, \zeta)$$

where:

1. \mathbf{P} is a nonempty set of **participants**; we may also call these **points** or **places**.
2. $\mathbb{H} \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event}(\Sigma))$ is a history structure (Definition 2.3.5).
Following Definition 2.3.13, we may call \mathbb{H} the **end of time** in \mathbb{M} , because it represents a time at which all events in the model are in the past.
3. ϱ is a **(predicate) interpretation**, such that

$$\varrho(p, H) \subseteq \mathbf{AtmPred}(\Sigma)$$

for every $p \in \mathbf{P}$ and $H \preceq \mathbb{H}$.

Intuitively, $\varrho(p, H)$ decides which atomic predicates are true at place p and at time H (we make this formal in the clause for $w \models \mathbf{P}(v_1, \dots, v_n)$ in Figure 3).

4. ζ is a **learner interpretation** which assigns a semifilter to each value, so it is such that

$$\zeta(v) \in \mathbf{SemiFilter}(\mathbf{P})$$

for every $v \in \mathbf{Value}$. We might write l for values when we intend that they be interpreted using ζ .

Intuitively, ζ assigns a semifilter (i.e. a set of quorums) to each value. We use this in the clause for $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n}$ in Figure 3.

²⁴There is a claim here: that the notion of *learner* used in this paper is morally identical to the notion of *abstract point* in the sense of point-free topology. The technical work to make this intuition precise is out of scope for this paper; but the reader can find more about abstract points in a semitopological context in [Gab24, Part II, *semiframes*] or [Gab25a].

REMARK 3.3.4. One difference between atomic predicates and events is that events happen at times $H \in \mathbb{H}$, whereas atomic predicates are assigned truth-values at times in $H \in \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$. This difference is real, e.g. no event can happen at the end of time \mathbb{H} , but predicates can be true or false there.

This flexibility is deliberate — e.g. our judgement form $\models \phi$ in Figure 3 explicitly uses the end of time \mathbb{H} , which intuitively is a time when all events have already happened, so no events should occur at \mathbb{H} , but we will still make logical assertions.

EXAMPLE 3.3.5 (Empty model). Arguably the simplest possible model takes $\mathbb{H} = \emptyset$. So we have sets of participants and events and all the structure of a model, but there are no events; nothing happens.

We call \emptyset the **empty history** and a model with the empty history an **empty model**.

If $\mathbb{H} \neq \emptyset$ then we call the history structure **nonempty**. If a model has a nonempty history structure then we call it a **nonempty model**.

Looking forward to Definition 3.5.1 ((in)active participants) a model is nonempty precisely when it contains some *active* participant, and empty when all of its participants are inactive.

EXAMPLE 3.3.6 (The minimal nonempty model). Following on from the empty model in Example 3.3.5, what is the smallest model in which all participants *do* something, i.e. they there is some event-tuple associated to each participant? Perhaps surprisingly, there is a canonical such:

1. **Event** = \emptyset .
2. $\mathbb{H} = \{(p, \dagger, \emptyset) \mid p \in \mathbf{P}\}$.
3. $\varrho = \zeta = \emptyset$ (empty functions because there is nothing to interpret).

Although this example looks simple, it captures much of the essential structure of a model. Other complexity is just a matter of extending this core.²⁵

3.3.3. Discussion of models

NOTATION 3.3.7. A model will *always* be written \mathbb{M} and the history structure of that model will *always* be written \mathbb{H} , so we might not always spell out that \mathbb{H} belongs to \mathbb{M} .

If the reader does not like this, they can read ‘ $\mathbb{H}_{\mathbb{M}}$ ’ every time they see ‘ \mathbb{H} ’, and their understanding will be precisely correct.

REMARK 3.3.8 (Values as learners). ζ maps values to semifilters. In effect, this allows us to use $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ to represent both a value or a learner. In places where we intend a value to denote a learner, we may write that value as l (rather

²⁵To be fair, that other complexity is considerable — even if we have empty sets of events and values. See the construction of the finite von Neumann numbers in Remark 2.3.19.

than as v); see for example $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_1} \phi$ in Figure 3. We may abuse notation go further and

$$\mathbf{Learner} = \mathbf{Value}.$$

So $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ has the same semantic meaning as $v \in \mathbf{Value}$; the difference is just how we intend this value to be used.

If the reader does not like this, the reader is welcome to mentally distinguish the two sets as disjoint sets of *learners* and *values*. The price we would then pay is just notational: we need two kinds of variable (one to range over learners, one to range over values), and two kinds of quantification (one for each kind of variable).

Indeed, we could introduce a sort system, and give event symbols and atomic predicate symbols arities, and maybe then extend to a full typing system. For a practical implementation we might require this apparatus, but it would not change the essential character of the mathematics. For an initial syntax in this paper, it suffices to take a single set and use it to denote values or learners as convenient.

REMARK 3.3.9. As we have set things up, learners are represented in the model via the *learner interpretation* ζ in Definition 3.3.3(4), which maps values (thought of as learners) to semifilters.

This is arguably counterintuitive: surely learners should be participants in the model? Intuitively, yes. In practice, the only thing we care about of a learner is its semifilter of quorums. We could certainly include learners as participants, but for our axioms and our correctness properties, this is not required.²⁶ So we do not bother.

3.4. The Kripke semantics associated to a model, and validity

REMARK 3.4.1 (Kripke structures). Our logical syntax from Figure 2 is overtly modal, in the sense of modal logic [BdRV01, Gar24]: we have symbols \downarrow , \uparrow , and \diamond which look like modalities, and we have even called them ‘modalities’. Modal logic has a standard semantics in terms of *Kripke structures* (also called *relational semantics*). A typical Kripke structure consists of a set of *possible worlds* and an *accessibility relation* on worlds.

²⁶ *A comment on design.* Initial drafts of this material included learners as participants. We imposed a full semitopology Open on the set of participants and the role of the semifilter $\zeta(l)$ was filled by just taking the set of open neighbourhoods of l ; $\text{Opn}(l) = \{O \in \text{Open} \mid l \in O\}$.

This is elegant, topological, and arguably intuitive (learners are participants and their quorums are their open neighbourhoods) — but it created an annoying notational problem that we needed our logic to have quantification over learners (and participants), and also quantification over values, and also variable symbols for both kind of quantifier, and it all got a bit long to write out.

The nice feature of identifying learners with values, using a learner interpretation ζ , and having just one quantification symbol, is that it gives a minimal and slick presentation of the logic and axioms. *And* it is enough to give us all the expressivity that we actually need. So we do that.

Modal validity is per-world, by which we mean that each predicate is valid or invalid at a possible world. The intuition is that the validity of some assertions naturally depends on where and/or when we make them, e.g. ‘it is raining’ may be valid in some places and times and not in others, so this is best understood as a modal judgement, as in e.g. ‘here \models it is raining’.

Definition 3.3.3 gives us a notion of what we call a *model* \mathbb{M} . We called \mathbb{M} ‘a model’ but really it is just a tuple; for it to behave like model, we need to use it to build a notion of logical validity. In this Subsection we will do that. We will extract from \mathbb{M} :

- a Kripke-style semantics (possible worlds $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ and an accessibility relation \ll), in Definition 3.4.2; and
- three modal notions of validity with respect to that semantics, in Definition 3.4.10 and Figure 3 (why we need *three* notions of validity will become clear).

3.4.1. Kripke (relational) semantics

DEFINITION 3.4.2 (Kripke-style semantics). Suppose $\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \varrho, \zeta)$ is a model.

1. Define $\mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$ the set of **possible times** by

$$\mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M}) = \{H \mid H \preceq \mathbb{H}\}.$$

(\preceq is from Definition 2.3.1(2); $H \preceq \mathbb{H}$ means either $H = \mathbb{H}$ or $(p, x, H) \in \mathbb{H}$ for some p and x .)

Intuitively, the possible times of a model is the set of all times of events that occur in the model, or \mathbb{H} the end of time itself.

2. Define $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ the set of **possible worlds** by

$$\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) = \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M}).$$

We will write $w, w' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$; so w and w' will range over possible worlds.

3. Define an **accessibility relation** \ll on possible worlds such that for every $(p, x, H), (p', x', H') \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$,

$$(p', x', H') \ll (p, x, H) \quad \text{when} \quad (p', x', H') \in H.$$

Equivalently writing $w' = (p', x', H')$ and $w = (p, x, H)$ and using $\mathit{time}(w)$ from Definition 2.2.6(1),

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{when} \quad w' \in \mathit{time}(w).$$

For convenient reference, we mention here that \ll will be transitive and ir-reflexive: see Proposition 3.4.5.

4. Define an **in-place accessibility relation** \ll such that for $(p, x, H), (p', x', H') \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$,

$$(p', x', H') \ll (p, x, H) \quad \text{when} \quad (p', x', H') \in H \wedge p' = p.$$

Equivalently using Definition 2.2.6(1),

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{when} \quad w' \in \text{time}(w) \wedge \text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w).$$

LEMMA 3.4.3. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w', w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then*

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{implies} \quad \text{time}(w') \prec \text{time}(w) \wedge \text{time}(w') \subsetneq \text{time}(w).$$

Proof. Suppose $w' \ll w$. By Definition 3.4.2(3) $w' \in \text{time}(w)$. By assumption $\text{time}(w) \prec \mathbb{H}$ or $\text{time}(w) = \mathbb{H}$; in either case, $\text{time}(w)$ is a history structure. By Definition 2.3.1(1) (since $w' \in \text{time}(w)$) $\text{time}(w') \prec \text{time}(w)$, and by Definition 2.3.2 and Remark 2.3.3 $\text{time}(w') \subsetneq \text{time}(w)$. \square

Lemma 3.4.4 is a correctness check that we can set $\mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M}) = \{H \mid H \preceq \mathbb{H}\}$ in Definition 3.4.2(1), rather than $\{H \mid H \preceq^* \mathbb{H}\}$, where \preceq^* denotes the transitive closure of \preceq :

LEMMA 3.4.4. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w, w' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then*

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{implies} \quad \text{time}(w') \prec \mathbb{H}.$$

Proof. By Definition 3.4.2(2) $\text{time}(w) \preceq \mathbb{H}$, which means that $\text{time}(w) \prec \mathbb{H}$ or $\text{time}(w) = \mathbb{H}$.

- If $\text{time}(w) = \mathbb{H}$ then by Lemma 3.4.3 (since $w' \ll w$) $\text{time}(w') \prec \mathbb{H}$ as required.
- If $\text{time}(w) \prec \mathbb{H}$ then by Lemma 3.4.3 we have $\text{time}(w') \prec \text{time}(w) \prec \mathbb{H}$ and by Lemma 2.3.12(1) (element-transitivity of history structures) $\text{time}(w') \prec \mathbb{H}$. \square

PROPOSITION 3.4.5 (Transitivity and irreflexivity of accessibility). *Suppose $\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \rho, \zeta)$ is a model. Then the accessibility relation \ll from Definition 3.4.2(3) is transitive and irreflexive. That is:*

$$\forall w, w', w'' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). w'' \ll w' \implies w' \ll w \implies w'' \ll w$$

and

$$\forall w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). \neg(w \ll w).$$

Proof. Suppose $w'' \ll w'$ and $w' \ll w$. By Definition 3.4.2(3) $w'' \in \text{time}(w')$ and by Lemma 3.4.3 $\text{time}(w') \subsetneq \text{time}(w)$, so $w'' \in \text{time}(w)$. By Definition 3.4.2(3) again $w'' \ll w$ as required.

Irreflexivity is a simple corollary of Lemma 3.4.3, since $\text{time}(w) \subsetneq \text{time}(w)$ is impossible. \square

3.4.2. Sequentiality

REMARK 3.4.6. We need the notion of *sequentiality* for Figure 3, to interpret the proposition *seq*. Intuitively, p is sequential in H when p performs its actions in sequence, according to H . Sequentiality will be important to our later mathematics because, for our needs, sequential participants will be the ‘good’ ones. In Remark 5.1.6 we will note a more abstract but more permissive *orderability* condition that would also suffice for our needs.

A technical definition will help us define sequentiality in Definition 3.4.9:

DEFINITION 3.4.7. Suppose $p \in \mathbf{P}$ and $H \in \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$. Define $H_{@p}$ the **history H at p** or **set of event-tuples at p** by

$$H_{@p} = \{w \in H \mid \text{place}(w) = p\}.$$

REMARK 3.4.8. Note that:

1. $H_{@p}$ is a prehistory but it need not be a history, because it might not be transitive (Definition 2.3.2) (this will not be a problem; we will only ever use it as a set).
2. Recalling from Definition 3.4.2(3) that

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{when} \quad w' \in \text{time}(w),$$

a nice characterisation of $w' \ll w$ from Definition 3.4.2(4) is

$$w' \ll w \quad \text{if and only if} \quad w' \in \text{time}(w)_{@ \text{place}(w)}.$$

DEFINITION 3.4.9 (Sequentiality). Suppose $p \in \mathbf{P}$ and $H \in \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$.

1. Call p **sequential** at H when

$$\forall w, w' \in H_{@p}. (w \ll w' \vee w' \ll w \vee w = w').$$

In words: p is sequential in H when event-tuples at p occur in sequence in H .

2. Call H **sequential** when

$$\forall w, w' \in H. (w \ll w' \vee w' \ll w \vee w = w')$$

In words: H is sequential when event-tuples in H occur in sequence.

3.4.3. Validity

DEFINITION 3.4.10 (Validity). Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ and ϕ is a closed predicate. Then we define three validity judgements as follows:

1. Define **possible world validity** $w \models \phi$ inductively by the rules in Figure 3. Write $w = (p, x, H)$. In the judgement “ $p, x, H \models \phi$ ”, we may follow Definition 2.2.6(2) and call p the **place**, x the **(maybe-)event**, and H the **time** of the judgement.

<i>false</i>	$w \models \perp$	$\iff \perp$
<i>implies</i>	$w \models \phi \Rightarrow \phi'$	$\iff (w \models \phi \implies w \models \phi')$
<i>equality</i>	$w \models v=v$	$\iff \top$
<i>inequality</i>	$w \models v=v'$	$\iff \perp$ (v' not equal to v)
<i>forall</i>	$w \models \forall a.\phi$	$\iff \forall v \in \mathbf{Value}. (w \models \phi[a:=v])$
<i>event</i>	$p, x, H \models E$	$\iff (x = E \wedge (p, E, H) \in \mathbb{H})$
<i>atomic predicate</i>		
	$p, x, H \models P$	$\iff P \in \varrho(p, H)$
<i>in the past</i>	$w \models \downarrow\phi$	$\iff \exists w' \ll w. (w' \models \phi)$
<i>end of time</i>	$p, x, H \models \uparrow\phi$	$\iff p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$
<i>admission</i>	$p, x, H \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$	$\iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \exists p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. (p', \downarrow, H \models \phi)$
<i>sequentiality</i>	$p, x, H \models \text{seq}$	$\iff p$ sequential at H
<i>validity (end-of-time)</i>		
	$\models \phi$	$\iff \forall p \in \mathbf{P}. (p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi)$
<i>validity (all-world)</i>		
	$\boxplus \models \phi$	$\iff \forall w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). (w \models \phi)$

Above:

- We assume a fixed signature $\Sigma = (\mathbf{VSym}, \mathbf{ESym}, \mathbf{PSym}, \mathbf{Value})$ (Definition 3.1.1) and model $\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \varrho, \zeta)$ (Definition 3.3.3) for that signature.
- $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ is a world (Definition 3.4.2(2)).
- $p \in \mathbf{P}$ is a participant, and E is an event in the sense of Definition 3.1.1(2), i.e. $E = E(v_1, \dots, v_n)$ for some $v_1, \dots, v_n \in \mathbf{Value}$ (and for some n).
- $w' \ll w$ is from Definition 3.4.2(4) and means $w' \in \text{time}(w) \wedge \text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w)$.
- p being sequential at H is from Definition 3.4.9 (see also Lemma 5.1.2).
- The italic text in the leftmost column (*false*, *implies*, etc) is just a reminder of how to read the connective. It has no formal meaning; it is just a useful hint. The terminology ‘admission’ for \diamond is put in context in Remark 3.6.3.
- In the first line, \perp on the left represents the formal symbol from our predicate syntax in Figure 2 (object-level), and \perp on the right represents logical false (meta-level). In the next line, \Rightarrow is an object-level symbol and \implies is meta-level implication. Similarly for $=$ and $=$, for \forall and \forall , and so on.

Figure 3. Validity (Definition 3.4.10)

2. Define **omniscient** or **end-of-time validity** by $\models \phi$ when $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$ for every $p \in \mathbf{P}$.
3. Define **all-world** validity by $\boxed{\vDash} \phi$ when $w \models \phi$ for every $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$.

Where we write just ‘validity’, it will always be clear which kind of validity we refer to. When we write $w \models \phi$, $\models \phi$, or $\boxed{\vDash} \phi$, it will always be clear (or unimportant) with respect to which model we intend this.

REMARK 3.4.11 (Validity and time). The treatments of validity and time in the judgement $w \models \phi$ from Definition 3.4.10 and Figure 3 are subtle. We make some observations:

1. Possible world validity $w \models \phi$ is a standard-looking modal validity judgement that ϕ is valid (or is not valid) at the possible world $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. However, Figure 3 defines two more validity judgements: *end-of-time* validity $\models \phi$ and *all-world* validity $\boxed{\vDash} \phi$. We discuss and contrast these in Subsection 5.2. Briefly: we use $\boxed{\vDash} \phi$ to impose axioms on a model, and $\models \phi$ to assert correctness properties that look retrospectively back on the model as viewed from the end of time.
2. In $w \models \phi$, note that:

- w has the form (p, x, H) for any $p \in \mathbf{P}$ and $x \in \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$ and $H \in \mathbb{H} \vee H = \mathbb{H}$.
- We *do not* make the stricter requirement that $w \in \mathbb{H}$. That is, w does not have to be an event-tuple that actually occurs in \mathbb{H} : this could be because $H = \mathbb{H}$, or because x is a maybe-event such that $(p, x, H) \notin \mathbb{H}$ (even though perhaps $(p, x', H) \in \mathbb{H}$ for some other choice of $x' \in \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$).²⁷

This is deliberate: the \uparrow modality takes us to the end of time, where by definition no events occur, so for the validity judgement $\models \phi$ (meaning $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$ for every p) to make sense, we need to consider possible worlds other than just those in \mathbb{H} .

Similarly when we interpret $w \models \diamond_{t_1 \dots t_n} \phi$ we consider $(p', \downarrow, \mathit{time}(w))$, a possible world for which there is no guarantee that $(p', \downarrow, \mathit{time}(w)) \in \mathbb{H}$.

This is why we define $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) = \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$ in Definition 3.4.2(2). This is inherent and a feature of our design. Conversely, defining $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ to be just equal to \mathbb{H} would be too weakly-structured for what Figure 3 requires.

²⁷ This comes from the fact that we define $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) = \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow} \times \mathbf{Time}(\mathbb{M})$ in Definition 3.4.2(2).

Design alternative: We could refine Definition 3.4.2(2) such that $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) = \mathbb{H} \cup \{(p, \downarrow, H) \mid H \preceq \mathbb{H}\}$, where \preceq is the notion of *non-strict element of* from Definition 2.3.1(2). It turns out (this is not obvious) that with this definition our results would work just as well. The key observation is that if we start from w in the refined set then every operation on possible worlds in Figure 3 keeps us within it. For computational purposes (e.g. model-checking) the refined set may be helpful, because it is smaller; but for our purposes Definition 3.4.2(2) suffices, and it is conceptually simple, so we use that.

3. Continuing the previous point and contrasting with it — the *in the past* modality \downarrow looks specifically for a possible world *in* \mathbb{H} . We unpack the clause for $w \models \downarrow\phi$ in Figure 3:

$$\begin{aligned} w \models \downarrow\phi &\iff \exists w' \ll w. (w' \models \phi) && \text{Figure 3} \\ &\iff \exists w' \ll w. (\text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w) \wedge w' \models \phi) && \text{Def. 3.4.2(4)} \\ &\iff \exists w' \in \text{time}(w). (\text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w) \wedge w' \models \phi) && \text{Def. 3.4.2(3)} \end{aligned}$$

It follows from the above and from Lemma 3.4.3 that $\text{time}(w') \in \mathbb{H}$.

Note also that the interpretation of $w \models E$ (for E an event) also appeals to whether a possible world is in \mathbb{H} .

So two notions of possible world coexist in Figure 3, in a kind of creative tension:

- There are $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$, which we call *possible worlds* in Definition 3.4.2(2).
- There are $w \in \mathbb{H}$, which we call *event-tuples* in Definition 2.2.6(1).

We require the former to interpret $\boxplus \models \phi$ and \uparrow and \diamond in Figure 3, and we require the latter to interpret \downarrow and E .

3.5. Active and inactive participants

It will be helpful later if we make a short technical detour and introduce the notion of (in)active participants:

DEFINITION 3.5.1 ((In)active participants). Call p **active** in \mathbb{H} when $\mathbb{H}_{@p} \neq \emptyset$. Unpacking Definition 3.4.7 this means that there exists some $w \in \mathbb{H}$ with $\text{place}(w) = p$. If p is not active (so \mathbb{H} contains no event-tuple starting with p) then call it **inactive** in \mathbb{H} .

Usually \mathbb{H} will be fixed or understood, so we will just call p (in)active, without mentioning \mathbb{H} explicitly. Intuitively, a participant is active when it is the location of at least one event.

REMARK 3.5.2. The empty model from Example 3.3.5 is characterised precisely by being such that all of its participants are inactive. The minimal model from Example 3.3.6 is simplest such that all of its participants are active.

LEMMA 3.5.3. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model with history structure \mathbb{H} and suppose $p \in \mathbf{P}$. Then the following are equivalent:*

1. $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \downarrow\top$.
2. p is active (there is an event-tuple in \mathbb{H} starting with p ; Definition 3.5.1).

As a corollary, $\models \downarrow\top$ if and only if all participants are active.

Proof. We just unpack the definitions in Figure 3. □

Sugar for basic propositions & predicates

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \neg\phi = (\phi \Rightarrow \perp) & \top = \neg\perp \\
 \phi \vee \phi' = ((\neg\phi) \Rightarrow \phi') & \phi \wedge \phi' = \neg((\neg\phi) \vee (\neg\phi')) \\
 \phi \Leftrightarrow \phi' = (\phi \Rightarrow \phi') \wedge (\phi' \Rightarrow \phi) & \\
 \exists a.\phi = \neg\forall a.\neg\phi & \\
 \exists_{\mathbf{01}}a.\phi = \forall a, b.\phi \Rightarrow \phi[a:=b] \Rightarrow a=b & \exists_{\mathbf{1}}a.\phi = (\exists_{\mathbf{01}}a.\phi) \wedge \exists a.\phi
 \end{array}$$

Sugar for time

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \Downarrow\phi = \neg\uparrow\neg\phi & \\
 \Updownarrow\phi = \uparrow\downarrow\phi & \Downup\phi = \neg\uparrow\neg\phi = \uparrow\downarrow\phi
 \end{array}$$

Sugar for the modality \diamond

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \Box_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi = \neg \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \neg \phi & \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi = \Box_{l_1 \dots l_n} \downarrow \phi \\
 \Downarrow_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi = \Box_{l_1 \dots l_n} \downarrow \phi & \Downup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi = \Downarrow_{l_1 \dots l_n} \downarrow \phi \\
 \Downup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi = \Downarrow_{l_1 \dots l_n} \downarrow \phi & \diamond \phi = \Box_{\emptyset} \phi \\
 \Box \phi = \Box_{\emptyset} \phi &
 \end{array}$$

Above, $\phi[a:=b]$ denotes the usual capture-avoiding substitution of b for a .

Figure 4. Extended (sugared) syntax (Definition 3.6.1)

3.6. Extending syntax with syntactic sugar

The core syntax from Figure 2 is expressive, and it will be convenient to use sugar as follows:

DEFINITION 3.6.1 (Syntactic sugar). We define **syntactic sugar** as described in Figure 4, and we unpack the corresponding denotation in Figure 5.

REMARK 3.6.2 (de Morgan dualities). We recall some standard background on logic and negation.²⁸

Logical connectives — quantifiers, modalities, and propositional connectives — tend to come in pairs, which are dual to one another by negation in a standard way. Standard dualities include:

1. *forall/exist duality* $\forall a.\phi = \neg\exists a.\neg\phi$ and $\exists a.\phi = \neg\forall a.\neg\phi$.
2. *and/or duality* $\phi \wedge \psi = \neg(\neg\phi \vee \neg\psi)$ and $\phi \vee \psi = \neg(\neg\phi \wedge \neg\psi)$.
3. *every/some duality* In modal logic, we have $\Box\phi = \neg\diamond\neg\phi$ and $\diamond\phi = \neg\Box\neg\phi$.

All definitions will be written out in full, but the reader should just note that usually these connectives come in pairs and we will structure our definitions accordingly.

²⁸The reader who is already familiar with *de Morgan* dualities should please be patient: *de Morgan* duality is surprising and not necessarily intuitive to the uninitiated reader.

$$\begin{aligned}
w \models \mathbf{T} & \iff \top \\
w \models \neg\phi & \iff w \not\models \phi \\
w \models \phi \mathbf{V} \phi' & \iff (w \models \phi) \vee (w \models \phi') \\
w \models \phi \mathbf{\wedge} \phi' & \iff (w \models \phi) \wedge (w \models \phi') \\
w \models \phi \mathbf{\leftrightarrow} \phi' & \iff ((w \models \phi) \iff (w \models \phi')) \\
w \models \exists a.\phi & \iff \exists v \in \mathbf{Value}.(w \models \phi[a:=v]) \\
w \models \exists_{\mathbf{0}1} a.\phi \text{ and } w \models \exists_{\mathbf{1}} a.\phi & \text{ are as expected} \\
\\
w \models \Downarrow\phi & \iff \forall w' \ll w. (w' \models \phi) \\
w \models \Updownarrow\phi & \iff \exists w' \in \mathbb{H}_{@place(w)}. (w' \models \phi) \\
w \models \Downarrow\phi & \iff \forall w' \in \mathbb{H}_{@place(w)}. (w' \models \phi) \\
\\
w \models \Box_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi & \iff \exists (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\
& \quad \forall p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. (p', \downarrow, time(w)) \models \phi \\
(w \models \Diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi) & \iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\
& \quad \exists w' \ll w. (p', H' \models \phi) \\
w \models \mathbb{1}_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi & \iff \exists (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\
& \quad \forall p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. \exists w' \ll w. \\
& \quad (place(w') = p' \wedge w' \models \phi) \\
w \models \mathbb{0}_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi & \iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\
& \quad \exists p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. \forall w' \ll w. \\
& \quad (place(w') = p' \implies w' \models \phi) \\
w \models \mathbb{1}_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi & \iff \exists (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\
& \quad \forall p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. \forall w' \ll w. \\
& \quad (place(w') = p' \implies w' \models \phi) \\
p, x, H \models \Diamond\phi & \iff \exists p' \in \mathbf{P}. p', \downarrow, H \models \phi \\
p, x, H \models \Box\phi & \iff \forall p' \in \mathbf{P}. p', x, H \models \phi
\end{aligned}$$

Above, $w' \ll w$ is from Definition 3.4.2(3) and means $w' \in time(w)$.

Note that Figure 4 defines syntactic sugar — like $\Downarrow\phi = \neg\downarrow\neg\phi$ — and this Figure unpacks the denotation of that sugar as per Figure 3. It is *not* the case that there are (for example) two \Downarrow symbols — indeed, formally there is no symbol \Downarrow at all, since it is a macro for $\neg\downarrow\neg$.

Figure 5. Denotation of sugar from Figure 4 (Definition 3.6.1)

REMARK 3.6.3. We briefly discuss the sugar in Figure 4, with more details to follow in the Remarks and Lemmas that follow:

1. \neg , \wedge , and \vee are defined from \perp and \Rightarrow using standard encodings.
2. $\exists a.\phi = \neg\forall a.\neg\phi$ is also standard: it is the usual *de Morgan* dual definition of \exists in terms of \forall .
3. \Downarrow is the de Morgan dual to \Downarrow . $\Downarrow\phi$ means that ϕ holds at the time of *some* present or past event at the current place, so its de Morgan dual $\Downarrow\phi$ means that ϕ holds at the time of *every* present or past event at the current place.
4. $\Updownarrow\phi$ and $\Downarrow\phi$ are temporal modal operators (see Subsection 1.3 of [GHR94] for an old but very approachable survey of the genre):
 - $\Updownarrow\phi$ — read **sometime** ϕ — means that ϕ holds at the time of *some* maybe-event at the current place.
 - $\Downarrow\phi$ — read **everytime** ϕ — means that ϕ holds at the time of *every* maybe-event at the current place.

These are de Morgan duals: $\Updownarrow\phi$ is equivalent to $\neg\Downarrow\neg\phi$ and $\Downarrow\phi$ is equivalent to $\neg\Updownarrow\neg\phi$.

5. $\Box_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi = \neg\Diamond_{l_1\dots l_n}\neg\phi$. This defines $\Box_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ as the de Morgan dual to $\Diamond_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$.
6. The \emptyset in $\Diamond\phi = \Diamond_{\emptyset}\phi$ and $\Box\phi = \Box_{\emptyset}\phi$ denotes the empty list (of learners).
7. Eight modalities are definable and will be of interest. We list them:
 - (a) $\Diamond_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ holds *somewhere* in every $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersection’. We may read this as

all $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersections **admit** ϕ .
 - (b) $\Box_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ holds *everywhere* in some $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersection’. We may read this as

some $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersection **agrees on** ϕ .
 - (c) $\Diamond_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ held in the past *somewhere* in every quorum intersection’. We may read this as

all $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersections **admit past** ϕ .
 - (d) $\Box_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ held in the past *everywhere* in some quorum intersection’. We may read this as

some $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersection **agrees on past** ϕ .
 - (e) $\Diamond_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ held up to (not including) now *somewhere* in every quorum intersection’. We may read this as

all $l_1\dots l_n$ -quorum intersections **admit ϕ up to (but not necessarily including) now**.
 - (f) $\Box_{l_1\dots l_n}\phi$ means ‘ ϕ held up to (not including) now *everywhere* in some quorum intersection’. We may read this as

some $l_1 \dots l_n$ -quorum intersection **agrees on ϕ up to (but not necessarily including) now.**

(g) We may read $\diamond\phi$ as ϕ holds **somewhere** (now), and $\square\phi$ as ϕ holds **everywhere** (now).

We will justify the terminology above, with the results that follow below. In our usage, ‘admit’ is the de Morgan dual to ‘agree’, because \diamond is the de Morgan dual to \square . That is: we admit ϕ if we do not agree on not- ϕ .

We check correctness of some parts of Figure 5:

LEMMA 3.6.4. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then as per Figure 5:*

1. *The following are equivalent:*

- $w \models \Downarrow\phi$
- $\exists w' \in \mathbb{H}. (\text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w) \wedge w' \models \phi)$
- $\exists w' \in \mathbb{H}_{@ \text{place}(w)}. w' \models \phi.$

2. *The following are equivalent:*

- $w \models \Downarrow\phi$
- $\forall w' \in \mathbb{H}. (\text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w) \implies w' \models \phi)$
- $\forall w' \in \mathbb{H}_{@ \text{place}(w)}. w' \models \phi.$

3. *The following are equivalent:*

- $w \models \Diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$
- $\forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \exists w' \ll w. (\text{place}(w') \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n \wedge w' \models \phi)$

Proof. Part 2 follows from part 1 by de Morgan duality, so we focus on part 1. We reason as follows, where we take $w = (p, x, H)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w \models \Downarrow\phi &\iff w \models \Uparrow\downarrow\phi && \text{Figure 4} \\
 &\iff p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \downarrow\phi && \text{Figure 3} \\
 &\iff \exists w' \ll (p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H}). w' \models \phi && \text{Figure 3} \\
 &\iff \exists H', x'. (p, x', H') \in \mathbb{H} \wedge p, x', H' \models \phi && \text{Definition 3.4.2(4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

The equivalences then follow from the definitions ($\mathbb{H}_{@ \text{place}(w)}$ is from Definition 3.4.7).

For part 3 we unpack \diamond as \diamond and \downarrow and use Figure 3 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
p, x, H \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi & \\
\iff p, x, H \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \downarrow \phi & \text{Figure 4} \\
\iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). & \\
\quad \exists p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. p', \downarrow, H \models \downarrow \phi & \text{Figure 3} \\
\iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). & \\
\quad \exists p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. \exists w' \ll w. & \\
\quad (\text{place}(w') = p' \wedge w' \models \phi) & \text{Figure 3} \\
\iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \exists w' \ll w. & \\
\quad (\text{place}(w') \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n \wedge w' \models \phi) & \text{Fact} \quad \square
\end{aligned}$$

REMARK 3.6.5. We unpack some common special cases of Figures 4 and 5:

1. $p, x, H \models \square_l \phi$ means that there exists an l -quorum O such that $p', \downarrow, H \models \phi$ for every $p' \in O$.

In words we say: **an l -quorum agrees that ϕ .**

2. $p, x, H \models \sqcup_l \phi$ means that there exists an l -quorum O such that for every $p' \in O$, some $(p', x', H') \in H$ exists such that $p', x', H' \models \phi$.

Equivalently, $w \models \sqcup_l \phi$ when there exists an l -quorum $O \in \zeta(l)$ of participants such that for every $p' \in O$ there exists $w' \ll w$ (Definition 3.4.7) such that $\text{place}(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$.

Equivalently again,²⁹ $w \models \sqcup_l \phi$ when there exists an l -quorum $O \in \zeta(l)$ of participants such that for every $p' \in O$ there exists $w' \in H_{@p'}$ such that $w' \models \phi$.

In words we say: **an l -quorum agrees that ϕ in the past.**

3. $p, x, H \models \sqcup_l \phi$ means that there exists an l -quorum O such that for every $w' \in H$, we have $w' \models \phi$.
4. We leave it to the reader to unpack $\square_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$, $\sqcup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$, and $\sqcup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$.

We may read $\sqcup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$ as **a(n $l_1 \dots l_n$ -)quorum intersection agrees that ϕ .**

5. Matters simplify further when $H = \mathbb{H}$: Thus:

- $\models \diamond_{l'} \phi$ and $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond_{l'} \phi$ mean that for every l -quorum and l' -quorum, there exists a p' in their intersection such that $p', \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$.
- $\models \diamond_{l'} \phi$ and $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond_{l'} \phi$ mean that for every l -quorum and l' -quorum, there exists a p' in their intersection and some $w' \in \mathbb{H}$ such that $\text{place}(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$.
- We leave it to the reader to unpack $\square_{l'} \phi$, $\sqcup_{l'} \phi$, $\diamond_{l'} \phi$, and $\sqcup_{l'} \phi$.

REMARK 3.6.6. We unpack the modalities \diamond , \square , \diamond , \diamond , \sqcup , and \diamond . We consider each modality in turn.

²⁹Is unpacking this three times overdone? Not really. We will use \sqcup_l a lot, so it might help some readers to explicitly unpack a range of possible contexts. If these three formulations and their equivalence are already obvious to the reader, then so much the better.

1. Modality $\diamond \phi$

$$\begin{aligned} p, x, H \models \diamond \phi &\iff \forall () \in *. \exists p' \in \bigcap \emptyset. p', \downarrow, H \models \phi \\ &\iff \exists p' \in \mathbf{P}. p', \downarrow, H \models \phi. \end{aligned}$$

$\forall () \in *$ denotes a choice of elements from the empty product $*$. This has one element: the 0-tuple $()$. Then $\bigcap \emptyset$ denotes taking the intersection of *no* subsets of \mathbf{P} , which by convention is \mathbf{P} .

So $p, x, H \models \diamond \phi$ just looks for some p' such that $p', \downarrow, H \models \phi$.

Subtlety alert: because of how \diamond ‘resets’ the current maybe-event from $x \in \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$ to \downarrow , it is not necessarily the case that $w \models E \Rightarrow \diamond E$. For a counterexample, take $\mathbf{P} = \{p\}$ and $\mathbf{Event} = \{E\}$ and $\mathbb{H} = \{(p, E, \emptyset)\}$ and $w = (p, E, \emptyset)$. The reader can check that $w \models E$ but $w \not\models \diamond E$.

We will never notice this edge case because we will only ever use \diamond (and indeed \square ; see next point) in situations where the current maybe-event is of no interest.

2. Modality $\square \phi$

This is just dual to $\diamond \phi$:

$$\begin{aligned} p, x, H \models \square \phi &\iff \exists () \in *. \forall p' \in \bigcap \emptyset. p', \downarrow, H \models \phi \\ &\iff \forall p' \in \mathbf{P}. p', \downarrow, H \models \phi. \end{aligned}$$

Note again a subtlety that it is not necessarily the case that $w \models \square \phi \Rightarrow \phi$. For a counterexample, take $\mathbf{P} = \{p\}$ and $\mathbf{Event} = \{E\}$ and $\mathbb{H} = \{(p, E, \emptyset)\}$ and $w = (p, E, \emptyset)$. Then $w \models \square \neg E$ but $w \not\models \neg E$.

3. Modality $\diamond \downarrow \phi$

This is a particularly important case. Recall that $\diamond \downarrow$ is sugar for $\diamond \downarrow$. The denotation is:

$$\begin{aligned} w \models \diamond \downarrow \phi &\stackrel{L3.6.4(3)}{\iff} \forall () \in *. \exists w' \ll w. (\text{place}(w') \in \bigcap \emptyset \wedge w' \models \phi) \\ &\iff \exists w' \ll w. (\text{place}(w') \in \mathbf{P} \wedge w' \models \phi) \\ &\iff \exists w' \ll w. w' \models \phi. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

We unpack how this works. First, we use Lemma 3.6.4(3). Then we simplify. $\forall () \in *$ denotes a choice of elements from the empty product $*$; this has one element the 0-tuple $()$. Then $\bigcap \emptyset$ denotes taking the intersection of *no* subsets of \mathbf{P} , which by convention is \mathbf{P} .

The idea of equation (1) is straightforward: $w \models \diamond \downarrow \phi$ means that ϕ holds at a world accessible from w . The traditional meaning of the modal *diamond* operator in Kripke semantics is precisely that $\diamond \phi$ holds when ϕ holds at some accessible world. In this sense, $\diamond \downarrow$ (not \diamond) is the natural modal diamond of our logic.

4. Modality $\Box\phi$

The reader can check that $w \models \Box\phi$ if and only if $w \models \neg\Diamond\neg\phi$, so this is the de Morgan dual of \Diamond . It is the modal ‘box’ operator to \Diamond ’s modal ‘diamond’: it means that ϕ holds at *every* accessible world, i.e.

$$w \models \Box\phi \iff \forall w' \ll w. w' \models \phi.$$

5. Modality \Diamond

$w \models \Diamond\phi$ means that for *some* $p' \in \mathbf{P}$, *every* event-tuple $w' \ll w$ such that $w' \in \mathbb{H}_{@p'}$ is such that $w' \models \phi$. In symbols:

$$w \models \Diamond\phi \iff \exists p' \in \mathbf{P}. \forall w' \ll w. (place(w') = p' \implies w' \models \phi).$$

6. Modality \Downarrow

$w \models \Downarrow\phi$ means that for *every* $p' \in \mathbf{P}$, *some* $w' \ll w$ exists with $place(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$ holds.

REMARK 3.6.7. Remark 3.6.6 describes six modalities: \Diamond , \Box , \Diamond , \Downarrow , \Box , and \Downarrow . These are all derived by suitable combinations of core modalities \Diamond , \neg , and \Downarrow , but our six modalities have a life of their own in the mathematics to follow, so (even if they can be decomposed) we can treat them as independent conceptual entities.³⁰

Conceptually, it may be more relevant to say that there are three dual pairs of modalities — to have one element of the pair is also, in some sense, to have the other:

- $\Diamond = \neg\Box\neg$ and $\Box = \neg\Diamond\neg$.
- $\Downarrow = \neg\Box\neg$ and $\Box = \neg\Downarrow\neg$.
- $\Diamond = \neg\Downarrow\neg$ and $\Downarrow = \neg\Diamond\neg$.

Do we need all of them?

Yes. The reader can find them all mentioned in our axioms and correctness properties: see for example Figure 6 (theory of liveness), Figure 7 (axioms of theory ThyHBB1), and Figure 8 (correctness properties of ThyHBB1).³¹

REMARK 3.6.8. Figures 4 and 5 do not exhaust the design space of modalities. We take a moment to mention other possible modalities (for simplicity we may omit $l_1 \dots l_n$ subscripts):

³⁰Analogy: every number can be derived by combining 0 with a suitable number of applications of the successor function. But this does *not* make number theory trivial, nor can we understand ‘three’ just by saying “it’s just some combination of 0 and successor”. 3 is its own thing relative to 0, just as \Downarrow is its own thing relative to \Diamond and \Box .

³¹*Technical note:* some uses of \Box in the maths could be equivalently replaced with \Box or \Downarrow . For example, in Proposition 6.5.3 the condition $\models \Box_l \text{live}$ could equivalently be written $\models \Box_l \text{live}$. In the presence of axiom (LiveAlways) these formulations are equivalent. We see this more as a technical observation because what we want to express in the precondition to Proposition 6.5.3 is “*there is a l-quorum of live participants*”, which is most naturally expressed as $\Box_l \text{live}$.

1. An *at some non-strictly preceding event* modality $\Downarrow\phi$ such that

$$w \models \Downarrow\phi \iff (w \models \phi \vee \exists w' \ll w. w' \models \phi).$$

This looks like \downarrow from Figure 3, but it uses a non-strict notion of ‘in the past’ which might include the present.

2. An *at some future* modality $\Uparrow\phi$ such that

$$w \models \Uparrow\phi \iff \exists w' \in \mathbb{H}. (w \ll w' \wedge w' \models \phi).$$

We do not need this for our axioms or correctness properties so far, so we omit it from the main development, but is a perfectly reasonable definition.

3. An **at every possible world** modality

$$\Box\phi \quad \text{meaning} \quad \forall w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). w \models \phi,$$

and its dual **at some possible world** $\Diamond\phi$ meaning $\exists w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). w \models \phi$. We do not put this modality directly into our predicate syntax in Figure 2 (we could; we just do not need to for now) — but we *will* see it in our notion of validity in equation (3) in Definition 5.2.1.

4. We can construct an *at every event in history* modality as $\Uparrow\Box\phi$ meaning $\forall w \in \mathbb{H}. w \models \phi$, and its dual *at some event in history* $\Uparrow\Diamond\phi$ meaning $\exists w \in \mathbb{H}. (w \models \phi)$. Note that $\Box\phi$ is not the same thing as $\Uparrow\Box\phi$ (at every possible world in \mathbb{H}), nor is it the same thing as $\Uparrow(\Box\phi \wedge \square\phi)$ (at every possible world in \mathbb{H} or at the end of time), and \Diamond is not the same thing as $\Uparrow\Diamond\phi$ or $\Uparrow(\Diamond\phi \vee \diamond\phi)$. There may exist event-tuples in $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ that are not in \mathbb{H} and are not of the form $(p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H})$. This is deliberate, and motivated by the semantics for \Diamond in Figure 3 (cf. footnote 27, which is based on a similar observation).

These and other modalities exist in a rich design space supported by our models.

REMARK 3.6.9. Definition 3.4.2 (possible worlds and the accessibility relation) and Definition 3.4.10 (validity) define a Kripke structure and a modal logic over it. Let us just spell this out explicitly. Given a model $\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \varrho, \varsigma)$, the corresponding Kripke structure $\mathcal{K}(\mathbb{M})$ is as follows:

- The set of possible worlds is $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ from Definition 3.4.2(2).
- The accessibility relation $w' \ll w$ is as per Definition 3.4.2(3) (namely: $w' \in \text{time}(w)$).
- We deem an E to hold at $w = (p, x, H)$ when $E = x$, and we deem an atomic predicate P to hold at w when $P \in \varrho(p, H)$ (see the predicate interpretation of \mathbb{M} ; Definition 3.3.3(3)).

So far, so straightforward. But there are some subtleties to this:

1. Not every possible world in $\mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ is an element of \mathbb{H} . On the contrary, there are many possible worlds that are not of this form, because of how \uparrow and \diamond are interpreted (see the discussion in Remark 3.4.11(2)).
2. The modalities — in-the-past \downarrow , end-of-time \uparrow , and the diamond modality $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n}$ — are *specific*, in the sense that they reflect structure that cannot be understood purely in terms of the accessibility relation on worlds. \diamond and \square are not specific in this sense: we can understand them purely in terms of \ll : they are just the standard diamond (‘for some accessible world’) and box (‘for all accessible worlds’) modalities in the usual modal sense (see Remark 3.6.6(3&4)).

But other modalities are not standard at all: to interpret \downarrow we require \ll which is a specific structure that enriches \ll with a notion of ‘same participant’; and \uparrow requires a notion of ‘end-of-time’.³² Then, and most strikingly, $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n}$ does its own idiosyncratic thing having to do with the existence of participants in quorum intersections.³³

So $\mathcal{K}(\mathbb{M})$ is ‘a Kripke structure’ similarly to how a lion is ‘a cat’: the generic description is true but elides specific characteristics that can matter a lot when we interact with the specific beast in question.

Working out what abstract properties $\mathcal{K}(\mathbb{M})$ has, above and beyond being a Kripke model, that give it its own particular and specific character, is future work.

3. We have not one, but *three* relevant notions of validity (and we will use all three).

All the above is to say to the reader who is expert in modal logic that: yes, this is a modal logic, and it does modal-flavoured things with things that look like modalities, but that is not the end of it. The choice of definitions, modalities, and the design of their semantics, is specific and crafted to satisfy specific constraints and expressivity requirements as imposed by the axiomatic theories and correctness proofs which we will see later.

Empirically, those design constraints are surprisingly stringent, in the sense that deviation from the design presented here seems to be punished by messy and/or incorrect proofs. This design did not write itself: we had to work to find it.³⁴

³²To be fair, this could be understood as finding an \ll -final possible world.

³³Idiosyncratic: *belonging to one’s peculiar and individual character*.

$\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_2}$ is undeniably a modality, but from the point of view of Kripke semantics there is nothing generic about it. It is motivated by specific notions of quorum intersections from distributed systems. Arguably, this modality is what imports the essence of distributed systems into a Kripke-logic style framework.

³⁴It remains to study classes of logics based on protocols other than Bracha Broadcast, to see how robust this logical design is. Perhaps it will turn out that each family of protocols has its own characteristic logic; or perhaps the logics will all be fundamentally similar, and all we need to do is perhaps tweak the modalities as per Remark 3.6.8. Most likely it will be some mixture of both. Finding this out will make

4. The modalities

Remarks 3.6.5 and 3.6.6 might give an impression that the modalities created from the combination of \diamond , \downarrow , and \neg — namely \diamond , \square , \diamond , \downarrow , \diamond , and \downarrow — will play an important role in what will follow. This impression is correct: we now develop more of the relevant theory.

4.1. Quorum intersection properties

A common theme in distributed systems is quorum intersection properties. A typical assumption has the form ‘any n quorums intersect’, for a value of n that may depend on the protocol under consideration. Common values are $n = 2$ or $n = 3$; see e.g. the Q^2 property from [DDFN07, Theorem 1], and the Q^3 property of [ACTZ24, Definition 2] or [HM00, page 4]. There is even a theorem that consensus requires $n \geq 3$; see [AW04, Theorem 5.8]. Going further back, Bracha’s original papers assumed the same thing, though for him quorum intersection was a corollary of a stronger cardinality assumption. See “In this section we show that the protocol in Fig. 1 achieves Asynchronous Byzantine agreement for $0 \leq t < n/3$ ” [Bra84, Subsection 3.2] and “[we present] a randomized consensus protocol that tolerates up to $t < n/3$ Byzantine processes” [Bra87, Page 133]. In the semitopological literature, these ideas appear as topological notions. An *intertwined space* from [Gab24, Gab25b] corresponds to any two quorums intersecting; and n -way intersection properties are considered in generality in a section on *n-twined semitopologies* in [GZ25].

Here, we will exploit an elegant way to express quorum intersection properties logically, using the \diamond modality:

LEMMA 4.1.1. *Suppose $l_1, \dots, l_n \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and suppose ϕ is a closed predicate. Then:*

1. $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$ if and only if every n -way quorum intersection between an n -tuple of l_1, \dots, l_n -quorums, contains some p such that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$.
2. $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \mathbf{T}$ if and only if every n -way quorum intersection between an n -tuple of l_1, \dots, l_n -quorums is nonempty.
3. $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$ implies $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \mathbf{T}$.

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. Routine from the clause for \diamond in Figure 3.
2. $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \mathbf{T}$ always by Figure 5. We use part 1 of this result.
3. Using the fact that $\phi \Rightarrow \mathbf{T}$. □

Some notation will be useful.

for interesting future research, for new logics, and hopefully it will lead us to improved protocols and improved confidence in existing ones.

NOTATION 4.1.2. Suppose $l_1, \dots, l_n \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and suppose $\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbb{H}, \varrho, \zeta)$ is a model (Definition 3.3.3). Then consider the following validity judgements:

$$\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \mathbf{T} \quad \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \text{seq} \quad \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \text{live}$$

- When $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \mathbf{T}$, say that $l_1 \dots l_n$ have **nonempty quorum intersections**, or just that they have **intersecting quorums**.
By Lemma 4.1.1(1) this means that for every n -tuple of quorums $O_1 \in \zeta(l_1), \dots, O_n \in \zeta(l_n)$ the intersection $O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n$ is nonempty.
- When $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \text{seq}$, say that $l_1 \dots l_n$ have **sequential quorum intersections**.
By Lemma 4.1.1(1) this means that for every n -tuple of quorums $O_1 \in \zeta(l_1), \dots, O_n \in \zeta(l_n)$ the intersection $O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n$ contains a sequential participant.
- When $\models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \text{live}$, say that $l_1 \dots l_n$ have **live quorum intersections**.
By Lemma 4.1.1(1) this this means that every n -tuple of quorums $O_1 \in \zeta(l_1), \dots, O_n \in \zeta(l_n)$ contains a live participant.

4.2. Modal properties

Modal logics are a rich field. The traditional study of modal logics has done a particularly nice job of building up a library of named axiomatic properties. To take one example, the reader might have seen the axiom “ $\Box A \implies \Box \Box A$ ” — traditionally this is called (4) in the literature. Accessible surveys are in [Gar24, GKWZ03].³⁵

Our set of modalities has a rich yet specific texture, since it includes \downarrow (in the past), \uparrow (end of time), and modality-schemes parameterised over lists of learners $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n}$, $\boxplus_{l_1 \dots l_n}$, $\boxminus_{l_1 \dots l_n}$, and their \Box -duals. Many interactions are possible; here we will study what is relevant to and/or required for our proofs.

LEMMA 4.2.1. *Suppose $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ and $l, l_1, \dots, l_n \in \mathbf{Learner}$, and suppose ϕ is a closed predicate. Then:*

1. $w \models \boxplus_l \phi \implies \boxplus \phi$.
This is reminiscent of the traditional (D) axiom from modal logic, which is usually written “ $\Box A \implies \Diamond A$ ”. In the standard Kripke semantics for (standard) modal logic, it corresponds to the accessibility relation being serial (there is always an accessible world).
2. $\models \Box \phi \implies \Diamond \phi$ and $\models \Box_l \phi \implies \Diamond \phi$.
3. $w \models \Box_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$ does not necessarily imply $w \models \Diamond \phi$.
4. $w \models \phi$ does not necessarily imply $w \models \Diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$.

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

³⁵A short but useful map, with names, can be found at <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/logic-modal/#MapRelBetModLog>.

1. By Remark 3.6.5(2) $w \models \Box_l \phi$ when there exists $O \in \zeta(l)$ such that for every $p' \in O$ there exists $w' \ll w$ such that $place(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$. Now $O \subseteq \mathbf{P}$ is assumed nonempty by Definition 3.3.2(3), so by assumption there exists *some* $p' \in O$ and $w' \ll w$ such that $place(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$. Thus there exists $w' \ll w$ such that $w' \models \phi$, and by Remark 3.6.6(3) $w \models \Diamond \phi$.
2. $\models \Box_l \phi \Rightarrow \Diamond \phi$ follows by similar arguments to part 1, or directly from part 1 taking $\phi = \neg \phi'$.
 $\models \Box \phi \Rightarrow \Diamond \phi$ also follows by similar arguments to part 1, using the fact in Definition 3.3.3 that we assumed $\mathbf{P} \neq \emptyset$.
3. The intersection $O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n$ might be empty.
4. p need not be in *every* quorum intersection (indeed, as just observed, the intersection might be empty). \square

LEMMA 4.2.2. *Suppose $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ and ϕ is a closed predicate. Then*

$$w \models \Diamond \Diamond \phi \Rightarrow \Diamond \phi.$$

This corresponds to the traditional (4) axiom from modal logic, which is usually written dually as “ $\Box A \Rightarrow \Box \Box A$ ” and is one of the signature axioms of the modal logic S4. In the standard Kripke semantics for (standard) modal logic, it corresponds to the accessibility relation being transitive.

Proof. We reason using equation (1) in Remark 3.6.6 and Proposition 3.4.5 (transitivity of the accessibility relation), as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} w \models \Diamond \Diamond \phi &\iff \exists w'' \ll w' \ll w. w'' \models \phi && \text{Equation (1)} \\ &\implies \exists w'' \ll w. w'' \models \phi && \text{Proposition 3.4.5} \\ &\iff w \models \Diamond \phi && \text{Equation (1)} \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

LEMMA 4.2.3. *Suppose $w \in \mathbf{World}(\text{model})$ and $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and ϕ is a closed predicate. Then:*

1. $w \models \Downarrow_l \phi \Rightarrow \Box_l \phi$.
2. $w \models \Diamond \Box_l \phi \Rightarrow \Box_l \phi$.

This axiom seems analogous to the traditional (B) axiom, usually written dually as “ $\Diamond A \Rightarrow \Box \Diamond A$ ” (‘B’ stands for the logician Brouwer), and is the signature axiom of the modal logic B. In the standard Kripke semantics for (standard) modal logic, it corresponds to the accessibility relation being symmetric.

3. *The reverse implications need not hold.*

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. By Figure 3, if $w \models \downarrow \sqcup_l \phi$ then there exists $w' \ll w$ (Definition 3.4.2(4)) such that $w' \models \sqcup_l \phi$. By Remark 3.6.5(2) there exists an l -quorum $O \in \zeta(l)$ of participants such that for every $p' \in O$ there exists $w' \ll w$ such that $place(w') = p'$ and $w' \models \phi$.
By Proposition 3.4.5 (transitivity of the accessibility relation; since $w' \ll w$) also $w'' \ll w$ and by Remark 3.6.5(2) again, $w \models \sqcup_l \phi$ as required.
2. The argument for part 2 is almost identical.
3. It suffices to provide a counterexample. Consider **Event** = $\{E_1, E_2, F\}$ (three distinct events) and **P** = $\{p\}$ (just one participant) and one learner l with one quorum equal to **P**. Define

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \{(p, E_1, \emptyset)\} & H_2 &= \{(p, E_2, \emptyset)\} \\ H_3 &= \{(p, F, H_1)\} \cup H_1 & H_4 &= \{(p, F, H_2)\} \cup H_2 \\ \mathbb{H} &= H_3 \cup H_4 \end{aligned}$$

We illustrate \mathbb{H} in derivation tree style:

$$\frac{\frac{}{p \vdash E_1} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash E_2}}{p \vdash F} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash F}}{\text{end of time}}$$

Then the reader can check that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \sqcup_l F$ but $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \neg \downarrow \sqcup_l F$ and $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \neg \diamond \sqcup_l F$.³⁶ □

5. Sequentiality and liveness

5.1. Properties of sequentiality

As per Definition 3.4.9, p is *sequential* at H when event-tuples in H starting with p are linearly ordered. Our logic in Figures 2 and 3 internalises sequentiality via a predicate *seq*. In this Subsection, we study sequentiality in more detail.

EXAMPLE 5.1.1. We start with an example to illustrate how sequentiality can be quite subtle. Consider

$$H = \{(p, E, \emptyset), (p, \downarrow, \{(p, E, \emptyset)\})\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{H} = H \cup \{(p, E', \emptyset)\}.$$

In derivation tree style we illustrate \mathbb{H} as

$$\frac{\frac{}{p \vdash E} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash E'}}{p \vdash \downarrow}$$

Note that $p, \downarrow, H \models \text{seq}$ (this is trivially so, because there is only one event in the past of H) but $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \not\models \text{seq}$.

³⁶This kind of behaviour is what our theory of liveness from Figure 6 is designed to exclude.

With the machinery we have built so far, we can give an attractive characterisation of the clause for $w \models \text{seq}$ in Figure 3:

LEMMA 5.1.2. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then the following are equivalent:*

1. $w \models \text{seq}$.
2. $\{w' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) \mid w' \ll w\}$ is linearly ordered by \ll .

Proof. By Figure 3 $w \models \text{seq}$ holds when $\text{place}(w)$ is sequential in $\text{time}(w)$. We check the equivalence by unpacking the definition of sequentiality (Definition 3.4.9(1)) and of the in-place accessibility relation (Definition 3.4.2(4)) and seeing that it is so. \square

LEMMA 5.1.3. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w, w' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then*

$w' \ll w$ implies $\{w'' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) \mid w'' \ll w'\} \subseteq \{w'' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) \mid w'' \ll w\}$.

Proof. By routine reasoning from the definition of \ll (Definition 3.4.2(4)) and transitivity of \ll on history structures (Proposition 3.4.5). \square

PROPOSITION 5.1.4 (Sequentiality monotone). *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w', w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then:*

1. If $w' \ll w$ then $w \models \text{seq}$ implies $w' \models \text{seq}$.
2. $w \models \text{seq} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \text{seq}$.

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. By Lemma 5.1.2 $w \models \text{seq}$ when $\{w' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}) \mid w' \ll w\}$ is linearly ordered by \ll . We use Lemma 5.1.3.
2. By Figure 5 $w \models \Downarrow \text{seq}$ when $\forall w' \ll w. w' \models \text{seq}$, but this just re-states part 1 of this result. \square

Proposition 5.1.5 is fundamental to our treatment of sequentiality:

PROPOSITION 5.1.5. *Suppose that:*

- \mathbb{M} is a model and $w = (p, x, H) \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$.
- $l, l' \in \mathbf{Learner}$.
- ϕ and ϕ' are closed predicates and E, E' are distinct events (meaning $E \neq E'$).

Then:

1. $w \models \Diamond_{ll'} \text{seq} \wedge \Box_l \phi \wedge \Box_{l'} \phi'$ implies $w \models \text{seq} \wedge \Downarrow \phi \wedge \Downarrow \phi'$.
2. $w \models \text{seq} \wedge \Downarrow E \wedge \Downarrow E'$ implies $w \models \Diamond (E \wedge \Downarrow E') \vee \Diamond (E' \wedge \Downarrow E)$.
3. $w \models \Diamond_{ll'} \text{seq} \wedge \Box_l E \wedge \Box_{l'} E'$ implies $w \models \Diamond (E \wedge \Downarrow E') \vee \Diamond (E' \wedge \Downarrow E)$.

Proof. We consider each part in turn. We may write w as (p, x, H) without comment:

1. Assume $w \models \diamond_{ll'} \text{seq} \wedge \sqcup_l \phi \wedge \sqcup_{l'} \phi'$.
 - Following the clause for \diamond in Figure 3, $w \models \diamond_{ll'} \text{seq}$ means that any l -quorum intersects any l' -quorum at some $p' \in \mathbf{P}$ such that $p, \downarrow, H \models \text{seq}$.
 - By Figure 4 $\sqcup_l = \square_l \downarrow$, and it follows that $w \models \sqcup_l \phi$ and $w \models \sqcup_{l'} \phi'$ mean that there exist an l -quorum of participants p' satisfying $p', \downarrow, H \models \downarrow \phi$ and an l' -quorum of participants p' satisfying $p', \downarrow, H \models \downarrow \phi'$.

Therefore, there exists $p' \in \mathbf{P}$ such that $p', \downarrow, H \models \text{seq} \wedge \downarrow \phi \wedge \downarrow \phi'$, and so $w \models \text{seq} \wedge \downarrow \phi \wedge \downarrow \phi'$ as required.

2. Suppose $w \models \text{seq} \wedge \downarrow E \wedge \downarrow E'$.
Since $w \models \text{seq}$, by Lemma 5.1.2 events in $H@p$ are linearly ordered. We assumed that $E \neq E'$, and so E happens before E' or vice versa. The result follows.
3. We combine parts 1 and 2 of this result. □

REMARK 5.1.6 (Design alternative: Sequentiality vs. orderability). Sequentiality is a maximalist condition: intuitively, it is the strongest well-behavedness property we could require on a participant, short of allowing it to control other participants or to see the future.

When we look at how our sequentiality property is actually used in the proofs, we see that its full power is not required. It would suffice to replace seq in Figure 3 with the following weaker (and thus more general) **orderability** predicate ord :

$$w \models \text{ord} \iff \forall E \neq E' \in \text{Event}. w \models (\downarrow E \wedge \downarrow E') \Rightarrow (\downarrow (E \wedge E') \vee \downarrow (E' \wedge E)) \quad (2)$$

Morally this is just Proposition 5.1.4(2). We could even present orderability as an axiom-scheme ThyOrd with one axiom for each choice of distinct E and E' as follows:

$$(\text{Order}) \quad \text{ord} \Rightarrow (\downarrow E \wedge \downarrow E') \Rightarrow (\downarrow (E \wedge E') \vee \downarrow (E' \wedge E))$$

This expresses intuitively that events at p are orderable in the sense that if p has E and E' then it has E' followed by E , or E followed by E' .

Orderability is weaker than sequentiality, because the above need not be the same instances of E and E' . We construct an example to illustrate this, in the derivation-tree style of Examples 2.3.8 and 2.3.10. Assume one participant p

and an event `echo`. Consider the following history structure:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{p \vdash \text{echo}(1)}}{} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash \text{echo}(0)}}{p \vdash \text{echo}(0)} \quad \frac{\frac{}{p \vdash \text{echo}(1)}}{} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash \text{echo}(3)}}{p \vdash \text{echo}(3)}}{p \vdash \text{echo}(2), \text{echo}(3)}$$

This example history structure p is orderable in the sense of equation 2, but it is not sequential in the sense of Definition 3.4.9. This is because sequentiality requires events to be linearly ordered, which clearly they are not in the example above; but nothing in the orderability clause insists that the E and E' mentioned to the left of the implication are the same instances as the E and the E' that occur in order to the right of the implication.

In fact, an even simpler example is possible:

$$\mathbb{H} = \{(p, \downarrow, \emptyset), (p, \text{echo}(), \emptyset)\} \quad \text{or in tree form} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash \downarrow} \quad \frac{}{p \vdash \text{echo}()}$$

p is orderable in \mathbb{H} , but not sequential. The reader might like to prove this (answer in footnote).³⁷

Orderability is weaker than sequentiality, and weak assumptions are generally preferable if they lead to the same results. We could remove `seq` from Figures 2 and 3 and instead use a predicate `ord` with a ‘theory of orderability’ `ThyOrd` — much as we will define a ‘theory of liveness’ `ThyLive` in Figure 6. This would be morally satisfying (a smaller core logic with more heavy lifting done by axioms is generally good practice) *and* more general.

Nevertheless, for now we use sequentiality: it is easier to think about, has a clear visual interpretation, and it is pragmatically justified as corresponding to what we think of as a participant following a protocol step-by-step.

5.2. A logical theory of liveness

5.2.1. (Axiomatic) theories

We have built a notion of model (Definition 3.3.3), and notions of logical validity over a model given by $w \models$, \models , and $\boxtimes \models$ from Figure 3. We are nearly ready to put this together to develop an axiomatic theory of what it means to be *live*, which we will do in Definition 5.2.4 and Figure 6.

First, we need to state what an axiomatic theory is, and what it means for such a theory to be valid in a model. Recall from from Figure 3, that

- $\models \phi$ means $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi$ for every $p \in \mathbf{P}$, and

³⁷There is only one event to order, namely `echo()`. The other event-tuple in this example uses the maybe-event `↓`. This is not an event! Thus, it is not in the domain of quantification for the E and E' in equation (2).

- $\boxed{w} \models \phi$ means $w \models \phi$ for every $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$.

Our notion of validity of a theory in a model is based on $\boxed{w} \models \phi$, as follows:

DEFINITION 5.2.1. Suppose Σ is a signature (Definition 3.1.1).

1. An **axiom** (over Σ) is a closed predicate ϕ in the syntax of Figure 2.
2. Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model for Σ (Definition 3.3.3) and suppose ϕ is an axiom (over Σ). Call ϕ **valid** of \mathbb{M} when

$$\boxed{w} \models \phi \quad \text{meaning} \quad \forall w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M}). w \models \phi. \quad (3)$$

3. A **theory** is a (possibly infinite) set of axioms.³⁸
4. Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model for Σ (Definition 3.3.3) and suppose Thy is a theory over Σ . We define $\boxed{w} \models \text{Thy}$ by

$$\boxed{w} \models \text{Thy} \quad \text{when} \quad \forall \phi \in \text{Thy}. (\boxed{w} \models \phi).$$

In words, a theory is valid when each of axioms is valid. In this case we may say that \mathbb{M} **satisfies** or **is a model of** Thy .

REMARK 5.2.2. Note that an axiom ϕ being valid in a model \mathbb{M} is based $\boxed{w} \models \phi$, as per equation 3 in Definition 5.2.1 above. That is, on its validity the time and place of every possible world.

Note that this definition is *not* based on $\models \phi$ (validity at every possible world at the end of time, i.e. having the form $(p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H})$).³⁹

In fact this is a matter of emphasis: we can derive the effect of $\models \phi$ using the validity judgement $\boxed{w} \models$, just by writing $\boxed{w} \models \uparrow\phi$. And indeed we do just this, in the two Knowledge axioms in Figure 6.

REMARK 5.2.3 (Design choice). An interesting design tension exists between two notions of *everywhere*:

- we have ‘at all events in history’, as in \boxed{t} , and
- we have ‘at all possible worlds’, as in \boxed{w} .

We use both notions, implicitly or explicitly, in our proofs.

There are deep reasons for this: it comes from the fact that our syntax in Figure 2 contains *events* and *predicates*. Events and predicates coexist in our syntax and our axioms, by design. For example, axiom (Safe) in Figure 7 mentions both a predicate *safe* and an event *propose*.

³⁸Infinite theories naturally exist. For instance, if the set of events **Event** is infinite (we will not consider any examples where this happens) then we might want an axiom-scheme parametric over infinitely many events.

Technically, ThyLive in Figure 6 is infinite provided there is at least one event and one learner, because it contains the Knowledge axiom-schemes, which are parameterised over events and lists of learners. See the discussion in Remark 5.2.6(1).

³⁹... It is also *not* based on $\models \uparrow\phi$ (validity at every possible world in \mathbb{H}).

(LiveAlways)	$\text{live} \leftrightarrow \uparrow \text{live}$
(LiveSeq)	$\text{live} \Rightarrow \text{seq}$
(Knowledge \diamond)	$\uparrow \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \downarrow \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$
(Knowledge \sqcup)	$\uparrow \sqcup_{l_1 \dots l_n} (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \downarrow \sqcup_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi$

Above: ϕ is a closed predicate and the \uparrow modality takes us to the end of time in the model (which we typically write as \mathbb{H}). Modalities like \uparrow , \diamond , and \sqcup bind less lightly than \Rightarrow . live is a predicate symbol and we shorten $\text{live}()$ to live , as per Notation 3.1.2.

Figure 6. ThyLive: a theory of liveness (Definition 5.2.4)

Events interact most naturally with \sqcup (because the history of a model is fundamentally a set of event-tuples); whereas predicates interact most naturally with \sqcap (because predicates are true or false at a possible world regardless of whether anything happens there). Our proofs will flow naturally, but under the surface there is this subtle design tension between predicates whose design shape suits \sqcap , and events whose design shape suits \sqcup . We accommodate this design tension as follows:

- The predicate syntax in Figure 2 includes event-based modalities like \downarrow , \diamond , and \sqcup . There is no \sqcap modality in the syntax.
- Our notion of axiomatic validity in Definition 3.4.10 uses an ‘at all possible-worlds’ based modality \sqcap .

This is a design choice: it seems to work well, but please just note that this was not *a priori* obvious, and other design choices might be possible and in other circumstances other choices might even be preferable. There is a design space here and we are free to use it as must convenient.

5.2.2. Definition of ThyLive

Intuitively, we call a participant p *live* when:

1. p does not crash, and
2. p correctly follows the algorithm.

Perhaps surprisingly, it is possible to render this intuition as an axiomatic theory ThyLive. Recall from Definition 5.2.1 that a theory is a set of closed predicates, which in this context we call *axioms*:

DEFINITION 5.2.4. Assume a signature with a predicate-symbol live . Let the **theory of liveness** ThyLive be as defined in Figure 6.

Note in Figure 6 that when we write $E \in \mathbf{Event}$, we really do mean $E \in \mathbf{Event}$ and not $E \in \mathbf{Event}_\downarrow$. Our syntax from Figure 2 does not admit \downarrow .

REMARK 5.2.5. We discuss the axioms of ThyLive in Figure 6:

- (LiveAlways): being live is a property of place, not of time.
(LiveAlways) expresses that p being live does not depend on the time H . This makes sense, because liveness is a property of a participant, not of the time of any event. During a run of an algorithm we cannot predict whether p will crash, because that would involve seeing the future. What ‘ p remains live during the run of the algorithm’ refers to is a property of p that only makes sense *after* the run of the algorithm is complete.
Note a subtlety that there is another important component to being live, that a live participant should progress according to the protocol. However, what ‘progress according to the protocol’ means is protocol-dependent. This part of liveness can be and is expressed on per-protocol basis as so-called *forward rules* in Figures 7, 9, and 11.
- (LiveSeq): live participants are sequential.
This is definitional. We define *live* to mean ‘does not crash *and* is sequential’. Being sequential, along with obeying the *forward rules*, captures the notion of ‘following the protocol’.
- (Knowledge \diamond) and (Knowledge \square): live participants communicate events.
The (Knowledge) axioms (actually axiom-schemes) reflects that if a live participant p knows something, it will (eventually) communicate this information to all other live participants.
So for example: if a quorum of live participants do some E , then (eventually) *every* live participant will know that a quorum of live participants have done E . The (Knowledge) axiom opens with \uparrow because this property is only true at the end of time. There are no guarantees about how long communication takes.

5.2.3. More on the Knowledge axioms

REMARK 5.2.6 (Some general observations on the Knowledge axioms).

1. (Knowledge \diamond) and (Knowledge \square) are axiom-schemes: technically, there is one pair of knowledge axioms for each choice of event and list of learners. Axiom-schemes are a standard device in logic.⁴⁰
2. The \uparrow modality in (Knowledge \diamond) and (Knowledge \square) is required. For example, this axiom is subtly wrong:

$$\text{(Wrong)} \quad \diamond_{I_1 \dots I_n} (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \diamond_{I_1 \dots I_n} \phi.$$

The reason is that, as discussed in Remark 5.2.2, axioms apply at *events*, but liveness is not about any single event, it is about events as viewed from the end of time.

⁴⁰In contrast, if an axiom mentions v or l — like the ones in Figure 7 — then this does not necessarily mean that they are axiom-schemes. As per standard notation in logic, an axiom is considered to be universally quantified over any free variables. Our logic has quantification over values, so an axiom that mentions values just has invisible \forall quantifiers quantifying those values at top level. We do not have an explicit quantification over events in the logic, so we use axiom-schemes.

To see what is wrong with (Wrong) as an axiom, consider a model with a live p that performs no action other than an initial event-tuple $(p, \downarrow, \emptyset)$. Then at that initial event-tuple $\diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} (\text{live} \wedge \phi)$ is trivially false, so (Wrong) is trivially satisfied. This is not what we intend, but we only see this from the end of time.

We will invoke the Knowledge axioms directly in what follows, but importantly, we also use them via Proposition 5.2.8 and in particular via the corollaries in Corollary 5.2.9. We need a technical observation for Proposition 5.2.8:

LEMMA 5.2.7. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $w \in \text{World}(\mathbb{M})$ and ϕ is a closed predicate. Then*

$$w \models \uparrow \diamond \phi \quad \text{implies} \quad \text{place}(w), \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond \phi.$$

In words: if at some time p knows of a past ϕ , then at the end of time there is a past ϕ .

Proof. By routine calculations from Figure 5. □

PROPOSITION 5.2.8. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $\mathbb{W} \models \text{ThyLive}$ (Figure 6) and suppose E is an event. Then*

$$\models \square_l \text{live} \quad \text{and} \quad \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge E) \quad \text{implies} \quad \models \perp_l (\text{live} \wedge \diamond E).$$

In words: if there is an l -quorum of live participants, and some live participant has an event E , then eventually there is an l -quorum of live participants who know that E occurred.

Proof. Suppose

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge E).$$

In words: there is an event in \mathbb{H} at which a live participant has E .

We assumed $\mathbb{W} \models \text{ThyLive}$ so — taking the empty list of learners in the (Knowledge \diamond) axiom-scheme — we have

$$\mathbb{W} \models \uparrow \diamond (\text{live} \wedge E) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \diamond E.$$

So consider some live $p \in \mathbf{P}$. We have that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge E)$ implies $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \text{live}$ implies $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \uparrow \diamond E$. It follows that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \uparrow \diamond E$ and so by Lemma 5.2.7 $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond E$. Since we assume that an l -quorum of live participants exists, we have $\models \perp_l (\text{live} \wedge \diamond E)$ as required. □

COROLLARY 5.2.9. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $\mathbb{W} \models \text{ThyLive}$ (Figure 6) and suppose $E \in \text{Event}$. Then:*

1. $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond E)$ implies $\models \perp_l (\text{live} \wedge \diamond E)$.
2. $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge E)$ implies $\models \perp_l (\text{live} \wedge \diamond E)$.

3. $\models \Box_l \text{live}$ and $\models \Diamond (\text{live} \wedge \Box_l E)$ implies $\models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \Box_l E)$.

Proof. Part 1 is from Proposition 5.2.8 taking $\phi = \Diamond E$ and using Lemma 4.2.2 ($\Diamond \Diamond E$ implies $\Diamond E$).

Part 2 is from Proposition 5.2.8 taking $\phi = E$.

Part 3 is from Proposition 5.2.8 taking $\phi = \Box E$, and using Lemma 4.2.3(2) ($\Diamond \Box_l E$ implies $\Box_l E$). \square

5.2.4. More on (LiveAlways)

LEMMA 5.2.10. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and satisfies ThyLive from Figure 6. Suppose $w, w' \in \mathbb{H}$ and $\text{place}(w) = \text{place}(w')$, and suppose $l \in \text{Learner}$. Then:*

1. $w \models \text{live}$ if and only if $\text{place}(w), \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \text{live}$.
2. $w \models \text{live}$ if and only if $w' \models \text{live}$.
3. $\models \text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \text{live}$.

Proof. Part 1 just restates (LiveAlways), unpacking the meaning of \uparrow in Figure 3.⁴¹ Part 2 follows by two uses of part 1. Part 3 follows by one use of part 1. \square

Proposition 5.2.11 is conceptually simple, and it turns out to be a key property for our Liveness 2 results (Propositions 6.4.5, 7.2.2, and 8.4.5):

PROPOSITION 5.2.11. *Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and $l_1, l_2 \in \text{Learner}$ and suppose ϕ is a closed predicate. Suppose further that*

$$\models \Diamond_{l_1 l_2} \mathbf{T} \quad \text{and} \quad \models \Box_{l_2} \text{live}.$$

Then

$$\models \Box_{l_1} \phi \quad \text{implies} \quad \models \Diamond (\text{live} \wedge \phi).$$

In words: if l_1 and l_2 have nonempty quorum intersections⁴² and l_2 has a quorum of live participants, then any l_1 -quorum of ϕ contains at least one live participant.

Proof. Suppose $\models \Box_{l_1} \phi$. By Lemma 4.1.1(2) (since $\models \Diamond_{l_1 l_2} \mathbf{T}$) every l_1 -quorum intersects every l_2 -quorum. Using Lemma 5.2.10(2) $\models \Diamond (\text{live} \wedge \phi)$ as required. \square

Lemma 5.2.12 has in common with Lemma 4.2.2 that it expresses in our logic a(nother) version of the (4) axiom from the modal logic S4. It is nice how the same basic axiomatic property arises in different ways, here for \Box_l -live:

⁴¹It is important here that $w \in \mathbb{H}$, instead of the more general condition that $w \in \text{World}(\mathbb{H})$. If we want to more general property we need to strengthen our notion of axiomatic validity to use \Box . See Remark 5.2.3. For our purposes, the Lemma as stated is enough.

⁴²This terminology is from Notation 4.1.2; it means that every intersection between an l_1 -quorum and an l_2 -quorum, is nonempty.

LEMMA 5.2.12. Suppose \mathbb{M} is a model and ϕ is a closed predicate and $l \in \text{Learner}$. Then

$$\models \Downarrow_l(\text{live} \wedge \phi) \quad \text{implies} \quad \models \Downarrow_l(\text{live} \wedge \Downarrow_l \phi).$$

In words: if an l -quorum of live participants know of past ϕ , then a quorum of live participants know of a quorum of live participants that know of past ϕ .

Proof. Suppose $\models \Downarrow_l(\text{live} \wedge \phi)$. Unpacking Remark 3.6.5(2) there exists an l -quorum $O \in \zeta(l)$ such that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \text{live} \wedge \downarrow \phi$ for every $p \in O$. Using (Knowledge \Downarrow) at each $p \in O$ we get $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \text{live} \wedge \downarrow \Downarrow_l \phi$ (we have \downarrow instead of \Downarrow on the right because this is at the end of time, so the two are equivalent). It follows using Lemma 5.2.10(3) that $\models \Downarrow_l(\text{live} \wedge \Downarrow_l \phi)$ as required. \square

REMARK 5.2.13 (Design choice). Our theory of liveness in Figure 6 does not exclude an empty model as per Example 3.3.5. This is a model with $\mathbb{H} = \emptyset$, in which there are no event-tuples in history and, intuitively, nothing happens.

Arguably this is pathological — in what sense is a participant who does nothing ‘live’ – and if the reader agrees then it is easy to add an axiom stating that every live participant performs *some* action. Using Lemma 3.5.3 we can concisely capture this idea as the following rather elegant axiom:

$$\text{(LiveActive)} \quad \uparrow \square(\text{live} \Rightarrow \downarrow \mathbf{T}) \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad \square(\text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \mathbf{T}).$$

We omit this from Figure 6 just because we do not need it for any of our correctness proofs. But it would cost nothing to add this axiom, if required.

6. Theory ThyHBB1

6.1. Definition of the theory

REMARK 6.1.1. Sections 6, 7, and 8 share a common structure. We take a moment to spell it out:

- Define a logical theory — ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3 respectively. Fix a model \mathbb{M} of that theory for the rest of the Section. Perhaps discuss the axioms.
- Prove Soundness/Agreement, then a Liveness 2 property, and then a Liveness 1 property. We gather the result for Theorems 6.1.6 (for ThyHBB1), 7.1.3 (for ThyHBB2), and 8.2.3 (for ThyHBB3).
- Discuss, and compare and contrast where appropriate with the other theories.

Our treatment of ThyHBB1 will be most detailed. Then, as we get used to the mathematics, we may elide routine details.

DEFINITION 6.1.2 (Theory ThyHBB1).

Backward rules (HBB)

(Echo?) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v)$
 (Vote?) $\text{vote}(l, v) \Rightarrow (\text{safe}(l) \wedge \boxplus_l \text{echo}(v))$
 (Deliver?) $\text{deliver}(l', l, v) \Rightarrow \boxplus_{l'} \text{vote}(l, v)$

Other rules

Include axioms of ThyLive from Figure 6
 (EchoNE) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$
 (Safe) $\text{safe}(l) \Leftrightarrow ((\exists_{\mathbf{0}1} v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \vee \forall l'. \diamond \boxplus_{l'} \text{seq})$

Forward rules

(Echo!) $(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{echo}(v')$
 (Vote!) $\uparrow \text{safe}(l) \Rightarrow (\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{vote}(l, v)$
 (Deliver!) $(\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_{l'} \text{vote}(l, v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l', l, v)$

Recall that \uparrow (sometimes) and \uparrow (everytime) are from Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 7. Theory ThyHBB1 (Definition 6.1.2)

1. Assume a signature (Definition 3.1.1) with event-symbols propose, echo, vote, and deliver, and with predicate-symbols live and safe.⁴³
2. Define ThyHBB1 in this signature to be the theory with axioms as per Figure 7.
3. For the rest of this Section, we fix a model \mathbb{M} of ThyHBB1, meaning that $\boxplus \models \text{ThyHBB1}$ as per Definition 5.2.1.

NOTATION 6.1.3. Here and in ThyHBB2, we will read $w \models \text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ as **place(w) delivers v for (l', l)**. We will call l the **source** learner and l' the **reporting** learner.⁴⁴

REMARK 6.1.4. We make some general observations about how ThyHBB1 generalises Bracha Broadcast. All three of our heterogeneous protocols generalise Bracha Broadcast’s quorums, such that there are multiple learners and each learner has its own quorum system — i.e. one set of trust assumptions — that may be different from that of a distinct learner. This is by design: it is what makes our setting ‘heterogeneous’.

Therefore, deliveries of values at the end of the protocol must be relative to a specific learner and its quorum system.

Several generalisations are possible here. In ThyHBB1 from Figure 7 we have a notion of delivering a value for a *pair* of learners: as per Notation 6.1.3 $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ is read ‘deliver v for (l', l) ’. Intuitively this means that

the delivering participant has observed an l' -quorum of participants who have

⁴³There are allowed to be other event-symbols and predicate-symbols, but we will not use them.

⁴⁴ThyHBB3 also has a notion of source and reporting learner, but the source learner is existentially quantified. See the discussion opening Section 8.

1. *Liveness 1*

If $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, l, v).$$

In words: suppose there is a live l -quorum and suppose precisely one value is proposed. Then if some live participant finds out about that proposed value, then every live participant eventually delivers.

2. *Liveness 2*

If $l'_1, l'_2, l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \top$ and $\models \text{safe}(l)$ and $\models \square_{l'} \text{live}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v).$$

In words: suppose l'_1 and l'_2 have nonempty quorum intersections and l is safe and there is a live l'_2 -quorum. Then if some participant delivers v for (l'_1, l) then every live participant delivers v for (l'_2, l) .

3. *Soundness / Agreement*

If $l_1, l_2, l'_1, l'_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \Rightarrow v_1 = v_2.$$

In words: suppose l'_1 and l'_2 have sequential quorum intersections. Then if some participant delivers v_1 for (l'_1, l_1) and another delivers v_2 for (l'_2, l_2) , then $v_1 = v_2$.

Figure 8. Correctness properties for ThyHBB1 (Theorem 6.1.6)

observed an l -quorum of participants who have observed $\text{propose}(v)$.⁴⁵

This makes the two-round structure from Bracha's original protocol explicit, in that delivery identifies which set of trust assumptions is used in each round.

We call l the *source* learner because its trust assumptions are used to determine when we have observed a quorum of echo (and thus propose) messages; we call l' the *reporting* learner because its trust assumptions are used to determine when we have observed a quorum of vote messages.

REMARK 6.1.5. The axioms from Figures 7, 9, and 11 fall into three groups:

- *backward rules* have names ending in ?,
- *forward rules* have names ending in !, and
- other rules.

We briefly explain this design (without going into details of specific rules; that discussion comes later):

- *Backward rules*: 'if we observe X , then we must have observed Y '.
(Echo?) is a typical backward rule. It says that if a participant does $\text{echo}(v)$ then it must know of a participant that did $\text{propose}(v)$.⁴⁶ (Vote?) and (Deliver?) follow a similar pattern.
- *Forward rules*: 'if X happens, then Y happens'.

These are not just the backward rules in reverse, because participants might fail or have choices in how to proceed, so forward rules tend to be a bit more complex than backward rules.

A case in point is (Echo!), which has liveness conditions and also a choice $\exists v'$; if a participant observes several propose messages, it is supposed to pick one to eventually echo.

An intriguing subtlety to the forward rules is that they are not really forward, at least not in the sense of time. For, consider that (Echo!) has a \Downarrow modality on its conclusion. Axiomatic validity is evaluated using the \Box \models validity judgement from Figure 3, meaning that for every $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ if $w \models (\text{live } \blacktriangle \Downarrow \text{propose}(v))$ then there exists a v' such that for *some* $w' \in \mathbb{H}$ with $\text{place}(w') = \text{place}(w)$ we have $w' \models \text{echo}(v')$. However, there is no condition on how $\text{time}(w)$ and $\text{time}(w')$ relate; for example it could even be that $\text{time}(w') \subsetneq \text{time}(w)$.

⁴⁵This is a simplification; we have elided the role of safe learners. See Remark 6.1.7 for a more detailed exposition.

⁴⁶We can put this strong condition even on byzantine participants because (for the protocols that interest us) we assume that messages are cryptographically signed, so no participant (not even a byzantine one) can forge a propose message. The first author's study of (homogeneous) Paxos did not assume such cryptographic guarantees, instead using a three-valued logic to represent byzantine behaviour, while retaining structurally similar axioms [GZ25].

This might seem odd, but remember that the backward rule (Echo?) still gives some guarantees. In particular, by (Echo?) there exists an $w'' \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ such that $w'' \models \text{propose}(v)$.

It is nevertheless remarkable that even with these somewhat weak conditions, we obtain a full suite of correctness results.

- *Other rules*

These represent assorted definitions, structural requirements on the model, or requirements on the protocol. In the case of ThyHBB1 these consist of:

- ThyLive, a structural requirement on the model (see Subsection 5.2),
- (EchoNE), a specific restriction on the protocol (see Remark 6.2.1), and
- (Safe), which defines the behaviour of a predicate safe (see Remark 6.2.2).

THEOREM 6.1.6. *In Figure 8 we collect the correctness properties we will require of our model \mathbb{M} such that $\boxed{\mathbb{M}} \models \text{ThyHBB1}$, for ease of reference.*

Proof. The relevant results are Propositions 6.5.3, 6.4.5, and 6.3.1 respectively. Proofs and discussion will follow. \square

REMARK 6.1.7. We can extract an abstract protocol from the axioms as follows, where we interpret atomic predicates as messages:

1. A proposer broadcasts $\text{propose}(v)$ for some value v .⁴⁷
2. p broadcasts $\text{echo}(v)$ for precisely one proposed value, provided it observes any proposals at all.
3. If p receives an l -quorum of $\text{echo}(v)$ messages and l is safe (so far as p knows at the time), then it broadcasts $\text{vote}(l, v)$.
 p considers l to be *safe* when at least one of the following conditions holds:
 - p only knows of at most one value that has been proposed.
 - For every learner l' and every l -quorum and l' -quorum, there is a participant in their intersection whom p has observed to be sequential.
4. If p receives an l' -quorum of $\text{vote}(l, v)$ messages then it broadcasts $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$.

It might help to spell out the intuitive logical content of each broadcast. We can write:

- $\text{propose}(v)$ means *I propose v*.

⁴⁷Our axiomatisation does not explicitly assume that a unique participant proposes, nor that precisely one value is proposed.

In an implementation, we would probably expect the proposer to be unique and to propose precisely one value. But we get our correctness properties without requiring this.

In part, this is because the Liveness 1 correctness property in Figure 8 is explicitly conditioned on assuming that precisely one value is proposed. Thus we can say that the practical assumption ‘assume one proposer who broadcasts a unique value’ is encoded precisely in that condition.

- $\text{echo}(v)$ means *I saw someone propose v .*
- $\text{vote}(l, v)$ means *I saw an l -quorum of participants who saw someone propose v , and l is a safe learner so far as I know.*
- $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ means *I saw an l' -quorum of participants who each believed l is a safe learner at a time when they saw an l -quorum of participants who saw someone propose v .*

6.2. Further discussion of some ThyHBB1 axioms

REMARK 6.2.1 (The (EchoNE) rule). ThyHBB1 from Figure 7 includes axiom (EchoNE), that

$$\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'.$$

Intuitively, this expresses that a sequential participant only ever echoes at most one value. (EchoNE) does permit a sequential participant to echo the same value multiple times, but it will not echo two distinct values one after the other.

This does not exclude hostile behaviour: a *nonsequential* participant can echo distinct values, just so long as they are in histories that are not \subseteq -comparable. This corresponds to p broadcasting $\text{echo}(v)$ to one group of participants, and $\text{echo}(v')$ to another group of participants, without telling one group about the value that it broadcast to the other.

In the literature this is called *equivocation*, defined informally as to make “conflicting statements to different processes” [CJKR12] or to “lie in different ways to different clients or servers” [CMSK07].⁴⁸

‘NE’ is short for ‘non-equivocation’, and non-equivocation axioms will be ubiquitous in our theories: ThyHBB2 from Figure 9 and ThyHBB3 from Figure 11 have the identical axiom (EchoNE), and ThyHBB3 includes a (VoteNE) axiom.

Our axioms are quite precise about what cannot be equivocated: just echo messages for ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2, and both echo and vote messages in ThyHBB3. We impose no further non-equivocation conditions, and this is a feature, because it means that our correctness results are robust against any other equivocation.

REMARK 6.2.2 (Axiom (Safe)). As touched on in Remark 6.1.7, (Safe) characterises $p, x, H \models \text{safe}(l)$ as holding when (as viewed from p, x, H)

- if two or more values have been proposed,

⁴⁸But surely a hostile participant could violate (EchoNE); just sequentially echo v and then echo v' ?

Yes, a hostile participant can do what it wants. But, if it broadcasts a history that violates (EchoNE) to an honest participant then that honest participant will refuse to accept that history as a well-formed message. So the force of (EchoNE) is not that it constrains hostile participants’ real-world behaviour; it is that it constrains hostile participants’ ability to influence the behaviour of honest ones.

This is a subtle difference between actual behaviour and a logical model of behaviour: our logical models can afford to be more abstract, even where they model hostile participants, essentially because we only care about hostile behaviour that might influence honest behaviour. This is a feature.

- then l has sequential quorum intersections with all other learners, meaning by Notation 4.1.2 that for every l -quorum O and every learner l' (including l) and every l' -quorum O' , there exists $q \in O \cap O'$ such that $q, \downarrow, H \models \text{seq}$.

The disjunct in (Safe) is there to give us the Liveness 1 property in Proposition 6.5.3, and specifically to give us Lemma 6.5.2: that if at most one value is proposed then every learner is safe.

Note from Figure 7 that being safe depends on quorum intersections being sequential. But the sequentiality condition is overspecified: sequentiality applies to *all* maybe-events, but in this protocol we only care about nonsequential echo events for distinct values.⁴⁹ If only one value is proposed then that is impossible.

REMARK 6.2.3. We study the fine structure of the (Echo!) axiom.

This expresses that if a live participant knows of a propose(v) then at some time that participant will perform echo(v') for some v' (which need not be equal to v). We mention a few subtleties to how this is constructed:

1. In full, (Echo!) is as follows — we just write out the implicit universal quantification over the v :

$$\forall v. (\text{live} \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \downarrow \text{echo}(v')).$$

2. Equivalent forms of (Echo!) exist, including:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{live} \Rightarrow (\exists v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)) &\Rightarrow \exists v'. \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \\ \text{live} \Rightarrow \downarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v) &\Rightarrow \exists v'. \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \end{aligned}$$

3. This axiom is subtly wrong:

$$\text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \diamond \text{propose}(v) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v').$$

We leave it to the reader to think why (sketch answer in footnote).⁵⁰

4. This axiom is wrong:

$$(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v')$$

This is wrong because by (EchoNE) a participant should echo at most *one* value. If a proposer proposes two values, each other participant is supposed supposed to pick one value and echo at most that value (and no other).

⁴⁹Likewise for ThyHBB2. In ThyHBB3 we care about nonsequential echo and *also* nonsequential vote events.

A rule of thumb is: nonsequentiality matters where it might break an axiom with a name of the form (EDup) for $E \in \mathbf{Event}$.

⁵⁰ $\uparrow \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ means that *some* participant knows of a propose(v), but does not guarantee that it is a live participant. A corrected version is $\uparrow \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v')$, but this is over-long because it folds in some of the power that is already included in the Knowledge axioms.

5. This axiom is correct and equivalent to what is written:

$$(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \exists v'. \text{echo}(v').$$

(We flip the existential quantifier $\exists v'$ and the *sometime* modality \uparrow .) While both forms are correct, as a matter of style and convenience here and elsewhere, we will follow a policy of putting quantifiers outside modalities where possible. This means that (working top-down through the predicate) we get to a proposition sooner rather than later.

REMARK 6.2.4 (A design alternative). We note in passing that (EchoNE) from Figure 7 is not the only possible non-equivocation axiom. We could impose a stronger condition:

$$(\text{EchoNE}') \quad \text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'.$$

All of our correctness properties would work just as well. We prefer (EchoNE) precisely because it is a weaker assumption; the weaker assumption means that our correctness results are stronger.

Intuitively — this is not a mathematical statement — (EchoNE') corresponds to an algorithm where we echo the first value we hear proposed, if we echo anything at all.⁵¹ (EchoNE) corresponds to an algorithm where we echo at most one of the values that we hear proposed, but it need not necessarily be the first one that we hear about.

6.3. Agreement

PROPOSITION 6.3.1 (Soundness / Agreement). *Suppose $l_1, l_2, l'_1, l'_2 \in \text{Learner}$ and $v_1, v_2 \in \text{Value}$ and*

$$\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq}.$$

Then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \Rightarrow v_1=v_2.$$

Proof. If $v_1 = v_2$ then there is nothing to prove, so it will be convenient (for the step marked ^(**) below) to assume $v_1 \neq v_2$ and derive a contradiction. We

⁵¹By axiom (Echo?), if we know of an $\text{echo}(v)$ then we also know of a $\text{propose}(v)$.

reason as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \wedge \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \\
& \implies \models \boxdot_{l'_1} \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \boxdot_{l'_2} \text{vote}(l_2, v_2) && \text{(Deliver?)} \\
& \implies \models \diamond (\text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l_2, v_2)) \vee \\
& \quad \models \diamond (\text{vote}(l_2, v_2) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l_1, v_1)) && \text{Prop 5.1.5(3), } v_1 \neq v_2, \\
& && \models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq} \\
& \implies w \models \text{vote}(l_2, v_2) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) && \text{2nd disjunct}^{(*)}, \text{ some} \\
& && w \in \mathbb{H} \text{ by Remark 3.6.6(3)} \\
& \implies w \models \text{safe}(l_2) \wedge \boxdot_{l_2} \text{echo}(v_2) \wedge \boxdot_{l_1} \text{echo}(v_1) && \text{(Vote?), Lemma 4.2.3(1)} \\
& \implies w \models \diamond_{l_2 l_1} \text{seq} \wedge \boxdot_{l_2} \text{echo}(v_2) \wedge \boxdot_{l_1} \text{echo}(v_1) && \text{(Safe)}^{(**)}, v_1 \neq v_2 \\
& \implies v_1 = v_2 && \text{Prop 5.1.5(3),} \\
& && v_1 \neq v_2, \text{(EchoNE)} \\
& \implies \perp && v_1 \neq v_2
\end{aligned}$$

We expand on two steps in the derivation above:

- (*) Just above the step marked (*), we have a disjunct between $\models \diamond (\text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l_2, v_2))$ or $\models \diamond (\text{vote}(l_2, v_2) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l_1, v_1))$. The first possibility is precisely symmetric with the second, so we just consider the second disjunct.
- (**) At the step marked (**) we go from $\text{safe}(l_2)$ to $\diamond_{l_2 l_1} \text{seq}$. The behaviour of safe is determined by (Safe) in Figure 7. This characterises safe using two disjuncts $\exists_{\mathbf{0}1} v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ or $\forall l'. \diamond_{ll'} \text{seq}$. The former disjunct is not valid because we are at a world at which we know of (quorums of, and thus) of some past $\text{echo}(v_2)$ and $\text{echo}(v_1)$, and using (Echo?) we know of some past $\text{propose}(v_2)$ and $\text{propose}(v_1)$ — and we assumed $v_1 \neq v_2$. Thus, the latter disjunct must be valid.

We note $v_1 \neq v_2$ using Proposition 5.1.5(3) above because the result requires *distinct* events. \square

6.4. Liveness 2

LEMMA 6.4.1. *Suppose $w' \ll w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$. Then:*

1. $w \models \text{safe}$ implies $w' \models \text{safe}$.
2. $w \models \text{safe} \implies \Downarrow \text{safe}$.

Proof. From the definition of safe in Figure 7, using Proposition 5.1.4 (seq monotone). \square

LEMMA 6.4.2. *Suppose ϕ and ψ are closed predicates and $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$. Then:*

1. $\models \boxdot_l \phi$ and $\boxtimes \models \phi \implies \uparrow \psi$ implies $\models \boxdot_l \psi$.

2. If $\boxplus \models \text{ThyLive}$ then

$$\models \sqcup_l (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \quad \text{and} \quad \boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi \quad \text{implies} \quad \models \sqcup_l (\text{live} \wedge \psi).$$

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. Suppose $\models \sqcup_l \phi$. By Remark 3.6.5(2) this means that there is an l -quorum O such that for each $p \in O$ there exists $w_p \in \mathbb{H}_{@p}$ such that $w_p \models \phi$. By our assumptions $w_p \models \phi \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi$ for each $p \in O$, and so by Lemma 3.6.4(1) there exists some $w'_p \in \mathbb{H}_{@p}$ such that $w'_p \models \psi$. This is true of every $p \in O$, and $\models \sqcup_l \psi$ follows.
2. First, note from Lemma 5.2.10(2) that

$$\boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi \quad \text{implies} \quad \boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \Downarrow (\text{live} \wedge \psi).$$

We can now just use part 1 of this result. □

LEMMA 6.4.3. *Suppose ϕ and ψ are closed predicates and $\boxplus \models \text{ThyLive}$. Then*

$$\models \text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \phi \quad \text{and} \quad \boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi \quad \text{implies} \quad \models \text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi.$$

Proof. We unpack definitions using Figures 3 (validity), 4 (syntactic sugar) and 5 (its denotation):

- By Figure 3 and Lemma 3.6.4(1), $\models \text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \phi$ means that for every live participant⁵² $p \in \mathbf{P}$ there exists some $w_p \in \mathbb{H}_{@p}$ (Definition 3.4.7) such that $w_p \models \phi$.
- By Figure 3, $\boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \phi) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi$ means that for every $w \in \mathbb{H}$, if $\text{place}(w)$ is live (by (LiveAlways) the time does not matter) then $w \models \phi$ implies that there exists some event-tuple $w' \in \mathbb{H}$ such that $\text{place}(w) = \text{place}(w')$ and $w' \models \psi$.
- $\models \text{live} \Rightarrow \Downarrow \psi$ holds when for every live participant $p \in \mathbf{P}$ there exists some $w_p \in \mathbb{H}_{@p}$ such that $w_p \models \psi$.

Putting the first two assumptions together we obtain the required conclusion. □

LEMMA 6.4.4. *Suppose ϕ is a closed predicate and $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$. Then*

$$\models \sqcup_l \Downarrow \phi \quad \text{if and only if} \quad \models \sqcup_l \phi.$$

Proof. By Figure 4, \Downarrow is sugar for $\Uparrow \Downarrow$. By Figure 3, $\models \sqcup_l \Downarrow \phi$ means $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \Uparrow \Downarrow \phi$ for every $p \in O$ for O some l -quorum. But it is clear from Figure 3 that $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \Uparrow \Downarrow \phi$ if and only if $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \Downarrow \phi$. Thus we can simplify $\models \sqcup_l \Downarrow \phi$ to $\models \sqcup_l \Downarrow \phi$, and by Figure 4 this is just $\models \sqcup_l \phi$ as required. □

⁵²Recall from Lemma 5.2.10(2) that by (LiveAlways) in Figure 6, it does not matter *when* p is live; p is either live or not live, at all $w \in \mathbb{H}_{@p}$.

PROPOSITION 6.4.5 (Liveness 2). Suppose $l'_1, l, l'_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$. Suppose further that

$$\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \mathbf{T} \quad \text{and} \quad \models \text{safe}(l) \quad \text{and} \quad \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live}.$$

In words: l'_1 and l'_2 have nonempty quorum intersections (Notation 4.1.2) and l'_2 has a live quorum. Then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v).$$

As corollaries,

$$\begin{aligned} &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) \quad \text{and} \\ &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We reason as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \\ &\Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_1} \text{vote}(l, v) && \text{(Deliver?)} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l, v_1)) && \text{Prop 5.2.11, } \models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \mathbf{T} \wedge \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_l \text{echo}(v)) && \text{(Vote?)} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} (\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_l \text{echo}(v)) && \text{Corollary 5.2.9(3), } \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} (\text{live} \wedge \text{safe}(l) \wedge \boxplus_l \text{echo}(v)) && \text{Lemma 6.4.1, } \models \text{safe}(l) \\ &\Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l, v)) && \text{Lemma 6.4.2(2), (Vote!)} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{vote}(l, v) && \text{(Knowledge}\boxplus\text{)} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 6.4.3, (Deliver!)} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \square_{l'_2} \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 6.4.4} \\ &\Rightarrow \models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 4.2.1(1)} \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

6.5. Liveness 1

Lemmas 6.5.1 and 6.5.2 will help us prove Proposition 6.5.3.

LEMMA 6.5.1. $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ implies $\boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{echo}(v)$.

Proof. Suppose $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ (i.e. precisely one value is proposed). To prove $\boxplus \models (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{echo}(v)$ it suffices by Figure 3 to show for every $w \in \mathbb{H}$ that $w \models \text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ implies $w \models \uparrow \text{echo}(v)$.

So suppose

$$w \models \text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v).$$

Using (Echo!)

$$w \models \uparrow \text{echo}(v') \quad \text{for some } v' \in \mathbf{Value}.$$

It follows using (Echo?) that $\models \diamond \text{propose}(v')$. However, we also assumed that $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$, so $v = v'$ and we are done. \square

Note the use of ‘there exists’ above. The inner \diamond takes the local view and has the value of

at w , p knows of a propose(v) event.

Note the use of ‘at w , p knows’ above. This is non-omniscient because we evaluate at $w \in \mathbb{H}$. Putting this together, we arrive at the full meaning of $\models \diamond(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v))$:

There exists some event by a live participant such that at the time of that event the live participant knows of a past propose(v) message.

That is a bit of a mouthful, and we can shorten it (with some mild loss of precision) to:

Some live participant learns of a propose(v).

6.6. Further discussion

REMARK 6.6.1. Recall from Notation 6.1.3 and Remark 6.1.4 that we read $p, x, H \models \text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ as ‘ p delivers v for (l', l) ’, and this implies that the delivering participant p has observed an l' -quorum of participants who observed an l -quorum of participants who observed $\text{propose}(v)$.

Let us reflect on the correctness properties from Figure 8:

- The Agreement property (Proposition 6.3.1) is strong: provided l'_1 and l'_2 have sequential quorum intersections (Notation 4.1.2), we have a guarantee that any p and p' that deliver values for (l'_1, l_1) and (l'_2, l_2) respectively, will agree on the value that they deliver.
- The Liveness 2 guarantee (Proposition 6.4.5) is weak in the following sense: An adversary could wait for some p to deliver v for (l'_1, l) , for some l . Then the adversary creates a nonsequential quorum intersection for that l , and advertise it to all other participants. This would prevent Proposition 6.4.5 from making any useful predictions about deliveries for (l'_2, l) for any l'_2 , because the condition $\models \text{safe}(l)$ would no longer hold.
- The Liveness 1 guarantee (Proposition 6.5.3) is as one would expect; no weaker or stronger than what makes sense.

Protocols ThyHBB2 and ThyHBB3 will go some way to correcting the weak Liveness 2 guarantee of ThyHBB1, or rather, they will make different trade-offs. See a comparative discussion of ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 in Remark 7.3.1.

REMARK 6.6.2. A few words on how the predicate symbols live and safe are used in ThyHBB1.

1. Both $\text{live}()$ (we drop the empty brackets and write this just as ‘live’) and $\text{safe}(l)$ are atomic predicates (Definition 3.1.1(2)).

We have not imposed an arity system on our syntax, but we use live as a 0-ary proposition which is true at a live participant. The property of being live is a property of a place/participant, but not a time, in a sense made formal by axiom (LiveAlways).

In contrast, the property of a learner l being safe is a property both of a place and a time, as per axiom (Safe). A learner l is only safe at a participant p and at a time H and it might become not-safe at p at a later H' — unless $H = \mathbb{H}$ in which case the system is omniscient and l is indeed safe until the end of time because, well, we are at the end of time and l is safe.

Regardless, the content of the assertion $\text{safe}(l)$ is that l is safe *here* and *until now*, i.e. it is a local assertion, whereas the content of the assertion live is that here is live, forever, i.e. it is an omniscient assertion about behaviour now and into the future.

2. Note that propose , echo , vote , and deliver are event-symbols, not predicate symbols. Events are very similar to atomic predicates but they are handled differently in the denotation; see the discussion in Remark 3.1.4.

REMARK 6.6.3 (What really matters (for correctness)). The central characteristic of an honest participant is being sequential. The central characteristic of a dishonest (= hostile, byzantine) participant is *not* being sequential. Because we assume that all messages are cryptographically signed, so forging messages is impossible, (non)sequentiality is the only (mis)behaviour that really counts, so that just two things really matter for determining our correctness properties: intersection properties of quorums, and sequentiality properties of participants within those quorums.

Ultimately, everything will boil down to conditions of these two forms.

7. Theory ThyHBB2

ThyHBB1 is not the only way to generalise Bracha’s reliable broadcast. Here we present ThyHBB2, a slightly simpler theory that makes different trade-offs between liveness and agreement.

7.1. Definition of the theory

DEFINITION 7.1.1 (Theory ThyHBB2).

1. Assume a signature with event-symbols propose , echo , vote , and deliver , and with a predicate-symbol live .
2. Define ThyHBB2 to be the theory with axioms as per Figure 9.
3. For the rest of this Section, we fix a model \mathbb{M} of ThyHBB2, meaning that $\mathbb{M} \models \text{ThyHBB2}$ as per Definition 5.2.1.

REMARK 7.1.2. We we did in Remark 6.1.7 for ThyHBB1, we can extract an abstract protocol from the axioms as follows, where we interpret atomic predicates as messages:

1. A proposer broadcasts $\text{propose}(v)$ for some value v .
2. p broadcasts $\text{echo}(v)$ for precisely one proposed value, provided it observes any proposals at all.
3. If p receives an l -quorum of $\text{echo}(v)$ messages, it broadcasts $\text{vote}(l, v)$.
4. If p receives an l' -quorum of $\text{vote}(l, v)$ messages, it broadcasts $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$.

We spell out the intuitive logical content of each broadcast:

- $\text{propose}(v)$ means *I propose v*.
- $\text{echo}(v)$ means *I saw propose v*.
- $\text{vote}(l, v)$ means *I saw an l-quorum of participants who each saw someone propose v*.
- $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ means *I saw an l'-quorum of participants who each saw an l-quorum of participants who each saw someone propose v*.

THEOREM 7.1.3. We collect the correctness properties for ThyHBB2 in Figure 10, for ease of reference.

Proof. The relevant results are Propositions 7.2.3, 7.2.2, and 7.2.1 respectively. \square

7.2. Proofs of Agreement, Liveness 1, and Liveness 2

PROPOSITION 7.2.1 (Agreement). *Suppose $l_1, l_2, l'_1, l'_2 \in \text{Learner}$ and*

$$\models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq.}$$

Then for every $v_1, v_2 \in \text{Value}$,

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \wedge \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \text{ implies } v_1 = v_2.$$

Proof. If $v_1 = v_2$ then we are done, so suppose $v_1 \neq v_2$. We reason as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \wedge \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) & \\ \implies \models \Box_{l'_1} \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \Box_{l'_2} \text{vote}(l_2, v_2) & \quad (\text{Deliver?}) \\ \implies \models \diamond \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \diamond \text{vote}(l_2, v_2) & \quad \text{Lemma 4.2.1(1)} \\ \implies \models \Box_{l_1} \text{echo}(v_1) \wedge \Box_{l_2} \text{echo}(v_2) & \quad (\text{Vote?}) \\ \implies v_1 = v_2 & \quad \text{Prop 5.1.5(3), } v_1 \neq v_2, \\ & \quad \models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq, (EchoNE)} \end{aligned}$$

We note $v_1 \neq v_2$ using Proposition 5.1.5(3) above because the result requires distinct events. \square

PROPOSITION 7.2.2 (Liveness 2). Suppose $l'_1, l'_2, l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and

$$\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \mathbf{T} \quad \text{and} \quad \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live}.$$

Then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v).$$

As corollaries,

$$\begin{aligned} &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) \quad \text{and} \\ &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We reason as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l'_1, v_1) \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_1} \text{vote}(l'_1, v_1) && \text{(Deliver?)} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l'_1, v_1)) && \text{Prop 5.2.11, } \models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \mathbf{T} \wedge \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_{l'_1} \text{echo}(v_1)) && \text{(Vote?)} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} (\text{live} \wedge \boxplus_{l'_1} \text{echo}(v_1)) && \text{Corollary 5.2.9(3), } \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l, v)) && \text{Lemma 6.4.2(2), (Vote!)} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{vote}(l, v) && \text{(Knowledge}\boxplus\text{)} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 6.4.3, (Deliver!)} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \square_{l'_2} \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \models \square_{l'_2} \text{live} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \boxplus_{l'_2} \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 6.4.4} \\ &\quad \Rightarrow \models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v) && \text{Lemma 4.2.1(1)} \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

PROPOSITION 7.2.3 (Liveness 1). Suppose $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and

$$\models \square_l \text{live} \quad \text{and} \quad \models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v).$$

Then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, l, v).$$

As corollaries,

$$\begin{aligned} &\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \boxplus_l \text{deliver}(l, l, v) \quad \text{and} \\ &\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l, l, v). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We reason as follows:

$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v))$	
$\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v))$	Corollary 5.2.9(1), $\models \Box_l \text{live}$
$\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \text{echo}(v))$	Lemma 6.4.2(2) & Lemma 6.5.1, $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$
$\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \Box_l \text{echo}(l, v))$	Lemma 5.2.12
$\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l, v))$	Lemma 6.4.2(2), (Vote!)
$\implies \models \text{live} \implies \uparrow \Box_l \text{vote}(l, v)$	(Knowledge \Box)
$\implies \models \text{live} \implies \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, l, v)$	Lemma 6.4.3, (Deliver!)
$\implies \models \Box_l \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, l, v)$	$\models \Box_l \text{live}$
$\implies \models \Box_l \text{deliver}(l, l, v)$	Lemma 6.4.4
$\implies \models \diamond \text{deliver}(l, l, v)$	Lemma 4.2.1(1) □

REMARK 7.2.4. We use Lemma 6.5.1 in the proof of Proposition 7.2.3 (liveness 1 for ThyHBB2) just as we used it in Proposition 6.5.3 (liveness 1 for ThyHBB1).

However, Lemma 6.5.1 was proved for theory ThyHBB1, whereas now we are working in theory ThyHBB2. This is an abuse of notation. However the proof of that Lemma depends only on axioms and properties that the two theories have in common, and examining the proof it is entirely clear that it works equally well here, so we take a liberty with the notation and reuse it.

7.3. Discussion

REMARK 7.3.1. ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 have similarities, but also significant differences:

- ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 are similar in that they have the same atomic predicates: propose, echo, vote, and deliver. In both theories, the delivery assertion $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$ can be read as

‘an l' -quorum of participants believe that an l -quorum of participants echoed v ’,

and we say (as per Remark 6.1.4) that we deliver v for (l', l) .

This makes explicit which learner’s trust assumptions (quorums) are used in the echo and vote stages, reflecting the fact that our protocol is heterogeneous and may involve multiple trust assumptions.

- ThyHBB2 is simpler in the sense that it does not use (or need) the predicate safe. As a result, the axiomatisation in ThyHBB2 is slightly smaller.
- The Agreement property for ThyHBB2 (Proposition 7.2.1) differs significantly from that for ThyHBB1 (Proposition 6.3.1). We compare the two Agreement

properties in sketch form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ThyHBB1} \quad & \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq} \implies \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \\
 & \implies \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \implies v_1 = v_2 \\
 \text{ThyHBB2} \quad & \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq} \implies \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \\
 & \implies \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \implies v_1 = v_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The difference above is highlighted:

- the precondition $\diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq}$ in ThyHBB1 assumes sequential quorum intersections between l'_1 and l'_2 , which is the learners who we want to agree; whereas
- the precondition $\diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq}$ in ThyHBB2 assumes sequential quorum intersections between the learners for whom we have the *original* quorums of echoes.

Arguably $\diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq}$ is a stronger condition than $\diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \text{seq}$, making the Agreement property of ThyHBB2 weaker than that of ThyHBB1.

In ThyHBB2, if an attacker creates a nonsequential quorum intersection between l_1 and l_2 then *no* l'_1 and l'_2 are guaranteed to agree in delivering values based on l_1 and l_2 . In ThyHBB1, an attacker wishing to destroy agreement would have to attack the quorum intersections between l'_1 and l'_2 directly, for each l'_1 and l'_2 .

- The Liveness 2 guarantee in Proposition 7.2.2 for ThyHBB2 is stronger than that for ThyHBB1 in Proposition 6.4.5. We just need the two learners to have nonempty quorum intersections. There is no safety restriction, as we needed for Proposition 6.4.5 for ThyHBB1. So ThyHBB2 is intuitively ‘more live 2’ than ThyHBB1.

So intuitively ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 are cut from similar cloth but but they make different trade-offs:

1. In ThyHBB1 it is relatively *hard* for an attacker to break agreement properties, but relatively *easy* for it to break the liveness 2 property, whereas
2. in ThyHBB2 it is relatively *easier* for an attacker to break agreement properties, but relatively *harder* for it to break the liveness 2 property.
3. The statement of the liveness 1 properties are identical, but arguably ThyHBB2 is also ‘more live 1’ than ThyHBB1, just because the (Vote!) drops the safety precondition. We compare the two (Vote!) rules for the reader’s convenience:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ThyHBB1} \quad & \uparrow \text{safe}(l) \Rightarrow (\text{live} \wedge \diamond_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{vote}(l, v) \\
 \text{ThyHBB2} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \diamond_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{vote}(l, v)
 \end{aligned}$$

It seems likely to be easier to make progress with the second rule, because we do not require l to be safe (ThyHBB2 does not even use this concept).

So to sum this up, ThyHBB1 is less live but tends to agree where the protocol succeeds; whereas ThyHBB2 is more live but may agree less. As always, which trade-offs we prefer will depend on the use-case, our trust assumptions, and our attacker model.

8. Theory ThyHBB3

A quick recap is in order. Recall from Notation 6.1.3 and Remark 6.1.4 that in ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2, the deliver event has the form $\text{deliver}(l', l, v)$, where we call l the *source* learner and l' the *reporting* learner. The trust assumptions (= quorums) of the source learner are used to determine when we have observed a quorum of echo messages, and the trust assumptions of the reporting learner are used to determine when we have observed a quorum of vote messages.

This reflects and makes explicit the two-round structure from Bracha's original protocol, and this is reasonable because in a heterogeneous setting we have design freedom in whose trust assumptions to use in each of the two rounds.

For ThyHBB3 we do things slightly differently.

The deliver event is simplified to be relative to a single learner: $\text{deliver}(l, v)$. Structurally, this gives us liveness and agreement properties that more closely resemble those of Bracha's original (homogeneous) broadcast algorithm. However, our setting is still heterogeneous and we are still dealing with a choice of trust assumptions; the complexity of managing that choice does not just go away.

ThyHBB3 deals with this by introducing a *correlation relation* \doteq , which expresses when learners might need to agree, and then — intuitively — we existentially quantify over an l -quorum of votes by \doteq -correlated chains of learners, where each chain of votes leads to a quorum of echo messages from some (existentially quantified) source learner.

We use logic to make the intuition precise. The key axioms to look at are (Vote?) and (Deliver?) in Figure 11. In particular, (Vote?) has a disjunct, between

- an l -quorum of echoes ($\sqcap_l \text{echo}(v)$), and
- another vote, by an existentially-quantified \doteq -connected learner (in symbols: $\exists l' \doteq l. \diamond \text{vote}(l', v)$).

The right-hand disjunct lets us build an existentially quantified chain of \doteq -correlated learners,⁵³ and the left-hand disjunct lets us terminate it with a

⁵³Subtlety alert: the correlations are measured at the times of the votes, not necessarily at the time of the final delivery.

quorum of echoes. Then (Deliver?) just expresses that if we deliver then we observed an l -quorum of votes, and we are done.

Of course there are many details to get just right, but we have the framework of our logic to help us and we can now proceed:

8.1. \doteq : the correlation relation

We give some intuition for how ThyHBB3 works. The discussion is informal and our logic will make it precise starting with Subsection 8.2.

REMARK 8.1.1. We introduce the notion of a binary relation $l \doteq l'$ between learners, which we read as **l correlates with l'** . We may write $\neg(l \doteq l')$ as $l \neq l'$ and say that **l does not correlate with l'** .

The correlation relation \doteq has two properties:

1. \doteq is a *partial equivalence relation* (transitive, symmetric, but not necessarily reflexive).
2. If p believes that l correlates with l' , then p should know that they should have sequential quorum intersections. In symbols:

$$(\doteq \text{seq}) \quad l \doteq l' \Rightarrow \Diamond_{ll'} \text{seq.}$$

The contrapositive is clearer: if p knows of an intersection between an l -quorum and an l' -quorum that *is not* sequential (i.e. every element is nonsequential), then p believes $l \neq l'$ and thus that l and l' do not correlate.⁵⁴

Note that the $(\doteq \text{seq})$ implication does *not* run in the other direction: just because p knows that l and l' have sequential quorum intersections does *not* mean that p believes $l \doteq l'$.

To see the motivation for this, consider two points:

1. If l and l' do not have sequential quorum intersections then there is some pair of quorums whose intersection is entirely composed of nonsequential participants, i.e. faulty ones. That faulty intersection could be reporting one version of history to an l -quorum of participants, and another version of history to an l' -quorum of participants. Thus (intuitively) p cannot necessarily expect behaviours regarding l and l' to correlate.

This motivates $(\doteq \text{seq})$.

2. Now imagine we have three learners l_1 , l_2 , and l_3 , and suppose p believes $l_1 \doteq l_2$ and $l_2 \doteq l_3$. By transitivity p also believes $l_1 \doteq l_3$.

Now suppose p learns of a nonsequential quorum intersection between l_1 and l_3 , so that p believes $l_1 \neq l_3$. By transitivity, p has to give up on at least one of

⁵⁴One particular special case is when there exist *disjoint* l - and l' -quorums. Then l and l' can never correlate. This recovers the spirit of the kind of quorum intersection property that is very commonly seen in the theory of distributed algorithms.

$l_1 \doteq l_2$ or $l_2 \doteq l_3$. There is no canonical way in general to do this.⁵⁵ So p just has to choose; thus even if (for example) l_1 and l_2 may have sequential quorum intersections, p may still need to give up on believing them to be correlated, because of nonsequential behaviour elsewhere.

This is all just a mathematical way of saying that opinions can diverge, and if they do, p may have to pick a side.

The benefit of introducing \doteq is that we can devise a simple protocol that, in some sense, uses \doteq to marry the strong Agreement properties of ThyHBB1 with the strong Liveness properties of ThyHBB2. That said, our third protocol has its own distinct identity.

REMARK 8.1.2. Our protocol will also include a strong assumption on quorums, namely (3twined) in Figure 11

$$(3\text{twined}) \quad \diamond_{ll' l''} \mathbf{T}$$

asserts as per Lemma 4.1.1(2) that any three quorums have nonempty intersection .

The terminology ‘3-twined’ follows to the semitopological terminology from [GZ25], where an n -twined semitopology is one such that any n nonempty open sets (= quorums) intersect (though here, of course, the situation is slightly different because the three quorums may come from three different learners’ trust assumptions).

The 3-twined assumption does not appear in ThyHBB1 or ThyHBB2. However, assumptions of this form are extremely common — arguably they are almost universal — in the literature on (homogeneous) distributed algorithms with byzantine behaviour. Quorum intersection properties may appear explicitly with names like ‘the Q^3 condition’ or ‘the B^3 condition’, or they may be arithmetically implicit: e.g. authors assume some $f \geq 0$ and that \mathbf{P} has size $3f + 1$ and that quorums have size at least $2f + 1$, which by simple arithmetic guarantees that any three quorums intersect. A discussion with references is at the start of Subsection 4.1.

Here, we have (3twined), which makes a beautiful and compact use of our logic to express precisely what is required.

8.2. Definition of the theory

DEFINITION 8.2.1 (Theory ThyHBB3).

1. Assume a signature with event-symbols propose, echo, vote, and deliver, and with predicate symbols live and \doteq (which we will write as a binary infix; thus $t \doteq t'$ is actually sugar for $\doteq(t, t')$).

⁵⁵This assertion can be made precise. A sets union of two partial equivalence relations is not necessarily a partial equivalence relation. It follows that if R is a partial equivalence relation, then the poset of partial equivalence relations greater than R in the subset ordering does not necessarily have a greatest element. It will have at least one maximal elements, but there is in general no single canonical greatest one.

2. Define ThyHBB3 to be the theory with axioms as per Figure 11.
3. For the rest of this Section, we fix a model \mathbb{M} of ThyHBB3, meaning that $\mathbb{M} \models \text{ThyHBB3}$ as per Definition 5.2.1.

REMARK 8.2.2. As in Remarks 6.1.7 and 7.1.2, we extract an abstract protocol from the axioms as follows, where we interpret atomic predicates as messages:

1. A proposer broadcasts $\text{propose}(v)$ for some value v .
2. p broadcasts $\text{echo}(v)$ for precisely one proposed value, provided it observes any proposals at all.
3. If p receives an l -quorum of $\text{echo}(v)$ messages, then it broadcasts $\text{vote}(l, v)$.
4. If p receives a $\text{vote}(l', v)$ message for some l' that correlates with l at the time, then p broadcasts $\text{vote}(l, v)$.
5. If p receives an l -quorum of $\text{vote}(l, v)$ messages then it broadcasts $\text{deliver}(l, v)$.

We spell out the intuitive logical content of each broadcast, bearing in mind that signatures cannot be forged:

- $\text{propose}(v)$ means *I propose v*.
- $\text{echo}(v)$ means *I saw propose v*.
- $\text{vote}(l, v)$ means *I saw an l-quorum of participants who saw propose v, or vote(l', v) for an l' that correlated with l at the time*.
- $\text{deliver}(l, v)$ means *I saw an l-quorum of participants, each of whom saw a correlated chain of votes leading to some l'-quorum of participants who saw propose v*.

THEOREM 8.2.3. *We collect the correctness properties for ThyHBB3 in Figure 12, for convenient reference.*

Proof. The relevant results are Propositions 8.5.1, 8.4.5, and 8.3.1 respectively. \square

8.3. Agreement

PROPOSITION 8.3.1 (Soundness / Agreement). *Suppose $l_1, l_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$. Suppose further that*

$$\models \square (l_1 \doteq l_2).$$

Then for every $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$,

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l_1, v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l_2, v_2) \Rightarrow v_1 = v_2.$$

Proof. Note from $\models \square (l_1 \doteq l_2)$ that:

- Using $(\doteq \text{seq})$ we have $\models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq}$.
- Using $(\doteq \Downarrow)$ we have $\models \boxplus (l_1 \doteq l_2)$, i.e. by Remark 3.6.6(4) $w \models l_1 \doteq l_2$ for every $w \in \mathbb{H}$.

If $v_1 = v_2$ then we are done, so suppose $v_1 \neq v_2$. We reason as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \models \Diamond \text{deliver}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \Diamond \text{deliver}(l_2, v_2) \\
& \implies \models \Box_{l_1} \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \Box_{l_2} \text{vote}(l_2, v_2) && \text{(Deliver?)} \\
& \implies \models \Diamond (\text{vote}(l'_1, v_1) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l'_2, v_2)) \vee && \text{Prop 5.1.5(3),} \\
& \quad \models \Diamond (\text{vote}(l'_2, v_2) \wedge \downarrow \text{vote}(l'_1, v_1)) && v_1 \neq v_2, \models \Diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq} \\
& \implies v_1 = v_2 && \text{(VoteNE), } \models \Box(l_1 \doteq l_2)
\end{aligned}$$

We note $v_1 \neq v_2$ using Proposition 5.1.5(3) above because the result requires distinct events. \square

REMARK 8.3.2 (Design alternative). There is a wrinkle in axiom $(\doteq\Downarrow)$ in Figure 11, that the modality \Downarrow only quantifies over worlds $w \in \mathbb{H}$, not over all possible worlds $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{H})$. An alternative axiom $\Uparrow(l_1 \doteq l_2) \Rightarrow l_1 \doteq l_2$ eliminates that possibility. This is weaker in the sense that the left-hand side of the implication goes to the end of time (the left-hand side of the implication in $(\doteq\Downarrow)$ as written does not do that), but it is stronger in the sense that the right-hand side works at all possible worlds. Perhaps surprisingly, either axiom will work in our proofs.⁵⁶

8.4. Liveness 2

Lemma 8.4.1 will help us prove Lemma 8.4.3(1):

LEMMA 8.4.1. *Suppose $l_1, l_2, l_3 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and suppose ϕ_1, ϕ_2 , and ϕ_3 are three closed predicates. Then*

$$\models \Diamond_{l_1 l_2 l_3} \mathbf{T} \Rightarrow (\Box_{l_1} \phi_1 \wedge \Box_{l_2} \phi_2 \wedge \Box_{l_3} \phi_3) \Rightarrow \Diamond (\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_3).$$

Proof. Suppose $\models \Diamond_{l_1 l_2 l_3} \mathbf{T}$. By Lemma 4.1.1(2),

1. an l_1 -quorum of $p \in \mathbf{P}$ that satisfies $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi_1$, and
2. an l_2 -quorum of $p \in \mathbf{P}$ that satisfies $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi_2$, and
3. an l_3 -quorum of $p \in \mathbf{P}$ that satisfies $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi_3$,

must intersect at some p , which will satisfy $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \wedge \phi_3$. The result follows. \square

Lemma 8.4.2 will help us prove Lemma 8.4.3(2):

LEMMA 8.4.2. *Suppose $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $w \in \mathbb{H}$. Then:*

⁵⁶The dedicated reader might look all this design space and conclude that \downarrow and \Downarrow should just quantify over possible preceding possible worlds, rather than just preceding worlds that are event-tuples in \mathbb{H} . Unfortunately, that does not work! We need \downarrow as written in order to express the Knowledge axioms in Figure 6. The design tension here is real. We could have two ‘in-the-past’ modalities (one for event-tuples in history and one for all possible worlds), or we can do as we have done and live with the wrinkle in $(\doteq\Downarrow)$. Since this wrinkle is harmless in our current proofs, this seems a valid tradeoff.

1. $w \models \text{vote}(l, v)$ implies $\models \sqcup_{l'} \text{echo}(v)$ for some $l' \in \mathbf{Learner}$.
2. $\models \diamond \text{vote}(l, v)$ implies $\models \sqcup_{l'} \text{echo}(v)$ for some $l' \in \mathbf{Learner}$.

Proof. Part 1 is by a simple inductive argument on $\text{time}(w)$, using (Vote?) from Figure 11. Part 2 follows since by Remark 3.6.6(3) $\models \diamond \text{vote}(l, v)$ just means $w \models \text{vote}(l, v)$ for some $w \in \mathbb{H}$. \square

LEMMA 8.4.3. *Suppose $l, l_1, l_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ — we do not assume $l \doteq l_1$ or $l_1 \doteq l_2$; these are just any three learners — and*

$$\models \sqcup_l \text{seq.}$$

Then for any $v, v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$:

1. $\models \sqcup_{l_1} \text{echo}(v_1) \wedge \sqcup_{l_2} \text{echo}(v_2)$ implies $v_1 = v_2$.
2. $\models \diamond \text{vote}(l_1, v_1) \wedge \diamond \text{vote}(l_2, v_2)$ implies $v_1 = v_2$.⁵⁷
3. $\sqsupset \models (\text{live} \wedge \uparrow l_1 \doteq l_2 \wedge \diamond \text{vote}(l_1, v)) \implies \uparrow \text{vote}(l_2, v)$.
4. $\sqsupset \models (\text{live} \wedge \sqcup_l \text{echo}(v)) \implies \uparrow \text{vote}(l, v)$.

Proof. We consider each part in turn:

1. Using Lemma 8.4.1 (since we assume (3twined) in Figure 11) we have

$$\models \diamond (\text{seq} \wedge \downarrow \text{echo}(v_1) \wedge \downarrow \text{echo}(v_2)).$$

The result now follows using Proposition 5.1.5(2) and (EchoNE).

2. From part 1 of this result, using Lemma 8.4.2.
3. From (Vote!), noting that by part 2 of this result, *only* v can ever be voted for.
4. From (Vote!), noting that by part 2 of this result, *only* v can ever be voted for. \square

LEMMA 8.4.4. *Suppose $l_1, l_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$. Then:*

1. $\models \diamond (l_1 \doteq l_2)$ implies $\models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \mathbf{T}$.
2. $\models \square (l_1 \doteq l_2)$ implies $\models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \mathbf{T}$.

Proof. Part 2 follows from part 1 using Lemma 4.2.1(2) (that \square implies \diamond).

For part 1, suppose $\models \diamond (l_1 \doteq l_2)$. Unpacking what this means using Remark 3.6.6(1), there exists $p \in \mathbf{P}$ such $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models l_1 \doteq l_2$. Using $(\doteq \text{seq})$ $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq}$ and (since $\text{seq} \implies \mathbf{T}$) also $p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H} \models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \mathbf{T}$. \square

⁵⁷This result might seem to imply (VoteNE), because if $\text{vote}(l, v)$ and $\downarrow \text{vote}(l', v')$ then certainly $\diamond \text{vote}(l, v)$ and $\diamond \text{vote}(l', v')$, and then by this result $v_1 = v_2$. However, this result assumes the existence of a quorum of sequential participants, whereas (VoteNE) does not.

Proof. Note that because $\models \Box_l \text{live}$, by (LiveSeq) from Figure 6 also $\models \Box_l \text{seq}$. We reason as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\models \Diamond (\text{live} \wedge \Diamond \text{propose}(v)) & \\
\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \Diamond \text{propose}(v)) & \text{Corollary 5.2.9(1), } \models \Box_l \text{live} \\
\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \text{echo}(v)) & \text{Lemma 6.4.2(2) \& } \\
& \text{Lemma 6.5.1, } \models \exists_1 v. \Diamond \text{propose}(v) \\
\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \Box_l \text{echo}(v)) & \text{Lemma 5.2.12} \\
\implies \models \Box_l (\text{live} \wedge \text{vote}(l, v)) & \text{Lemmas 6.4.2(2) \& 8.4.3(4), } \models \Box_l \text{seq} \\
\implies \models \text{live} \implies \uparrow \Box_l \text{vote}(l, v) & \text{(Knowledge}\Box\text{)} \\
\implies \models \text{live} \implies \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, v) & \text{Lemma 6.4.3, (Deliver!)} \\
\implies \models \Box_l \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, v) & \models \Box_l \text{live} \\
\implies \models \Box_l \text{deliver}(l, v) & \text{Lemma 6.4.4} \\
\implies \models \Diamond \text{deliver}(l, v) & \text{Lemma 4.2.1(1)} \quad \square
\end{array}$$

REMARK 8.5.2. We abuse Lemma 6.5.1 in the proof of Proposition 8.5.1 above, because it concerns echo in ThyHBB1, and here we are working with echo in ThyHBB3. However, the (Echo?) and (EchoNE) rules of ThyHBB1 are identical to the (Echo?) and (EchoNE) rules of ThyHBB3, and it is clear that the result transfers.

8.6. Discussion

REMARK 8.6.1. ThyHBB3 assumes a *correlation relation* \doteq . We make minimal assumptions on \doteq such that our proofs work. These are:

- Symmetry (\doteq symm) and transitivity (\doteq tran); at every $w \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$, the relation $\{(l, l') \mid w \models l \doteq l'\}$ is a partial equivalence relation.
- Monotonicity (\doteq ↓); if l and l' stop correlating then they cannot (re)correlate later.
- Sequentiality (\doteq seq): correlated learners must have sequential quorum intersections (and conversely, if they do not, they they do not correlate).

Other properties for \doteq are possible. We do not need any to prove our correctness properties, but it is interesting to mention a few here:

1. $\forall l, l'. \downarrow (l \doteq l')$ *All learners correlate at first.*
The intuition is that learners with no behaviour should correlate, and only when they start to display behaviour might we decide that these behaviours do not correlate.
2. $\Box (l \doteq l') \Leftrightarrow \Diamond (l \doteq l')$ *Correlation is a property of time, but not of place.*
The intuition is that, given the same information, participants should globally agree on what the correlation relation should be.

3. $\forall l, l'. \diamond l \doteq l'$ *All learners correlate somewhere, sometime.*

This is perhaps the most interesting property. Algorithmically, this reflects an intuition (which we do not prove here) that if l never correlates with l' anywhere, at any time, then their \doteq -equivalence partitions are in some sense running two concurrent algorithms. Even if they use the same messages, these two partitions cannot block one another so they can be thought of logically as two distinct runs of the algorithm, which happen to be run on the same network, but which are logically distinct nonetheless.

REMARK 8.6.2 (Discussion of (3twined)). The proof of Proposition 8.4.5 uses (3twined) once, and this is the only place that our correctness properties for ThyHBB3 use that axiom.⁵⁹

Specifically, we use (3twined) in Proposition 8.4.5 via the use of Lemma 8.4.3(1), whose proof requires a nonempty intersection between an l -quorum of sequential participants, and l_1 - and l_2 -quorums of echo messages.

This is the only place in which we use (3twined), so we should examine the proof to see precisely how this property is used — and whether something weaker might suffice. The actual property we require is this:

$$\forall l_1, l_2, l_3. (\sqcup_{l_2} \text{seq} \implies l_1 \doteq l_2 \implies \downarrow(l_2 \doteq l_3) \implies \diamond_{l_1 l_3} \text{seq}).$$

((3twined) in Figure 11 also quantifies over its learners, but as standard in writing axioms, we elide top-level universal quantifiers.) If we follow Remark 8.6.1(1) and assume that all learners correlate at first, then this simplifies to:

$$\forall l_1, l_2, l_3. (l_1 \doteq l_2 \implies \sqcup_{l_2} \text{seq} \implies \diamond_{l_1 l_3} \text{seq}). \quad (4)$$

This looks a bit like a cross between (3twined) and the notion of a ‘safe’ learner from ThyHBB1.

We could assume property (4) in ThyHBB3 instead of (3twined) and the proofs would work just as well. We prefer (3twined) because:

- It is a purely structural restriction on quorums whose validity does not depend on behaviour during a run of the protocol.
- It is very simple.
- It corresponds nicely to the standard ‘ $2f+1$ ’-style assumption on quorum sizes that appears frequently in the literature (e.g. [HM00, page 4, $Q^{(3)}$ property] or [ACTZ24, Definition 2]).

Nevertheless, we note that a design space exists here, which could be explored in future work.

⁵⁹We could also use (3twined) to deduce $\diamond_{l_1 l_2} \top$, but we have that from $l_1 \doteq l_2$.

REMARK 8.6.3 (Alternative vote axioms). Arguably the following backward and forward rules for vote are more elegant than what is in Figure 11 (the other rules, including (VoteNE), are unchanged):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(AltVote?)} \quad & \text{vote}(l, v) \Rightarrow \exists l' \triangleq l. \Box_{l'} \text{echo}(v) \\ \text{(AltVote!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \uparrow(l' \triangleq l) \wedge \Box_{l'} \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \downarrow \text{vote}(l, v') \end{aligned}$$

This gives $\text{vote}(l, v)$ and intuition of *I saw an l' -quorum of participants who saw someone propose v for an l' that correlates with l* — note that it may be that $l' = l$.

This treatment of vote is simpler and cleaner than the one in Figure 11, but it is also weaker. We see this clearly when we contrast the alternate forward rule (AltVote!), which only guarantees progress for l that correlate with themselves, with (Vote!) in Figure 11, which has no such restriction.

In practice we are most interested in learners that do indeed correlate with themselves, so this restriction is not critical. Nevertheless, we prefer to state the stronger (more live) theory.

REMARK 8.6.4 (Wrong treatment of seq). In view of Proposition 5.1.4 (seq monotone) it might be tempting to unify axioms $(\triangleq \text{seq})$ and $(\triangleq \Downarrow)$ in Figure 11 into a single axiom as follows:

$$(\triangleq \text{wrong}) \quad l \triangleq l' \Leftrightarrow \Diamond_{l'} \text{seq.}$$

But this would be wrong. As outlined in Remark 8.1.1(2), a participant might need to pick a side in some dispute between two other learners, and as a result decide to break $l \triangleq l'$ — even though $\Diamond_{l'} \text{seq}$ still holds.

REMARK 8.6.5 (Concluding remarks on ThyHBB3). ThyHBB3 succeeds on its own terms: it describes a short and simple protocol that naturally generalises homogeneous Bracha Broadcast, with correctness properties that resemble those for Bracha Broadcast.

If there is a defect it is that the 3-twined quorum intersection property that any three quorums intersect (needed for the Liveness 2 property; see Remark 8.6.2) might be too strong an assumption for some use-cases. That said, and to be fair, assuming nonempty triple quorum intersections (e.g. as in “assume $3f + 1$ participants of which at most f are faulty”) is a standard assumption in the literature, including for broadcast and consensus protocols.

9. Conclusions

9.1. Looking back on the results

Let us summarise our ideas at a high level:

1. Prehistories equate time with an epsilon-structure of past events: a point in time is a set of place-event-time tuples, the time of each is itself a set of tuples, and so on.

History structures are just hereditarily transitive prehistories. Intuitively, transitivity means that knowledge of time is transitive: if we know of an event from a participant that knew of some other event, then we know of that other event. This corresponds to modelling full information protocols.

2. We use (pre)histories to design a modal logic, tailored to specifying and reasoning distributed protocols. We include built-in modalities for specifying things like occurrence of events in the past, quorums of present and past events, quorum intersections, and sequentiality / non-equivocation. Using this, we can write clean and compact formal axiomatisations of relevant properties (see next point).
3. We use our modal logic to specify distributed protocols symbolically as axiomatic theories. A model of the axioms corresponds to a concrete run of the protocol; the class of all models corresponds to the set of all possible runs of the protocol.

Essentially, phrasing things in this way turns distributed protocol design and verification into axiomatic logic and model theory. Verification of a correctness property ϕ is just a proof that ϕ is valid in every model of the axioms: if a structure validates the axioms, then it satisfies ϕ .

4. We use this machinery to design three protocols for Heterogeneous Bracha Broadcast (HBB) — ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3 — each of which is a generalisation of broadcast to the case with multiple learners, and the three of which taken together give an idea of the design space involved. We formally state and prove their correctness properties.⁶⁰

We can shorten this to three slogans and a claim:

1. Slogan 1: Times are sets.
2. Slogan 2: Protocols are theories.
3. Slogan 3: Protocol verification is proof and model-checking.
4. Claim: Heterogeneous broadcast can be studied as the above.

We do not mean these slogans reductively, rather: set theory, modal logic, and model-theory are well-developed fields and we can usefully import their ideas to represent and prove things about distributed protocols.

The development in this paper has been formalised in Lean 4. The relevant files are easily available [Har25], along with (clear and straightforward) usage

⁶⁰Other protocols are possible, but HBB is an excellent start: a simple but nontrivial and useful protocol which occupies a (for us) helpful spot in the design space.

instructions.⁶¹

The logic-and-models approach offers *precision*: English is good for exposition and for giving context, but logic has a way of distilling complex ideas into short predicates with precise meanings. Informal arguments reduce to precise and concise formal reasoning. In the ideal case, verification of correctness properties reduces to symbol-pushing. Furthermore, we would argue that the understanding of the protocol is deeper for a logic formalisation, for the same reason that logic helps deepen understanding in other fields: this encourages (and forces) us to state assumptions, to identify key lemmas, and to phrase assumptions in abstract yet precise form.

The reader can find this exhibited in, for example, the specification of ThyHBB3 in Figure 11, its correctness properties in Figure 12, and in their proofs.

REMARK 9.1.1. Our modal logic is *specific*, in the sense that the maths is shaped by and optimised for the requirements of specific algorithms. Conversely, our three algorithms only exist because we designed them using this logic. We might not have found them otherwise.

The logic and its semantics, and the protocols, came into existence by a constructive symbiosis. There is a real and useful sense in which the logic, semantics, and protocols have constrained, motivated, guided, and validated the design of the other.

9.2. Why heterogeneous protocols?

9.2.1. It's about the ecosystem

Why should we consider heterogeneous distributed protocols? The short answer is: because they are ubiquitous. The longer answer is as follows:

Any distributed protocol must include some form of trust model. In this paper, we represent the trust model as a semiframe (a.k.a. a quorum system) as per Definition 3.3.2. But let us step back from the mathematics and its definitions and note that:

- if you use Ethereum, you trust Ethereum (to some extent);
- if you use a bank, you trust that bank (to some extent);
- if you live in a country, you trust that country's society and governance (to some extent);
- if you eat a pre-made sandwich, you trust the industrial complex that manufactured it to (probably) not give you food poisoning;
- if you go to a nightclub, you trust the staff to keep you safe;

and so on. So the world is naturally an *ecosystem of distributed systems*, each

⁶¹We emphasise the 'clear and straightforward'. Anybody who can get this far in the paper can certainly follow the formalised development.

one based on and requiring some kind of trust assumption. That is: the world is distributed *and* heterogeneous.

There is a tendency within a system to use that system, and to pretend that the rest of the world is somehow out-of-scope. Indeed, some trust models have been very successful: Ethereum, the US dollar, large sandwich brands. This may generate an illusion of homogeneity, but this is an illusion — and this illusion can become expensive, and even self-defeating. At best, a very popular, trusted system can lead to high prices as the system is oversubscribed. At worst, a homogeneous, dominant trust model can lead to monopolistic and rent-seeking behaviour [Doc25].⁶²

There will always be a bottleneck. There will always be someone who wants a different service. There will always be someone who will not (or cannot, e.g. for regulatory reasons) submit to your trust model.⁶³

As helpful as it is to optimise individual distributed systems to be faster and more reliable, this will just result in improved individual distributed systems, and to the extent that these might gain users, these improvements will only make more pressing the bottlenecking question of how to make multiple distributed systems interact well, as a healthy *ecosystem*. There can never be One Final Trusted Party.

Therefore, and inevitably, we must ask ourselves: how can we approach heterogeneous distributed systems? How can distributed systems collaborate gracefully, reliably, and at low cost? What is the mathematics of an ecosystem with heterogeneous trust?

History structures, our modal logic, and our three heterogeneous trust broadcast protocols are this paper's preliminary, theoretical, provisional answer.

⁶² *Enshittification or platform decay* [Doc25]: the tendency of a useful platform ('trust model', in our terms) to create value, succeed, dominate — then extract rent from each of the parties who trusted it until the original value proposition is completely undermined. *Enshittification* seems more accurate than 'platform decay', because 'decay' suggests a natural process that happens through neglect, whereas 'enshittification' more accurately suggests the outcome of active choices made by participants in an economic framework. A classic text 1960s text on business management [Dru67, page 14] comes at a related point, when it writes of a tendency of executives in an organisation to make poor decisions because they *simply forget that the outside world exists*: "The executive is *within* an organisation [but] there are no results within an organisation. All the results ... are produced by a customer who converts the ... efforts of the business into ... profits through his willingness to exchange his purchasing power for ... products and services". The underlying common theme here is that it never just about the system, it's always about how that system interacts with the rest of the world. Where we forget that, things go wrong.

⁶³ It may help to put numbers to this. The market capitalisation of Ethereum at time of writing is (according to an internet search) roughly 0.5 trillion USD. This is a lot of money. However, it is less than the total assets of the House of Saud at 1.4 trillion USD, or of J.P. Morgan's assets under management at 3.4 trillion USD. The numbers are subject to change but what will not change is that J.P. Morgan, House of Saud, and Ethereum will *never* merge. They will *never* fully trust each other. The real world is *inherently* heterogeneous.

9.2.2. Why this has not been done before

We see two reasons that protocols like ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3 have not been studied before:

1. Distributed systems in the modern sense are relatively new. The founding papers are from the 1980s, but it has only been with the rise of the internet and then blockchains that distributed systems have assumed the modern reach and relevance that we now associate to them. In a nutshell, these issues have only become pressing in the last ten years or so. The mathematics is very much still catching up.
2. Distributed systems are hard, and *heterogeneous* distributed systems are even harder, because of how the trust model may vary by participant and by time.

A goal of this paper is to establish heterogeneous distributed systems as a field of study and to show how they can be accurately and conveniently approached via modal logic over (pre)histories. These ideas are new — though we would argue that they are also necessary and inevitable.

In short, as we see it, heterogeneous broadcast is at the cutting edge both of practical necessity and of what modern mathematics can deliver. This paper is intended to improve the state of the art in both dimensions: it makes new things possible, and it opens up new mathematical ways of making further progress.⁶⁴

So: if heterogeneity is unavoidable, then how do existing systems deal with it? With difficulty, and sometimes at considerable expense.

Mostly, existing systems deal with heterogeneous trust work by reducing the system to its worst common denominator. Because this denominator may very low (i.e. participants do not trust one another) this often means in effect inventing more trusted parties, at great expense. To caricature the situation: if two parties that do not trust one another want to transact, it is necessary for them to find or create, and pay for, a third neutral trusted party to mediate between them. While possible, this is expensive and it does not scale — not least because it just pushes the problem down a level. What happens if the transaction above is successful and now a fourth party wants to interact? Should they invent a fifth neutral trusted party (more expense), or should they accept a single shared trusted arbiter of all truth (brings its own challenges)? Where does this end, if not in centralising all trust?

9.2.3. Embracing heterogeneity

The mathematics in this paper — preliminary, theoretical, and provisional as it may be — is of a different colour, in that it embraces heterogeneity in existing

⁶⁴There is an irony to our solution, in that the techniques we import are from modal logic and model theory, which are old fields (older than distributed systems). But then again perhaps we should not be surprised: modal logic and model theory were designed to handle complexity, so perhaps (heterogeneous) distributed algorithms are just another thing they are good at.

trust assumptions as a central technical challenge and tries to exploit it and make it mathematical and efficient. This is an interesting, relevant, and useful research direction which we hope will grow and be fruitful.

9.3. Related work

9.3.1. Heterogeneous Paxos (2021)

The second author has been working on heterogeneous protocols since inventing *Heterogeneous Paxos* (HP) [SWRM21].

An early success of the logic used in this work was to help us find an error in the HP correctness proofs. The HP liveness property in [SWRM21] uses an unstated assumption (which to the authors had not realised) buried in its proofs: it assumes crashes occur at the beginning of time (this is generally not a realistic assumption for distributed protocols!). We were able to discover this thanks to creating a compact presentation using the logic in this paper.

Empirically, our logic decreased the textual volume of the second author's proofs tenfold: ten pages of verbal argument reduced to one page of logical symbol-pushing. In this precise modal logic, the gap in the proof for the original HP system became evident.

9.3.2. XRP Ledger and Stellar (2014/15)

The XRP Ledger [SYB14] and Stellar [Maz15] payment protocols are two commercially successful systems offering global payment services.⁶⁵ They are blockchains, but this is almost incidental: what sets them apart is that they acknowledge the problem of heterogeneity directly in their design (incompatible bank transfer systems are a *big* practical problem), and they use heterogeneous consensus algorithms as a basis for practical infrastructure offering reliable, fast, low-cost bank transfers.⁶⁶

This work has in common with XRP Ledger and Stellar that we embrace heterogeneity. However, the scenario in this work is substantively different in its emphasis. XRP Ledger and Stellar are about participant-learners coming to a global agreement on a single network. This gives XRP Ledger and Stellar a flavour of each creating a trusted third party, whom we may trust (and pay!) for global payments services. Here, we are interested in collaboration between existing systems, whose trust assumptions may be distinct. We consider learners

⁶⁵The XRP Ledger protocol is sometimes colloquially called *Ripple*. This is not quite correct. XRP Ledger is a protocol; Ripple is a company (which administers a blockchain running the XRP Ledger protocol).

⁶⁶The first author has studied them theoretically and proposed that mathematically, they correspond to distributed logic programming computing open sets in a semitopology. More details are in [Gab24, Gab25b]. In XRP Ledger and Stellar each participant heterogeneously picks their preferred trust assumptions. Semitopologically, the trust assumptions of a participant p correspond to what topologists call the *open neighbourhood system* of p , which is just the set of open neighbourhoods that contain p . We mention this because it pinpoints a precise technical connection to this work: these open neighbourhood systems correspond to the *semifilters* from Definition 3.3.2.

(representing trust assumptions of existing systems) separately from participants (trust domains drawn from one or more collaborating systems). This gives our work a flavour of promoting emergent collaborations between existing chains; not creating a whole new one. If this seems like semantic hair-splitting, it is not: it makes a substantive difference both to the mathematics and the use-cases. Both are legitimate, distinct — dare we say *heterogeneous* — answers to the question ‘How heterogeneity?’.

In distributed systems terms, there are two key distinctions in our approach to heterogeneity:

- We consider a *closed world*: participants know all the learners and all their trust assumptions in advance. XRP Ledger and Stellar use *open world* systems: participants learn trust assumptions as part of the protocol. Open world protocols are more general, but more things are possible in a closed world.
- We specify the *safety* and *liveness* guarantees of our protocols fully in terms of facts known to participants in advance. XRP Ledger and Stellar learners cannot know (in advance) the conditions which guarantee a decision. Indeed, this is likely impossible in an open system.

9.3.3. Epistemic logics

Epistemic logics are logics for reasoning about knowledge. This is a well-researched field; an excellent and comprehensive survey in [BvdH14].

Our logic is a modal temporal logic with an epistemic flavour, in that the notion of possible world $w = (p, x, H) \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ from Definition 3.4.2(2) includes a history structure H which is the knowledge that p has of past events — as well as being a moment in time, since as per Remark 2.3.7 our notion of time equates time with knowledge of past events as being literally equal and encoded in H as an epsilon-structure.

This appears to be new: to the best of our knowledge, this approach to time in general, and in particular history structures as defined in Definitions 2.2.4 and 2.3.5, are novel in the field of epistemic temporal logic. In the epistemic logic literature, if a notion of ‘history’ is relevant it is in the first instance modelled as a *linear* trace of events, and ‘knowledge’ is thought of denotationally as an equivalence class of traces. More sophisticated approaches include using simplicial complexes (where knowledge is modelled as a simplex) and even as an elegant denotation using chromatic hypergraphs [GKL24]. To that canon, this paper adds history structures.

There is another more subtle difference between what we do in this paper and the epistemic logic literature: the latter is historically about studying ... logic, whereas for us the focus is on specific theories: ThyLive, ThyHBB1, ThyHBB2, and ThyHBB3. These use specific axioms in a specific modal logic to embed

specific mechanisms of interaction which we care about for specific protocols. Epistemic logic as traditionally pursued is more about the general theory. This matters, and it gives the mathematics a different flavour and momentum.

We should perhaps also note that even if all the reader cares about *is* general theory, what we do here matters because it is a new example: the use-cases lead us to study new modalities and semantics; namely, \downarrow , \uparrow , and the \diamond family of modalities for learners over semifilters. Thus, this work certainly fits into a rich literature on using logic for epistemology, but it would appear that logic for decentralised heterogeneous computation is its own thing. We hope that this observation will motivate and enrich new research directions in epistemic modal logics.

REMARK 9.3.1. We commented that our logic as an ‘epistemic flavour’. We will unpack what this means concretely, because the connection is quite interesting.

Let \mathbb{M} be a model with history structure \mathbb{H} , and consider a possible world $w = (p, x, H) \in \mathbf{World}(\mathbb{M})$ as per Definition 3.4.2(2). This includes a participant $p \in \mathbf{P}$, a maybe-event $x \in \mathbf{Event}_{\downarrow}$, and a time $H \in \mathbf{History}(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Event})$. The time H is a set of past events and (because we model full information protocols in this paper) H is also what p knows at the possible world w .

This epistemic flavour becomes even more explicit when we give meaning to \diamond in Figure 3. We repeat the clause here, for clarity:

$$p, x, H \models \diamond_{l_1 \dots l_n} \phi \iff \forall (O_1, \dots, O_n) \in \zeta(l_1) \times \dots \times \zeta(l_n). \\ \exists p' \in O_1 \cap \dots \cap O_n. (p', \downarrow, H \models \phi).$$

There are a lot of symbols here, but note that

- we start with p, x, H on the left and
- we end up with $p', \downarrow, H \models \phi$ on the right.

This structure matters, because even if some event (p', E', H) is in \mathbb{H} , the predicate ϕ does not *a priori* get access to that information when we evaluate $p', \downarrow, H \models \phi$.⁶⁷

So, there is implicitly a local view of \mathbb{H} here, in that we change the place of our context from p to p' , but do not update the time to include any events that p' might perform. Indeed, it may even be that $(p', \downarrow, H) \notin \mathbb{H}$! That is: the possible world (p', \downarrow, H) is potentially ‘virtual’, in the sense that it does not actually happen within \mathbb{H} . The tuple (p', \downarrow, H) represents a state of p' as p might imagine it when p is at time H . That is epistemic: it is not necessarily a real state of p' as per \mathbb{H} ; it is a state that p constructs at time H in order to understand (to the best of its H -knowledge) what p' has done.

⁶⁷ ϕ can always gain omniscient access by being $\uparrow\phi'$, but that is a different story.

In this sense, we can view \diamond as logically representing an act of imagination based on current knowledge, and the ‘sideways, imaginary’ step to a (p', \downarrow, H) that need not be in \mathbb{H} , has an explicit epistemic flavour.

Arguably also the end-of-time modality \uparrow does something similar, in the sense that it takes us from (p, x, H) to $(p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H})$, and $(p, \downarrow, \mathbb{H}) \notin \mathbb{H}$. This is a possible world at the end of time, when all events are known.

9.3.4. The ATL logic family

A thread of research is based on branching-time temporal logic to describe concurrent games between agents. This starts with ATL (alternating-time temporal logic) [AHK97] and has been extended in various ways including with epistemic aspects [vdHW03].

There three things to note about the relation with this work.

1. ATL is a logic for talking about agents and their (possibly cooperative) strategies. In contrast the logic in this paper is all about expressing particular protocols. If we think of a protocol as a kind of strategy, then this logic is good for specifying and reasoning about the strategies that ATL-like logics might then reason about.
2. Our logic puts the idea of possibly faulty participants front and centre, reflecting the fact that this is a central concern of designing distributed protocols. ATL-style logics are designed for reasoning about games; a faulty participant could in principle be modelled as a player with extra moves, but for our purposes that is somewhat less natural.
3. Our logic puts quorums and quorum intersection properties, and also temporal properties like ‘the end of time’, front and centre. We are not aware of such an emphasis in the ATL family of logics.

In short, the ATL family of logics are different and designed for different purposes, though these purposes are complementary to the extent that our protocols can correspond to ATL’s strategies.

9.3.5. Event structures

Event Structures are a model of concurrency, where we assume a set of *events*, a so-called *causal relation* on events, and consistency and inconsistency relations between events. An overview is in [WN95].

This looks like it should be related to our notion of history structure from Definition 2.3.5, but in fact they turn out to be quite different.

We have a set **Event** that we call a set of events, but our events are abstract actions; an event in Event Structures corresponds more closely to our notion of an *event tuple* or *possible world*. However, events in the Event Structure sense are unlike event tuples in that they are uninterpreted — all their structure comes from their causal, compatibility, or incompatibility relations — whereas

our event-tuples carry a place and a time, which we use to give meaning to a rich modal logic for reasoning about events at a place, at a time in the past or the future, and about quorums of events and their quorum intersections.

Our modal logic can use implication to express ‘backward rules’ (if X happens then Y must have happened). This looks like it should be related to the causal relation of event structures, but implication is weaker than causation; there may be many Y in the past relative to X and there is no *a priori* sense within the logic that one of them in particular caused X . On the other hand, our modal logic can express ‘forward rules’ (having to do with liveness), and of course because of our focus on distributed systems, our logic includes rich modal structure for reasoning about quorums and quorum intersections.

In short: History Structures and their modal logic share with Event Structures that they talk about ‘events’, and they abstract away from linear / numerical notions of time, but they seem to be different tools created for different purposes.

9.3.6. Trace Diagrams

Our derivation-tree style presentation of history structures (see for example Figure 1) follow a tradition of diagrammatic illustration of runs of distributed systems. Lamport’s diagrams [Lam78, Figure 1] are foundational in this area (and the pedigree extends further; Lamport was following Minkowski space-time diagrams [TW92]). More recent diagram systems for traces include Message Sequence Charts [IT11] and Communication Diagrams in UML [uml17]. These diagrams feature events, happens-before arrows, and *instances* or *processes* which correspond to our *places*.

Unlike our history structures, Message Sequence Charts and Communication Diagrams diagrams admit messages as first-class entities in the diagram — as arrows between instances/processes — and they treat receiving a message as an event. Our setup is equivalent in expressivity, but it arranges the ideas differently. Messages are implicit in the history structure itself: when one place knows about events at another place, this represents a message carrying information about those events having been transmitted. When necessary, we can model times and places where messages were received but nothing else happened using the \downarrow maybe-event, but \downarrow has its own (in our opinion very interesting!) mathematical identity: interpretations of our \downarrow maybe-event are discussed in Subsection 2.3.5, starting with Remark 2.3.15).

Some trace diagrams try to totally order events: for our needs, the additional liberty to let history structures be partially but not totally ordered history is *extremely* useful. This saves us having to reason about trivially equivalent traces differing only in how they interleave events whose order we do not care about, and furthermore, it allows us to avoid modelling processes that act on information that would be unknowable, such as the relative order of unrelated events.

9.3.7. Temporal Logic

Temporal Logic is a well-studied field with a long and distinguished theoretical pedigree and many practical applications. A body of prior work applies Temporal Logic to specify and prove properties of concurrent systems, including distributed systems. In this area, Lamport’s TLA⁺ [Lam02] and its automated proof system [CDL⁺12] have been extremely influential.

Like the modal logic used in this paper, Temporal Logic features *always* and *eventually* modalities, so we can reason about time. Unlike the models used in this paper, TLA⁺ models (and models of related logics) consist of sets of totally ordered traces of events, and possible worlds are just times (more-or-less in the sense of clock-ticks). There is no notion of place nor epsilon-inductive notion of history-structure-as-time.

For our needs, our modal logic’s ability to reason about time and place, and in particular what information is available at each time and place, is extremely useful for the distributed systems we wish to axiomatise and reason about.

9.3.8. Cross-domain state updates

Bracha’s reliable broadcast has consensus number 1, meaning it can be used to update a distributed register (a piece of mutable state) despite byzantine failures, with the caveat that the register may get stuck (never update again) if two simultaneous updates are proposed [Her91]. Sui generalizes this register to a notion of *owned objects*, which can update more quickly and easily (using broadcast) than the rest of Sui’s state (which uses consensus), but which can get stuck if the object’s *owner* misbehaves [BCD⁺24]. This suffices for a cryptocurrency [GKM⁺19] where we imagine a cryptocurrency account as an owned object, in the sense that an owner’s misbehaviour can affect only their own account.

As we discussed in the Introduction, a motivation for heterogeneous protocols is to enable interoperability between distributed systems with different trust models. The Heterogeneous Paxos paper [SWRM21] — which as mentioned in Subsection 9.3.1 we found an error in using the logic in this paper — envisioned atomic transactions across multiple consensus-based distributed systems. In principle, the Heterogeneous Broadcast(s) in this paper could serve the same function and be used the same way: to update Sui-style owned objects simultaneously across multiple domains.

9.3.9. Interoperability of state for blockchain

Interoperability been something of a challenge for blockchains. IBC [Goe20] allows compatible chains to send messages to one another (from one chain’s replicated state machine to the other’s), something most blockchains cannot do by default. Protocols like ICS20 [ics24] use IBC to transfer *wrapped* tokens to other chains, while keeping track of relevant trust assumptions [Cos]. So-called

blockchain bridges take a similar approach, with different details when chains are not compatible with IBC. Such protocols are extremely useful, but they are fundamentally asynchronous point-to-point communication, so they do not and cannot carry the guarantees that broadcast can.

In contrast, Heterogeneous Broadcast ensure that multiple chains receive the same message together, or not at all (specifically, this is *Liveness 2*). We can use this for cross-chain atomic transactions with Sui-style owned objects [BCD⁺24], without requiring a multi-phase commit [Her18] using cross-chain messaging protocols. Broadcast-based cross-chain transactions would be much faster than multi-phase commits. Another advantage of this approach is that in a multi-phase commit, each chain locks state until the other chains respond. If another (involved) chain never responds, everyone else's state remains locked: liveness of all involved state is bounded by the *least live* chain, which is not ideal. Protocols that directly address heterogeneity would be immune or less susceptible to this issue.

9.4. Future work

Several future directions are clear:

1. *Model checking.* A model-checker for our logic would be helpful. This would accelerate the development loop for candidate protocols, because we could write down axioms and some desired correctness properties and ask the machine to find a refuting counterexample if it can, i.e. a model that satisfies the axioms but does not satisfy the correctness properties. This would help with triage of protocols.

We would still want formal proofs of correctness for the final, successful, axiomatisation.

2. *Theorem-proving.* An implementation of our logic in a theorem-prover would likewise be useful, for machine checking these formal proofs, once we have them.
3. *n-round HBB.* We have given three HBB protocols in this paper, but the design space is large and we have by no means exhausted it.

In particular, preliminary investigation suggests that an n -round protocol (where n is the number of learners) would provide stronger agreement guarantees. The intuition is that after n rounds, any hostile behaviour that does exist will become known to all n learners, thus in some sense reducing the n -learner heterogeneous case to something closer to the simpler homogeneous case.

The relevant protocols remain to be developed and checked.

4. *Heterogeneous Paxos.* Continuing the previous point, broadcast is useful for many kinds of algorithms (e.g. payment algorithms, where all we want to do is reliably broadcast actions by individual participants), but *consensus* would be a step up in power. Consensus can be expressed using broadcast [Bra87, Section 4, “The Consensus Protocol”], but a Heterogeneous Paxos algorithm would be useful.

As noted in Subsection 9.3.1 the logic of this paper was used to formalise and find a bug in the correctness proofs of the *heterogeneous paxos* algorithm from [SWRM21]. Its replacement remains to be designed and checked, and if we do then we will use this logic to do so.

5. *Implementation.* It remains to implement a prototype system based on the heterogeneous protocols in this paper or evolved from these (e.g. see previous point). Subsections 9.3.8 (cross-domain state updates) and Subsection 9.3.9 (interoperability) outline some concrete use-cases (these examples are not exhaustive).

6. *Other protocols.* Protocol design is an active area of research. It remains to use the declarative methodology of this paper to study further protocols, and to design new ones.

One particular interest is heterogeneous protocols, but the design space of distributed protocols, heterogeneous or not, is vast. We would put to the reader that each protocol family has its own distinct character, each of which may correspond to a distinct family of logics which remains to be discovered and studied. A lot of interesting theoretical work, with useful practical outcomes, may be possible here, giving declarative formalisations of distributed protocols.

7. *Methodology.* Having now analysed a number of protocols in declarative logical style, including Paxos [GZ25] and both homogeneous and heterogeneous broadcast, the first author puts to the reader that we do not really understand a protocol until we have declaratively axiomatised it.

We may *think* that we do, but the declarative axiomatic method is as much of a step up in clarity and precision applied to distributed protocols, as it was when Euclid invented and applied it to geometry [Euc83]. The first author would argue that our understanding of every protocol could be deepened and enriched by a declarative axiomatisation in the general spirit of this paper, and that we should be applying the techniques in this paper and its companion papers (e.g. [GZ25]) more widely to protocols both large and small.

8. *Morphisms.* An interesting question is what an appropriate notion of morphism of models would be (Definition 3.3.3). Since morphisms are

structure-preserving maps, to answer this question is to decide on the essential structure of a model. This is similar to the question we posed in Remark 3.6.9(2), as to what abstractly the structure of one of our Kripke models is.

One likely answer, given that our modalities refer to quorums and quorums are semitopological (cf. Subsection 3.3.1 and footnote 26), is to decide that we have been studying *semitopological Kripke structures* (i.e. Kripke structures where possible worlds are enriched with notions of points and semitopological structure). This seems natural.

A notion of ‘topological Kripke structure’ has been created [Pym02], though we do not believe they would necessarily be closely related to what we do here. This is future research.

9. *Time-heterogeneity; more heterogeneity.* In Remark 1.1.3 we discussed how in the real world quorums (trust assumptions) vary both by space and by time. In this paper we use a notion of *learner*, each of which identifies a different set of trust assumptions, but this is not the only way to set things up. Notably, we could extend our framework and logic such that trust assumptions can evolve, e.g. they could evolve over time. In fact our protocol ThyHBB3 already includes some element of this, by using logic to express a correlation relation \doteq between learners. Nevertheless, there is clear scope for more exploration of a design space where trust assumptions are allowed to vary even more.

On a related note, this paper is about heterogeneous distributed systems, but (as noted in the previous paragraph) it is not the *most* heterogeneous situation imaginable. So we can ask: what is the most heterogeneous possible mathematically interesting notion of trust? Right now we are clearly nowhere near that limit. We see this because our definitions are full of mathematical structure: semifilters; modal logics; history structures. To be clear: this paper is designed to have structure in search of specific broadcast protocols, not remove it in search of generality for its own sake (though even if all we care about is generality for its own sake, studying specific protocols still informs the shape of the interesting design space). In future work we could go the other way and generalise, generalise, generalise, trying to distil most general possible accounts (there may be more than one) of what heterogeneous trust can mean.

References

- ACTZ24. Orestis Alpos, Christian Cachin, Björn Tackmann, and Luca Zanolini. Asymmetric distributed trust. *Distributed Computing*, 37(3):247–277, 2024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00446-024-00469-1>, doi:10.1007/S00446-024-00469-1. (cit. on pp. 46 and 84.)

- Acz88. Peter Aczel. *Non-wellfounded Set Theory*. Number 14 in CSLI lecture notes. CSLI, 1988. (cit. on p. 15.)
- AHK97. Rajeev Alur, Thomas A. Henzinger, and Orna Kupferman. Alternating-time temporal logic. In *Proceedings 38th Annual Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science*, pages 100–109, 1997. <http://doi.org/10.1109/SFCS.1997.646098>. (cit. on p. 93.)
- AW04. Hagit Attiya and Jennifer Welch. *Fault-Tolerant Consensus*, chapter 5, pages 91–124. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2004. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/0471478210.ch5>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/0471478210.ch5>, doi:10.1002/0471478210.ch5. (cit. on p. 46.)
- BCD+24. Sam Blackshear, Andrey Chursin, George Danezis, Anastasios Kichidis, Lefteris Kokoris-Kogias, Xun Li, Mark Logan, Ashok Menon, Todd Nowacki, Alberto Sonnino, Brandon Williams, and Lu Zhang. Sui lutris: A blockchain combining broadcast and consensus, 2024. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.18042>, arXiv:2310.18042. (cit. on pp. 8, 95, and 96.)
- BdRV01. Patrick Blackburn, Maarten de Rijke, and Yde Venema. *Modal Logic*. Cambridge University Press, 2001. (cit. on pp. 3 and 30.)
- Bra84. Gabriel Bracha. An asynchronous [(n-1)/3]-resilient consensus protocol. In *Proceedings of the Third Annual ACM Symposium on Principles of Distributed Computing*, PODC '84, page 154–162, New York, NY, USA, 1984. Association for Computing Machinery. doi:10.1145/800222.806743. (cit. on pp. 46 and 102.)
- Bra87. Gabriel Bracha. Asynchronous byzantine agreement protocols. *Information and Computation*, 75(2):130–143, 1987. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/089054018790054X>, doi:10.1016/0890-5401(87)90054-X. (cit. on pp. 6, 7, 46, 97, and 102.)
- BvdH14. Nick Bezhanishvili and Wiebe van der Hoek. Structures for epistemic logic. In Alexandru Baltag and Sonja Smets, editors, *Johan van Benthem on Logic and Information Dynamics*, pages 339–380. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2014. Available online at https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-06025-5_12. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-06025-5_12. (cit. on p. 91.)
- CDL+12. Denis Cousineau, Damien Doligez, Leslie Lamport, Stephan Merz, Daniel Ricketts, and Hernán Vanzetto. Tla+ proofs. In Dimitra Giannakopoulou and Dominique Méry, editors, *FM 2012: Formal Methods*, pages 147–154, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2012. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. Extended version: <https://proofs.tlapl.us/doc/web/content/Documentation/Publications/fm-long.pdf>. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-32759-9_14. (cit. on p. 95.)
- CGR11. Christian Cachin, Rachid Guerraoui, and Luís E. T. Rodrigues. *Introduction to Reliable and Secure Distributed Programming (2nd edition)*. Springer, 2011. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-15260-3. (cit. on pp. 4 and 7.)
- CJKR12. Allen Clement, Flavio Junqueira, Aniket Kate, and Rodrigo Rodrigues. On the (limited) power of non-equivocation. In *Proceedings of the 2012 ACM Symposium on Principles of Distributed Computing*, PODC '12, page 301–308, New York, NY, USA, 2012. Association for Computing Machinery. doi:10.1145/2332432.2332490. (cit. on p. 63.)
- CMSK07. Byung-Gon Chun, Petros Maniatis, Scott Shenker, and John Kubiatowicz. Attested append-only memory: making adversaries stick to their word. *SIGOPS Operating Systems Review*, 41(6):189–204, October 2007. doi:10.1145/1323293.1294280. (cit. on p. 63.)
- Cos. Cosmos Developer Portal. IBC token transfer. <https://tutorials.cosmos.network/academy/3-ibc/7-token-transfer.html>. Accessed: 2025-10-29. (cit. on p. 95.)
- DDFN07. Ivan Damgård, Yvo Desmedt, Matthias Fitzi, and Jesper Buus Nielsen. Secure protocols with asymmetric trust. In Kaoru Kurosawa, editor, *Advances in Cryptology - ASIACRYPT 2007, 13th International Conference on the Theory and Application of Cryptology and Information Security, Kuching, Malaysia, December 2-6, 2007, Proceedings*, volume 4833 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 357–375.

- Springer, 2007. doi:10.1007/978-3-540-76900-2_22. (cit. on p. 46.)
- Dev93. Keith Devlin. *The Joy of Sets: Fundamentals of Contemporary Set Theory*. Undergraduate Texts in Mathematics. Springer New York, NY, 2 edition, August 1993. doi:10.1007/978-1-4612-0903-4. (cit. on p. 23.)
- Doc25. Corey Doctorow. *Enshittification: Why Everything Suddenly Got Worse and What To Do About It*. Verso Books, October 2025. (cit. on p. 88.)
- Dol82. Danny Dolev. The byzantine generals strike again. *Journal of Algorithms*, 3(1):14–30, 1982. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0196677482900049>, doi:10.1016/0196-6774(82)90004-9. (cit. on p. 7.)
- Dru67. Peter F. Drucker. *The effective executive*. Harper & Row, 1st edition, 1967. (cit. on p. 88.)
- Euc83. Euclid. In I.L. Heiberg and H. Menge, editors, *Euclidus Opera Ominia*. 1883. Online at <https://farside.ph.utexas.edu/books/Euclid/Euclid.html> (permalink). (cit. on p. 97.)
- Gab24. Murdoch J. Gabbay. *Semitopology: decentralised collaborative action via topology, algebra, and logic*. College Publications, August 2024. ISBN: 9781848904651. (cit. on pp. 27, 28, 46, and 90.)
- Gab25a. Murdoch Gabbay. Semiframes: algebras of heterogeneous consensus, 2025. Journal paper to appear, available online at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.00956>. arXiv:2310.00956. (cit. on p. 28.)
- Gab25b. Murdoch J. Gabbay. Semitopology: a topological approach to decentralised collaborative action. *The Journal of Logic and Computation*, January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1093/logcom/exae050>. doi:10.1093/logcom/exae050. (cit. on pp. 27, 46, and 90.)
- Gar24. James Garson. Modal Logic. In Edward N. Zalta and Uri Nodelman, editors, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Spring 2024 edition, 2024. Available online at <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2024/entries/logic-modal/>. (cit. on pp. 30 and 47.)
- GHR94. Dov M Gabbay, Ian Hodkinson, and Mark Reynolds. *Temporal Logic: Mathematical Foundations and Computational Aspects*, volume 1. Oxford University Press, 07 1994. doi:10.1093/oso/9780198537694.001.0001. (cit. on p. 39.)
- GKL24. Éric Goubault, Roman Kniazev, and Jérémy Ledent. A Many-Sorted Epistemic Logic for Chromatic Hypergraphs. In Aniello Murano and Alexandra Silva, editors, *32nd EACSL Annual Conference on Computer Science Logic (CSL 2024)*, volume 288 of *Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs)*, pages 30:1–30:18, Dagstuhl, Germany, 2024. Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik. URL: <https://drops.dagstuhl.de/entities/document/10.4230/LIPIcs.CSL.2024.30>, doi:10.4230/LIPIcs.CSL.2024.30. (cit. on p. 91.)
- GKM⁺19. Rachid Guerraoui, Petr Kuznetsov, Matteo Monti, Matej Pavlovič, and Dragos-Adrian Seredinschi. The consensus number of a cryptocurrency. In *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM Symposium on Principles of Distributed Computing*, PODC '19, page 307–316, New York, NY, USA, 2019. Association for Computing Machinery. Extended version: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.05574>. doi:10.1145/3293611.3331589. (cit. on pp. 8 and 95.)
- GKWZ03. Dov M. Gabbay, Agnes Kurucz, Frank Wolter, and Michael Zakharyashev. *Many-dimensional modal logics: theory and applications*, volume 148 of *Studies in Logic and the Foundations of Mathematics*. Elsevier, 2003. (cit. on p. 47.)
- Goe20. Christopher Goes. The Interblockchain Communication Protocol: An Overview, May 2020. <https://github.com/cosmos/ibc/blob/8d9d3b6fe7309b034df8457760b3bbd11d24b8e1/archive/papers/2020-05/build/paper.pdf#L2>. (cit. on p. 95.)
- GZ25. Murdoch J. Gabbay and Luca Zanolini. A declarative approach to specifying distributed algorithms using three-valued modal logic, 2025. Journal draft submitted for publication. Available at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.00892>. arXiv:2502.00892. (cit. on pp. 8, 46, 61, 78, and 97.)

- Har25. Anthony Hart. Heterogeneous Broadcast in Lean 4, Nov 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17611734> Direct download link of zip archive: <https://zenodo.org/api/records/17611735/files-archive>. doi:10.5281/zenodo.17611735. (cit. on pp. 6 and 86.)
- Her91. Maurice Herlihy. Wait-free synchronization. *ACM Trans. Program. Lang. Syst.*, 13(1):124–149, January 1991. doi:10.1145/114005.102808. (cit. on pp. 8 and 95.)
- Her18. Maurice Herlihy. Atomic cross-chain swaps. In *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Symposium on Principles of Distributed Computing*, PODC '18, page 245–254, New York, NY, USA, 2018. Association for Computing Machinery. doi:10.1145/3212734.3212736. (cit. on p. 96.)
- HM00. Martin Hirt and Ueli Maurer. Player simulation and general adversary structures in perfect multiparty computation. *Journal of Cryptology*, 13(1):31–60, January 2000. doi:10.1007/s001459910003. (cit. on pp. 46 and 84.)
- HMU07. John E. Hopcroft, Rajeev Motwani, and Jeffrey D. Ullman. *Introduction to Automata Theory, Languages, and Computation*. Pearson/Addison Wesley, Boston, 3rd edition, 2007. Available online (permalink). (cit. on p. 21.)
- ics24. Draft Spec for Multi-Denom Packets ICS20 v2, March 2024. <https://github.com/cosmos/ibc/blob/main/spec/app/ics-020-fungible-token-transfer/README.md>. (cit. on p. 95.)
- ITU11. ITU-T. ITU-T Z.120 (02/2011): Message Sequence chart (MSC). Technical report, ITU-T Recommendations, 2011. <https://handle.itu.int/11.1002/1000/11063> (persistent link to direct download: https://www.itu.int/rec/dologin_pub.asp?lang=e&id=T-REC-Z.120-201102-I!!PDF-E&type=items). (cit. on p. 94.)
- Jec06. Thomas Jech. *Set theory*. Springer, 2006. Third edition. (cit. on p. 14.)
- Joh87. Peter T. Johnstone. *Notes on logic and set theory*. Cambridge University Press, 1987. (cit. on p. 15.)
- Lam78. Leslie Lamport. Time, clocks and the ordering of events in a distributed system. *Communications of the ACM* 21, 7 (July 1978), 558–565. Reprinted in several collections, including *Distributed Computing: Concepts and Implementations*, McEntire et al., ed. IEEE Press, 1984., pages 558–565, July 1978. (cit. on pp. 9, 16, 20, and 94.)
- Lam02. Leslie Lamport. *Specifying Systems: The TLA+ Language and Tools for Hardware and Software Engineers*. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., USA, 2002. Available online at <https://lamport.azurewebsites.net/tla/book.html>. (cit. on p. 95.)
- LSP82. Leslie Lamport, Robert Shostak, and Marshall Pease. The byzantine generals problem. *ACM Trans. Program. Lang. Syst.*, 4(3):382–401, July 1982. <https://doi.org/10.1145/357172.357176>. doi:10.1145/357172.357176. (cit. on p. 4.)
- Mal99. Dahlia Malkhi. Quorum systems. In *Encyclopedia of distributed computing*. Kluwer, 1999. Tutorial chapter, available online at <https://malkhi.com/files/Quorums1999.pdf> (permalink). (cit. on p. 27.)
- Maz15. David Mazières. The Stellar consensus protocol: a federated model for Internet-level consensus. Technical report, Stellar Development Foundation, 2015. <https://www.stellar.org/papers/stellar-consensus-protocol.pdf> (permalink: <https://web.archive.org/web/20240629063518/https://stellar.org/learn/stellar-consensus-protocol>). (cit. on p. 90.)
- MR97. Dahlia Malkhi and Michael Reiter. Byzantine quorum systems. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing*, STOC '97, page 569–578, New York, NY, USA, 1997. Association for Computing Machinery. doi:10.1145/258533.258650. (cit. on p. 27.)
- Pym02. David J. Pym. *Topological Kripke Semantics*, pages 67–87. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2002. doi:10.1007/978-94-017-0091-7_5. (cit. on p. 98.)
- RS96. Michel Raynal and Mukesh Singhal. Logical time: capturing causality in distributed systems. *Computer*, 29(2):49–56, 1996. Available online at <https://decomposition.al/CSE232-2021-09/readings/extra/>

- raynal-singhal-logical-time-survey.pdf (permalink). doi:10.1109/2.485846. (cit. on pp. 9 and 16.)
- SM94. Reinhard Schwarz and Friedemann Mattern. Detecting causal relationships in distributed computations: In search of the holy grail. *Distributed Computing*, 7:149–174, March 1994. Available online at <https://vs.inf.ethz.ch/publ/papers/holygrail.pdf> (permalink). doi:10.1007/BF02277859. (cit. on pp. 9 and 16.)
- SWRM21. Isaac Sheff, Xinwen Wang, Robbert van Renesse, and Andrew C. Myers. Heterogeneous Paxos. In Quentin Bramas, Rotem Oshman, and Paolo Romano, editors, *24th International Conference on Principles of Distributed Systems (OPODIS 2020)*, volume 184 of *Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs)*, pages 5:1–5:17, Dagstuhl, Germany, 2021. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik. ISSN: 1868-8969. URL: <https://drops.dagstuhl.de/opus/volltexte/2021/13490>, doi:10.4230/LIPIcs.OPODIS.2020.5. (cit. on pp. 90, 95, and 97.)
- SYB14. David Schwartz, Noah Youngs, and Arthur Britto. The Ripple Protocol Consensus Algorithm. *Ripple Labs Inc White Paper*, 5(8):151, 2014. (cit. on p. 90.)
- TW92. Edwin F. Taylor and John Archibald Wheeler. *Spacetime Physics, Second Edition*. W. H. Freeman and Co., New York, USA, 1992. Available online at <https://www.oftaylor.com/spacetimephysics/>. (cit. on p. 94.)
- uml17. UML: Unified modeling language. Technical report, Object Management Group Standards Development Organization (OMG SDO), 2017. <https://www.omg.org/spec/UML/2.5.1/>. (cit. on p. 94.)
- vdHW03. Wiebe van der Hoek and Michael Wooldridge. Cooperation, knowledge, and time: Alternating-time temporal epistemic logic and its applications. *Studia Logica*, 75(1):125–157, Oct 2003. doi:10.1023/A:1026185103185. (cit. on p. 93.)
- Wik25. Wikipedia. Kleene fixed-point theorem — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2025. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Kleene_fixed-point_theorem&oldid=1289692885. (cit. on p. 14.)
- WN95. Glynn Winskel and Mogens Nielsen. Models for Concurrency. In *Handbook of Logic in Computer Science*, volume 4. Oxford University Press, 1995. (cit. on p. 93.)

A. Reducing to the homogeneous case

We consider what happens to our axiomatisations and correctness properties when we assume there is just one learner.

We further assume that any three quorums intersect at a sequential participant (in our logic: $\diamond_{III} \text{seq}$), as per the original algorithm by Bracha — see “In this section we show that the protocol in Fig. 1 achieves Asynchronous Byzantine agreement for $0 \leq t < n/3$ ” [Bra84, Subsection 3.2] or “[we present] a randomized consensus protocol that tolerates up to $t < n/3$ Byzantine processes” [Bra87, Page 133].

Given one learner and sequential triple quorum intersections, it is easy to check that:

1. $\models \diamond_{II} \mathbf{T}$ and $\models \diamond_{III} \mathbf{T}$ and $\models \diamond_{II} \text{seq}$ always.
2. In ThyHBB1, every participant is safe.
3. In ThyHBB3, we have (3twined) and ($\neq \text{seq}$). We will also assume that every learner is correlated. Since there is only one learner, and all quorum intersections contain a sequential participant, this is reasonable.

We obtain axiomatisations and correctness properties as below. We sum up the outcome:

1. ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 become textually identical to one another and to the idea of Bracha Broadcast.
2. ThyHBB3 is textually slightly different because of the disjunct in its (Vote?) rule and because of (Vote!), but a very small amount of proof shows that this is only apparent: the disjunct and (Vote!) are logically redundant and can be removed. There is also the (VoteNE) rule, but with our assumptions this is also redundant because it can be derived from (EchoNE) and the other axioms. So ThyHBB3 simplifies to the same thing as ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2.

In conclusion: in the homogeneous case, our three protocols — boringly and reassuringly — reduce to the same core.

A.1. Homogeneous ThyHBB1 and ThyHBB2 (Figures 7 and 9)

Backward rules (HBB)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(Echo?)} \quad & \text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v) \\ \text{(Vote?)} \quad & \text{vote}(v) \Rightarrow \square_l \text{echo}(v) \\ \text{(Deliver?)} \quad & \text{deliver}(v) \Rightarrow \square_l \text{vote}(v) \end{aligned}$$

Other rules

Include axioms of ThyLive from Figure 6

$$\text{(EchoNE)} \quad \text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$$

Forward rules

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(Echo!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{echo}(v') \\ \text{(Vote!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \square_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{vote}(v) \\ \text{(Deliver!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \square_l \text{vote}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(v) \end{aligned}$$

1. *Liveness 1* If $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(v).$$

2. *Liveness 2* If $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \square_l \text{live}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(v).$$

3. *Soundness / Agreement* If $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(v_2) \Rightarrow v_1=v_2.$$

A.2. Homogeneous ThyHBB3 (Figure 11)

Backward rules

- (Echo?) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v)$
 (Vote?) $\text{vote}(v) \Rightarrow (\sqcup_I \text{echo}(v) \vee \diamond \text{vote}(v))$
 (Deliver?) $\text{deliver}(v) \Rightarrow \sqcup_I \text{vote}(v)$

Other rules

Include axioms of ThyLive from Figure 6

- (EchoNE) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$
 (VoteNE) $\text{vote}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{vote}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$

Forward rules

- (Echo!) $(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{echo}(v')$
 (Vote!) $(\text{live} \wedge \sqcup_I \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{vote}(v')$
 (Vote'!) $(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{vote}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{vote}(v')$
 (Deliver!) $(\text{live} \wedge \sqcup_I \text{vote}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(v)$

1. *Liveness 1* If $\models \square_I \text{live}$ and $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \text{deliver}(v).$$

2. *Liveness 2* If $\models \square_I \text{live}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(v).$$

3. *Soundness / Agreement* If $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(v_2) \Rightarrow v_1=v_2.$$

Backward rules (HBB)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(Echo?)} \quad & \text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v) \\ \text{(Vote?)} \quad & \text{vote}(l, v) \Rightarrow \square_l \text{echo}(v) \\ \text{(Deliver?)} \quad & \text{deliver}(l', l, v) \Rightarrow \square_{l'} \text{vote}(l, v) \end{aligned}$$

Other rules

Include axioms of ThyLive from Figure 6

$$\text{(EchoNE)} \quad \text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$$

Forward rules

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(Echo!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \uparrow \text{echo}(v') \\ \text{(Vote!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \square_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{vote}(l, v) \\ \text{(Deliver!)} \quad & (\text{live} \wedge \square_{l'} \text{vote}(l, v)) \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l', l, v) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 9. Theory ThyHBB2 (Definition 7.1.1)

1. *Liveness 1*

If $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \exists v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l, l, v).$$

In words: suppose there is a live l -quorum and suppose precisely one value is proposed. Then if some live participant finds out about that proposed value, then every live participant eventually delivers.

2. *Liveness 2*

If $l'_1, l'_2, l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \diamond_{l'_1 l'_2} \top$ and $\models \square_{l'} \text{live}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l, v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l'_2, l, v).$$

In words: suppose l'_1 and l'_2 have nonempty quorum intersections and there is a live l'_2 -quorum. Then if some participant delivers v for (l'_1, l) then every live participant delivers v for (l'_2, l) .

3. *Soundness / Agreement*

If $l_1, l_2, l'_1, l'_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \diamond_{l_1 l_2} \text{seq}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_1, l_1, v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l'_2, l_2, v_2) \Rightarrow v_1=v_2.$$

In words: suppose l_1 and l_2 have sequential quorum intersections. Then if some participant delivers v_1 for (l'_1, l_1) and another delivers v_2 for (l'_2, l_2) , then $v_1 = v_2$.

Figure 10. Correctness properties for ThyHBB2 (Theorem 7.1.3)

Backward rules

- (Echo?) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{propose}(v)$
(Vote?) $\text{vote}(l, v) \Rightarrow (\Box_l \text{echo}(v) \vee \exists l' \doteq l. \diamond \text{vote}(l', v))$
(Deliver?) $\text{deliver}(l, v) \Rightarrow \Box_l \text{vote}(l, v)$

Other rules

Include axioms of ThyLive from Figure 6

- (EchoNE) $\text{echo}(v) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \text{echo}(v') \Rightarrow v=v'$
(VoteNE) $\text{vote}(l, v) \Rightarrow \Downarrow \text{vote}(l', v') \Rightarrow l=l' \Rightarrow v=v'$
(3twined) $\diamond_{ll'l'} \mathbf{T}$
(\doteq seq) $l \doteq l' \Rightarrow \diamond_{ll'} \text{seq}$
(\doteq ↓) $l \doteq l' \Rightarrow \Downarrow (l \doteq l')$
(\doteq symm) $l \doteq l' \Rightarrow l' \doteq l$
(\doteq tran) $l \doteq l' \Rightarrow l' \doteq l'' \Rightarrow l \doteq l''$

Forward rules

- (Echo!) $(\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \Uparrow \text{echo}(v')$
(Vote!) $(\text{live} \wedge \Box_l \text{echo}(v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \Uparrow \text{vote}(l, v')$
(Vote'!) $(\text{live} \wedge \Uparrow (l \doteq l') \wedge \diamond \text{vote}(l', v)) \Rightarrow \exists v'. \Uparrow \text{vote}(l, v')$
(Deliver!) $(\text{live} \wedge \Box_l \text{vote}(l, v)) \Rightarrow \Uparrow \text{deliver}(l, v)$

Above, \Uparrow , \Downarrow , and \Downarrow are from Figure 5 and means ‘at every event at p ’, ‘at some event at p ’, and ‘at every past event at p ’ respectively. \doteq is the correlation relation from Subsection 8.1.

Figure 11. Theory ThyHBB3 (Definition 8.2.1)

1. *Liveness 1*

If $l \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $\models \square_l \text{live}$ and $\models \exists_1 v. \diamond \text{propose}(v)$ then

$$\models \diamond (\text{live} \wedge \diamond \text{propose}(v)) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \text{deliver}(l, v).$$

In words: suppose there is a live l -quorum and suppose precisely one value is proposed. Then if some live participant finds out about that proposed value, then every live participant eventually delivers.

2. *Liveness 2*

If $l_1, l_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \square (l_1 \doteq l_2)$ and $\models \square_{l_2} \text{live}$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l_1, v) \Rightarrow \text{live} \Rightarrow \uparrow \text{deliver}(l_2, v).$$

In words: suppose l_1 and l_2 are always and everywhere correlated and there is a live l_2 -quorum. Then if some participant delivers v for l_1 then every live participant delivers v for l_2 .

3. *Soundness / Agreement*

If $l_1, l_2 \in \mathbf{Learner}$ and $v_1, v_2 \in \mathbf{Value}$ and $\models \square (l_1 \doteq l_2)$ then

$$\models \diamond \text{deliver}(l_1, v_1) \Rightarrow \diamond \text{deliver}(l_2, v_2) \Rightarrow v_1 = v_2.$$

In words: suppose l_1 and l_2 are always everywhere correlated. Then if some participant delivers v_1 for l_1 and another delivers v_2 for l_2 , then $v_1 = v_2$.

Figure 12. Correctness properties for ThyHBB3 (Theorem 8.2.3)